

D2.3 - Best practices for enhanced EPC

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) systems, emerging Building Renovation Passport (BRP) approaches, and supporting technical and governance frameworks across partner countries, complemented by insights from selected EU-funded projects.

The analysis shows that all partner countries have established EPC systems aligned with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), based on national methodologies, regulatory frameworks, and certified experts. While differences exist in calculation methods, indicators, and implementation models, a common trend can be observed: EPC systems are gradually evolving from static certification tools towards more comprehensive instruments that support renovation planning and long-term decarbonization objectives.

Across countries, there is a clear move towards expanding EPC systems with additional functionalities, including improved data management, climate-adapted calculations, and the introduction of staged renovation approaches. In parallel, Building Renovation Passports are being developed as complementary tools, typically building on existing EPC frameworks and aiming to support step-by-step renovation pathways.

The review of technical solutions highlights increasing digitalization and integration of data. Centralized EPC registries, enhanced calculation models, and user-oriented outputs are already widely implemented, while further developments are expected to focus on interoperability, digital building logbooks, and more advanced decision-support tools.

EU-funded projects play an important role in testing innovative approaches and bridging the gap between policy and implementation. They contribute to the development of practical methodologies, digital solutions, and stakeholder engagement models, while also facilitating knowledge exchange and alignment across countries.

Based on the analysis, several key best practices have been identified. These include the gradual upgrading of EPC systems, the use of standardized and regularly updated methodologies, the integration of multiple performance indicators, and stronger links between technical assessment, policy frameworks, and financial instruments. Effective governance models combine national regulatory structures with qualified experts, dedicated institutions, and multi-level implementation approaches.

This report on best practices for enhanced EPCs has been developed under the same work package than D2.1 “Guidelines framework for data collection, processing, validation and sharing”. Various findings present in this document

(e.g., EPC outcome metrics, KPIs, and identified workflows for data submission and quality checks) are used as valid inputs to support and inform that guidelines framework of D2.1 , ensuring that it reflects the practical lessons and priorities identified through this best-practice review.

Overall, the findings indicate a clear transition towards more integrated, flexible, and user-oriented systems that support building renovation and align with EU climate and energy objectives.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
BRP	Building Renovation Passport
BIM	Building Information Modeling
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
BLD	Building Digital Logbooks
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
kWh	Kilowatt-hour
m ²	Square metre

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this task is to systematically identify, analyze and compare existing initiatives across Europe related to enhanced Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Building Renovation Passports (BRPs). In line with the objectives of the project, the task aims to provide a comprehensive overview of currently available solutions, methodologies, and approaches that contribute to improving the role of EPCs as instruments supporting the energy transition in the building sector.

The analysis covers a broad spectrum of initiatives, including market-ready solutions developed by private companies, tools and frameworks implemented by public authorities, as well as innovative approaches emerging from research activities and European-funded projects. Attention is given to solutions that enhance the usability, reliability, and strategic value of EPCs, especially in relation to long-term renovation planning and decision-making processes.

Building on this mapping exercise, the task seeks to identify best practices and transferable approaches that demonstrate a high potential for replication and upscaling. At the same time, it aims to highlight existing gaps, limitations, and opportunities for further development, particularly in relation to the integration of EPCs with BRPs, digitalization of building data, and the inclusion of advanced indicators.

The main outcome of this task is a structured report that consolidates the findings into a curated collection of best practices, accompanied by an analytical assessment of strategies and solutions that can be further developed, adapted, or integrated within the framework of the project. In this way, the task provides a solid knowledge base to support subsequent project activities and contributes to the overall objective of strengthening EPC systems as key tools for accelerating building renovation across Europe.

1.2 Definition of enhanced EPCs and Building Renovation Passports

Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are a key policy instrument introduced under the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), which establishes the European regulatory framework for assessing and communicating the energy performance of buildings. The last EPBD recast entered into force on 28 May 2024 and will need to be transposed into national laws by 29 May 2026.

Conventional Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) have traditionally functioned as compliance-oriented documents, primarily based on calculated

energy performance indicators and used at specific moments such as construction, sale or rental of buildings. Their main purpose has been to provide a standardised assessment of building energy performance and basic recommendations for improvement.

Enhanced EPCs, however, expand this traditional role by transforming EPCs into more dynamic, digital and user-oriented instruments that support renovation planning and the energy transition. They go beyond standard energy classification by integrating structured and machine-readable data (e.g. XML formats), improved and more comprehensive indicators, tailored renovation recommendations, and interoperability with external tools and databases such as digital building logbooks, financing schemes or policy monitoring systems. In this sense, enhanced EPCs are increasingly understood not only as certification instruments, but as data-driven tools supporting decision-making, renovation roadmaps and building performance management.

This evolution is further reinforced by the recast EPBD (2024), which promotes digitalised, interoperable and more actionable EPC systems, strengthening their role as a foundation for enhanced EPC approaches and their future integration with Building Renovation Passports.¹

Closely linked to this evolution is the concept of the Building Renovation Passport (BRP). A BRP is defined as a structured, long-term roadmap for the step-by-step renovation of a building, tailored to its specific characteristics and conditions. Unlike traditional EPC recommendations, which are often generic and static, BRPs provide a plan of renovation measures, including timing and prioritization of interventions, expected energy and emission savings, cost estimates, and links to financing options. The EPBD (2024) further specifies the content of BRPs, including information on renovation steps, energy performance improvements, greenhouse gas reductions, lifecycle considerations, and broader aspects such as circularity, indoor environmental quality and climate resilience. BRPs are intended to support building owners and stakeholders in making informed decisions and avoiding lock-in effects by ensuring that renovation steps are coherent and aligned over time.

The relationship between enhanced EPCs and BRPs is increasingly recognized as complementary. While EPCs provide a standardized assessment of the performance of building, BRPs offer a strategic and operational planning instrument. The integration of the two is a key objective of recent EU policy developments, particularly within the framework of the recast EPBD, which promotes the digitalization of EPC systems, the development of Building

¹ Directive (EU) 2024/1275 on the energy performance of buildings, available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202401275&pk_keyword=Energy&pk_content=Directive

Renovation Passports, and the creation of integrated building data ecosystems, including digital building logbooks².

In this context, enhanced EPCs can serve as a foundation for BRP development by providing reliable, standardized and interoperable input data, while BRPs extend EPC functionality towards actionable and long-term renovation strategies. Together, these instruments represent a shift from static assessment towards dynamic, data-driven and user-centric approaches, which are essential for accelerating the decarbonization of the European building stock.

1.3 Methodology and sources

The methodology applied in this task is based on a structured comparative analysis of EPC systems across selected European countries, with a particular focus on their level of digital maturity, data accessibility, and potential for integration with advanced tools such as Building Renovation Passports (BRPs). A key methodological decision was to prioritize countries with more advanced EPC frameworks, in order to identify best practices that can effectively support the objectives of the project. To ensure a consistent and objective selection, a specific technical criterion was introduced, namely the availability of EPC data export in .xml format.

The use of .xml export functionality was considered a critical indicator for several reasons. Firstly, it reflects the presence of structured and machine-readable digital data, which enables further processing, interoperability, and integration with external systems. Secondly, such digital information can be effectively used by national authorities and policymakers to support evidence-based decision-making, including improvements in legislation, optimization of funding schemes, and enhancement of certification processes, in line with EU policy objectives.

Furthermore, the availability of EPC data in .xml format allows for:

- advanced data analysis and benchmarking,
- automation of data processing,
- integration with digital building logbooks and renovation planning tools, and
- improved monitoring of energy performance at national and regional levels.

² Directive (EU) 2024/1275 on the energy performance of buildings, available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202401275&pk_keyword=Energy&pk_content=Directive

From a methodological perspective, the presence of .xml export capability was therefore used as a proxy indicator of system standardization and digitalization maturity. Countries meeting this criterion are assumed to have more technologically advanced and interoperable EPC systems, making them particularly relevant for in-depth analysis. However, the analysis did not aim to cover all countries where such functionality exists. Instead, a targeted selection approach was applied. Priority was given to the countries directly involved in the project pilot activities, as these represent the primary testing environment for the proposed methodologies and tools. This ensures that the analysis is directly linked to practical implementation and supports the development of replicable solutions. In addition, a limited number of other countries were selected based on their level of advancement in EPC digitalization, availability of relevant data, and representativeness of different regulatory and technical approaches. This allowed for a balanced comparison across diverse systems while maintaining a manageable scope of analysis.

In addition to this selection criterion, the methodology also included a review of available software solutions for EPC generation. This involved analysing their main functionalities, data handling capabilities, and level of digital integration. The findings of this analysis further supported the identification of countries with more advanced systems and reinforced the relevance of the .xml-based selection approach.

Moreover, the study incorporated a review of European research and innovation projects addressing enhanced EPCs and Building Renovation Passports. These projects provided valuable insights into emerging methodologies, digital tools, and policy directions, which were considered when interpreting national practices and identifying transferable solutions.

The main sources used in this task include:

- National legislation and official EPC frameworks of the analysed countries,
- National EPC registries and institutional websites,
- Technical documentation and software solutions for EPC generation,
- EU-funded projects and research initiatives related to EPC enhancement and BRPs, and
- Relevant European policy frameworks and guidelines.

Overall, this methodology ensures a targeted and evidence-based analysis, focusing on the most relevant and forward-looking systems. The selection of countries based on the availability of .xml export is therefore justified as it

directly supports the project's ambition to advance data-driven, interoperable, and future-proof EPC systems.

2 MAPPING OF EXISTING INITIATIVES IN EUROPE

2.1 National initiatives of EPC and BRP in pilot countries

2.1.1 Poland

2.1.1.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Poland, the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is a key instrument for assessing the energy efficiency of the building stock, regulated primarily by the Act of 29 August 2014 on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Dz.U. 2014 poz. 1200). This act establishes the legal framework for energy performance of buildings in Poland. It provides information about when energy performance certificates (EPCs) are required, who can prepare certificates, how they must be calculated, and how they are registered in the national system (CRCEB database). It implements EU requirements to improve building energy efficiency and transparency.

The issuance of an EPC is mandatory in several specific scenarios:

- Property sale/transaction: The seller must provide the certificate to the buyer (the notary records this in the notarial deed).
- Rental of flat/house: The landlord must provide a copy of the certificate to the tenant when signing the lease agreement.
- Completion of construction: The investor must attach the certificate to the notification of completion or the application for an occupancy permit.
- Single family house construction: Completion of the construction of a new single-family home larger than 70 m² requires an EPC
- Existing public buildings: An EPC is required for public buildings or parts of buildings used by courts, prosecutor's offices, and public administration offices, where the area used by these authorities exceeds 250 m² and are frequently visited. There are several exemptions: buildings that are protected monuments under heritage laws, buildings used as places of worship or for religious activities, industrial or agricultural buildings without energy-consuming installations (except for built-in lighting), residential buildings used for no more than four months per year, detached buildings with a usable area below 50 m², and farm buildings where the primary energy consumption (EP) does not exceed 50 kWh/m²/year.

In Poland, the methodology for calculating EPCs is based on a quasi-steady approach with monthly calculations that are then aggregated to annual values. The building is divided into thermal zones, and for each zone, the energy demand for heating, cooling (if applicable), and domestic hot water is

calculated. The method considers building envelope characteristics (walls, roof, floor), ventilation, and energy systems such as heating, cooling, and hot water supply. Local climate data, typically monthly average temperatures, are used in the calculations. The monthly energy demands are summed to produce annual indicators including EP (primary energy demand), EK (final energy demand), and EU (useful energy demand). This methodology is defined in the Minister of Development and Technology's regulation and is designed to comply with EU EPBD requirements while being practical for official certification and registration in the CRCEB (*Establishment of the Central Register of Energy Performance of Buildings*) system. An expert issuing an EPC analyses the building's actual technical documentation. This documentation should include material characteristics of main building elements (such as walls, roof, floors, windows), their actual thermal transmittance factor (thermal conductivity coefficient λ [W/mK]), blueprints/floor plans with dimensions, installed technical system for HVAC. There is no obligation for the expert to visit the building in person. Nevertheless, when any information is missing, the expert must perform on-site visual inspection and checks. The expert assumes full responsibility for the accuracy and validity of the EPC.

Poland is currently in the process of introducing, updating, and aligning its Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) formats with the EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). As part of this process, energy classes are to be introduced, and Poland is obliged to implement them along with related adjustments by 29 May 2026. However, the development of supporting legislation and technical standards is currently delayed, which may affect the full implementation and operational readiness of the new system. The EU requires Member States to establish a Building Renovation Passport (BRP) system, but in Poland this is not yet mandatory. Currently, the work is at the conceptual and strategic stage, and it will be implemented as a framework and guidance tool.

2.1.1.2 Energy-performance indicators

Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) in Poland requires a set of calculations that quantify a building's energy use and environmental impact. Following indicators are mandatory for calculations:

- Annual Useful Energy (EU [kWh/m²*year]): Represents the energy needed to ensure comfort and functionality (heating, cooling, hot water, ventilation, lighting), excluding system losses-reflects the building's inherent demand.

- Annual Final Energy (EK [kWh/m²*year]): Represents the energy delivered to building systems to meet demand, including internal losses like heat in pipes or electricity for pumps and fans.
- Annual Non-renewable Primary Energy (EP [kWh/m²*year]): Represents the total non-renewable energy required, including upstream losses from extraction, transport, and conversion-shows environmental impact.
- CO₂ Emissions [tCO₂/m²*year]: Represents the amount of CO₂ released due to energy use, based on energy type and quantity-indicates environmental footprint.
- Share of renewable energy sources in annual energy demand (U_{oze} [%]): Represents the percentage of energy from renewable sources; higher values mean less fossil fuel use and lower emissions.

Poland is preparing to introduce energy classes for buildings as part of its Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) system. This measure, required under the EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), will classify buildings according to their overall energy efficiency, with the classification based on the building's Annual non-renewable primary energy demand (EP). The energy classes will provide clear indicators of performance for owners, buyers, and tenants. The implementation of energy classes is scheduled to take effect by 29 May 2026, ensuring that all EPCs issued in Poland will reflect this standardized classification.

Energy class	EP coefficient (kWh/m ² ·year)	Requirements
A+	≤0	An energy-positive building. It must generate more energy from renewable sources (e.g., a large photovoltaic system) than it consumes. Passive standard + positive energy balance.
A	0 < EP ≤ 63	Zero-emission building. Passive house or ultra-energy-efficient standard. No on-site combustion of fossil fuels. Heating via heat pump or district heating + heat recovery + renewable energy sources.
B	63 < EP ≤ 75	Current standard i.e. Technical Conditions for buildings 2021, ("Dz.U. 2022 poz. 1225 ^[1] "). Most new buildings built after 2021. Very good insulation, energy-efficient windows, and often a heat pump or gas heating with significant support from renewable energy sources.
C	75 < EP ≤ 94	A standard similar to Technical Conditions for buildings 2017 ("WT 2017"). The buildings are well insulated (e.g., 15–20 cm of polystyrene foam), but are heated by gas or a pellet boiler

		without the use of solar panels.
D	$94 < EP \leq 113$	Average standard. Buildings constructed between 2000 and 2015 that have undergone partial energy retrofitting. Average wall insulation; older models of gas or oil boilers.
E	$113 < EP \leq 131$	Low-standard, older buildings, typically from the 1990s, with minimal insulation (for example, only 5 cm of expanded polystyrene) and outdated heating systems. These buildings are characterized by high energy bills.
F	$131 < EP \leq 150$	These are buildings in very poor condition, urgently needing renovation. They typically lack roof or wall insulation, have old windows, and rely on outdated solid-fuel heating systems. Many of these buildings also suffer from internal problems such as mold and fungal growth.
G	> 150	Approximately 15% of buildings have the lowest energy efficiency ratings. These are typically older, poorly insulated houses, including prefabricated buildings from the 1970s and 1980s, often heated with coal-fired stoves and experiencing significant heat loss.

Figure 1 Standardized classification in Poland (energy classes)

The template for Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is a formalized and it is provided by the Ministry of Development and Technology. All the templates are provided on the [website of the Ministry](#) in-pdf format. The template is uniform for residential buildings, building units (apartments), and non-residential buildings, taking into account the specifics of the installations.

WZÓR ŚWIADECTWA CHARAKTERYSTYKI ENERGETYCZNEJ BUDYNKU

ŚWIADECTWO CHARAKTERYSTYKI ENERGETYCZNEJ BUDYNKU			
Numer świadectwa ¹⁾			
Oceniany budynek			
Rodzaj budynku ²⁾		Zdjęcie budynku	
Przeznaczenie budynku ³⁾			
Adres budynku			
Budynek, o którym mowa w art. 3 ust. 2 ustawy ⁴⁾			
Rok oddania do użytkowania budynku ⁵⁾			
Metoda wyznaczania charakterystyki energetycznej ⁶⁾			
Powierzchnia pomieszczeń o regulowanej temperaturze powietrza (powierzchnia ogrzewana lub chłodzona) A _v [m ²]			
Powierzchnia użytkowa [m ²]			
Ważne do (rrrr-mm-dd)⁷⁾			
Stacja meteorologiczna, według której danych jest wyznaczana charakterystyka energetyczna ⁸⁾			
Ocena charakterystyki energetycznej budynku¹⁰⁾			
Wskaźniki charakterystyki energetycznej	Oceniany budynek	Wymagania dla nowego budynku według przepisów techniczno-budowlanych	
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na energię użytkową	EU = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)		
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na energię końcową ¹¹⁾	EK = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)		
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na nieodnawialną energię pierwotną ¹¹⁾	EP = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)	EP = ... kWh/(m ² · rok)	
Jednostkowa wielkość emisji CO ₂	E _{CO₂} = ... t CO ₂ /(m ² · rok)		
Udział odnawialnych źródeł energii w rocznym zapotrzebowaniu na energię końcową	U _{ren} = ... %		
Wskaźnik rocznego zapotrzebowania na nieodnawialną energię pierwotną EP [kWh/(m ² · rok)] ↓ Oceniany budynek ↑ Wymagania dla nowego budynku			
Obliczeniowa roczna ilość używanego nośnika energii lub energii przez budynek¹²⁾			
System techniczny	Rodzaj nośnika energii lub energii	Ilość nośnika energii lub energii	Jednostka/(m² · rok)
Ogrzewania	1) n)		
Przygotowania ciepłej wody użytkowej	1) n)		
Chłodzenia	1) n)		
Wbudowanej instalacji oświetlenia ¹¹⁾	1) n)		
Sporzadzający świadectwo:			
Imię i nazwisko: Nr wpisu do wykazu ¹³⁾ :		Podpis	
Data wystawienia świadectwa:			

Wygenerowano z centralnego rejestru charakterystyki energetycznej

Figure 2: The visual identity of first page for EPC in Poland.

Key elements of the certificate template (page by page):

- Page 1: Certificate number, general assessment (EP and EK indicators), building data (address, year of construction, floor area), and a declaration of system generation.
- Page 2: Technical and functional characteristics, including detailed calculations of energy demand for individual systems (heating, ventilation, cooling, domestic hot water).
- Page 3: Guidance on the cost-effectiveness of energy modernization and proposed recommendations.
- Page 4: Explanations and a list of legal acts.

2.1.1.3 Qualification of certifiers

In Poland, the person authorized to prepare Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) is technically referred to as an authorized expert (often colloquially called an "auditor"). Since the deregulation of the profession, there is no longer a requirement to pass a separate state exam, provided the candidate meets specific educational or professional criteria. To issue energy certificates in Poland, a person must fulfil one of the following requirements:

1. Technical Higher Education: Hold a degree (Engineer, Architect, Master of Engineering, or Master) in fields such as Construction, Architecture, Environmental Engineering, Power Engineering, or related technical disciplines (EQF level 6).
2. Postgraduate Studies: If a person has a university degree in a different field, they must complete specialized postgraduate studies focused on energy auditing or the energy performance of buildings.
3. Building Qualifications: Hold "Building Licence" (*uprawnienia budowlane*) as defined by the Polish Construction Law. "Building Licence" in Poland are official professional licenses that allow a person to independently perform technical functions in construction, such as designing buildings or managing construction works. They are granted after meeting strict requirements, including relevant higher education (usually in engineering), professional practice, and passing a state exam. These licenses are regulated by Polish construction law and supervised by professional chambers.

In addition to these educational requirements, the candidate must have full legal capacity and a clean criminal record regarding specific offences (such as crimes against property, documents, or economic turnover). It is also important to note that expert registered in the system must have mandatory professional liability insurance (OC). This insurance protects the property owner in case of making a significant error in the calculations or the assessment of the building's energy performance.

Experts are allowed to issue an EPC only if they are officially registered in the national database: the Central Register of Energy Performance of Buildings (CRCEB). The list of the experts that can issue the certificates is publicly available.

2.1.1.4 Other initiatives

In Poland, the development of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) system is increasingly supported by initiatives related to the digitalization of building data, the improvement of EPC methodologies, and the gradual

introduction of concepts such as Building Renovation Passports (BRP) and Digital Building Logbooks (DBL). These developments are mainly driven by regulatory changes, the expansion of national data systems, and participation in European research and innovation projects.

A key supporting element is the ongoing digitalization of building-related data through several national registries. In addition to EPC-related systems, Poland has established the Central Emission Register of Buildings (CEEB), operated by the Main Office of Building Control. This registry collects detailed information on heating systems and fuel types used in buildings across the country. While it is not directly integrated with the EPC framework, it is an important step towards developing a broader digital building logbook by collecting data related to energy use and emissions. The existence of separate registries shows a gradual move towards more complete data systems, although full interoperability and standardized data exchange have not yet been achieved.

At the strategic level, Poland has adopted the Long-Term Renovation Strategy for Buildings, which sets a roadmap for reducing emissions from the building stock by 2050. The strategy highlights the need for better data availability, improved monitoring of building performance, and the development of tools that support long-term renovation planning. Although Building Renovation Passports are not yet formally implemented, the strategy provides a policy basis for their future introduction, especially in relation to staged renovation and better integration of building data.

Poland is also involved in European Union-funded projects aimed at improving the role of EPCs and linking them with broader digital and strategic tools. One of the key initiatives is the iBRoad2EPC project, which addresses the limited long-term usefulness of traditional EPCs by adding elements of Building Renovation Passports and Digital Building Logbooks. The project supports the transformation of EPCs into tools that can help plan renovations step by step rather than serving only as static assessments.

The integration of life-cycle assessment (LCA) into the building sector in Poland is still limited and has not yet been included in EPC methodologies or national regulations. However, LCA is increasingly recognized in research and policy discussions, including in the context of European frameworks such as Level(s), as an important element of future building assessment systems. Overall, Poland's approach reflects a transitional stage in the development of EPC-related tools. While the country has established important elements of digital infrastructure and strategic planning, the integration of EPCs with renovation passports, digital logbooks, and life-cycle-based assessment is still in progress. Current initiatives show a clear direction towards more complete and data-driven systems, but their implementation is not yet fully integrated.

2.1.2 Slovenia

2.1.2.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Slovenia, the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is a key instrument for assessing the energy performance of the building stock. The system is regulated through a combination of legislative acts, including the Energy Efficiency Act (ZURE) and specific by-laws governing the methodology for EPC calculation and issuance. The system is designed to provide transparent information to property owners, tenants, and buyers regarding the energy performance of buildings and to encourage energy-saving measures.

The issuance of an EPC is mandatory in several specific scenarios:

- Property Transactions: Owners must obtain an EPC for a building or individual building unit when selling or renting the property for a period exceeding one year.
- New Constructions: A valid EPC is required for all newly constructed buildings.
- Public and Frequently Visited Buildings: An EPC is mandatory for buildings with a total usable floor area exceeding 250 m² that are owned or used by public sector entities.

The Energy Performance Certificate remains valid for a period of ten years. However, property owners have the option to obtain a new certificate before this period expires, particularly following significant energy renovations that improve the building's performance³.

Types of Certificates:

Slovenian legislation distinguishes between two primary types of certificates based on the assessment methodology:

- Calculated EPC: This is mandatory for all residential buildings and new constructions. The methodology is consistent with the calculations required for obtaining a building permit. It relies on technical documentation reflecting the actual state of the building, including dimensions, envelope construction (walls, materials, window properties), and installed technical systems. In cases where documentation is missing, experts must perform on-site measurements and visual inspections.

³ Energy Efficiency Act (ZURE), Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia, No. 158/2020, including subsequent amendments

- **Measured EPC:** This type is intended specifically for existing non-residential buildings. It is generated based on actual energy consumption data, typically requiring records (such as invoices) from the past three years.

While the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) recast envisions more holistic and dynamic tools, the Building Renovation Passport (BRP) is not yet a mandatory document within the current Slovenian legislative framework. Current initiatives focus on enhancing the existing EPC schemes to better support extensive renovations, as surveys indicate that many end-users do not yet perceive the standard EPC as a sufficient tool for planning major building upgrades.

2.1.2.2 Energy-performance indicators

The energy performance of a building in Slovenia is determined through a set of standardized indicators that reflect the building's thermal characteristics, the efficiency of its technical building systems (TBS), and its environmental impact. Following the latest national legislation (Pravilnik o učinkoviti rabi energije v stavbah – PURES 3), the indicators differ slightly depending on whether the EPC is issued based on a calculation (calculated EPC) or based on actual energy consumption (measured EPC).

The calculated EPC is based on the physical properties of the building and its systems, independent of user behavior. The primary indicators include⁴:

- **Annual Heating Demand ($Q'_{H,nd,an}$):** Represents the specific annual heat required for heating the building per unit of useful floor area ($\text{kWh/m}^2\text{a}$). It reflects the quality of the building envelope.
- **Delivered Energy ($E'_{del,an}$):** Represents the specific unweighted annual energy delivered to the building for the operation of all technical building systems (heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water, and lighting) ($\text{kWh/m}^2\text{a}$).
- **Primary Energy ($E'_{Ptot,an}$):** Represents the specific total annual primary energy required for the operation of technical building systems ($\text{kWh/m}^2\text{a}$). This indicator accounts for the efficiency of energy transformation and distribution from the source to the building.

⁴ Pravilnik o metodologiji izdelave in izdaji energetskih izkaznic stavb, Official Gazette of RS, No. 4/23. Available at: <https://pisrs.si/pregledPredpisa?id=PRAV14831>

- CO₂ Emissions ($M_{CO_2,an}/A_{use}$): Indicates the environmental footprint of the building's energy use, expressed as specific annual emissions (kg/m²a).

The measured EPC is used for existing non-residential buildings and is based on actual energy records from the previous three years. The key indicators are:

- Total Delivered Energy: The actual annual delivered energy per unit of conditioned floor area (kWh/m²a).
- Delivered Electricity: Specifically tracks the annual electrical energy consumption per unit of conditioned floor area (kWh/m²a).
- Primary Energy (Non-renewable part): Represents the portion of primary energy derived from non-renewable sources required for the operation of technical building systems (kWh/m²a).
- CO₂ Emissions: Similar to the calculated EPC, it reflects the specific annual greenhouse gas emissions (kg/m²a).

In Slovenia, buildings are categorized into energy classes from A1 to G, based on their annual heating demand ($Q'_{H,nd,an}$). The classification provides a quick visual representation of the building's efficiency:

- Class A1 (0 - 10 kWh/m²a): Represents buildings with maximum energy efficiency, where the thermal energy demand for heating is virtually negligible.
- Class A2 (10 - 15 kWh/m²a): Represents buildings with very low energy consumption, meeting the highest standards of modern sustainable construction with minimal heat loss.
- Class B1 (15 - 25 kWh/m²a): High-efficiency buildings, typical for modern, well-insulated new constructions.
- Class B2 (25 - 35 kWh/m²a): High-efficiency buildings, typical for modern, well-insulated new constructions.
- Class C (35 - 60 kWh/m²a): Energy-efficient buildings that meet the standard requirements for renovated or new buildings.
- Class D (60 - 105 kWh/m²a): Solid energy performance, often achieved in older buildings with partially renovated envelopes.
- Class E (105 - 150 kWh/m²a): Represent energy-inefficient buildings.
- Class F (150 - 210 kWh/m²a): Represent energy-inefficient buildings.

- Class G (over 210 kWh/m²a) identifies the worst-performing buildings with no insulation and outdated heating systems, which are the primary targets for deep energy renovation.

To ensure transparency and a better understanding of the differences between the two assessment methodologies, the figure below illustrates the visual identity and key elements of the energy performance certificates used in Slovenia. The image on the left shows the calculated EPC, which is based on the physical characteristics of the building and its systems. The image on the right displays the measured EPC, which reflects the actual energy consumption of the occupants over a specific period.

Figure 3: Comparison of the visual identity for Calculated EPC (left) and Measured EPC (right) in Slovenia

2.1.2.3 Qualification of certifiers

The integrity and accuracy of the Energy Performance Certification system in Slovenia rely on a rigorous qualification process for independent experts. According to the Energy Efficiency Act (ZURE), specifically Article 40, energy performance certificates (EPCs) and inspections of technical systems can only be performed by licensed professionals who meet strict educational, professional, and training criteria.

To become a licensed independent expert for issuing EPCs, an individual must fulfill the following statutory requirements:

- **Educational Background:** Candidates are required to hold at least a Level 7 degree under the Slovenian Qualifications Framework, specializing in relevant fields of study. These include engineering, architecture, spatial planning, construction, or physics.
- **Professional Experience:** Applicants must demonstrate at least two years of relevant work experience in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energy sources in buildings, gained after obtaining their formal education.
- **Specialized Training:** Within the five years prior to applying for a license, the candidate must successfully complete a mandatory training program for independent EPC experts, which includes a formal examination of knowledge.

Licenses for independent experts are granted by the Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy for an indefinite period. To ensure that practitioners remain aligned with the latest technical standards and legislative updates, the law mandates continuous professional development, requiring experts to complete a mandatory 'refresher' or complementary training course every five years. Independent EPC experts are classified as a regulated profession in the Republic of Slovenia. This status reflects the importance of the role in achieving national energy-saving targets and ensures that the certificates produced provide a reliable basis for financial incentives and property transactions. The quality of their work is further monitored through independent control systems, as outlined in the national energy strategy.

2.1.2.4 Other initiatives

An important national initiative in this direction is the development of the PURES LCC software tool, which represents an advanced methodological extension of the existing EPC calculation framework. PURES LCC is a computer-based tool for assessing the cost-effectiveness of energy efficiency (EE) and renewable energy (RES) measures over the entire life cycle of a building (Life Cycle Cost – LCC). The primary objective of the tool is to support users in the economic evaluation of renovation measures, providing additional analytical capabilities beyond standard EPC calculations⁵.

The tool operates as an upgrade and extension of the PURES-3 software, meaning that energy demand and minimum performance requirements are

⁵ Energy portal of the Republic of Slovenia, Calculation of energy performance of buildings. Available at: <https://www.energetika-portal.si/podrocja/energetika/energetske-izkaznice-stavb/izracun-energijske-ucinkovitosti-stavb/>

calculated using established EPC methodologies, while additional modules allow for financial and lifecycle-based analysis of investment options. A key feature of PURES LCC is the possibility to assess different renovation approaches, including a comprehensive (deep) renovation scenario, and step-by-step (staged) renovation strategies, which aligns closely with the conceptual approach of Building Renovation Passports (BRPs). Importantly, PURES LCC represents one of the first national tools enabling building-level LCC calculations in Slovenia. The tool is currently in an early stage of deployment and further development, with planned upgrades.

2.1.3 Spain

2.1.3.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Spain, the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is legally mandatory for most real estate transactions and is regulated by Royal Decree No. 390/2021⁶. This Decree partially transposes Directive (EU) on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD) by incorporating EPC-related data, including updated definitions and databases, and by linking financial incentives to energy savings. However, it does not address Building Renovation Passports (BRPs), Zero-Emission Buildings (ZEBs), or long-term renovation strategies⁷, as the Royal Decree No. 390/2021 is pending update to the EPBD from 2024.

An EPC is required when selling or renting a property, as well as when advertising a property for sale or rent, in which case the certificate must have been issued in advance. It is also mandatory for newly constructed buildings and for those undergoing major renovation, both at the design stage and upon completion, as well as for buildings or parts of buildings in which a public authority occupies a total usable area greater than 250 m². Furthermore, the requirement applies to non-residential buildings exceeding 500 m² and to properties subject to the Technical Building Inspection (ITE), which includes residential buildings more than 45 years old. The EPC is valid for a period of ten years; however, in cases where a property receives a G rating, the certificate's validity is limited to five years⁸.

The Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) must be conducted by a qualified technician. In the case of an existing building, the technician will undertake an on-site inspection in order to collect real data. To carry out the EPC, it is necessary to have the building regulations, its geometry, the composition of its

⁶ Real Decreto 390/2021. Boletín Oficial del Estado, No. 131, published the 02/06/2021.

⁷ Anape (2025). Transposición de la directiva de eficiencia energética de edificios a la normativa española. Available at: <https://anape.es/actualidad/transposicion-de-la-directiva-de-eficiencia-energetica-de-edificios-a-la-normativa-espanola/>

⁸ EPC SPAIN. Frequently Asked Questions. Available at: <https://www.epc-spain.com/questions-about-energy-performance-certificate.html>

envelope its energy systems (heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water, and lighting (in tertiary use buildings)), and whether renewable energy is used or solar protection is provided, among others. This information is subsequently entered into an official energy simulation programme, which calculates the building's energy demand and assigns an energy rating on a scale from A (most efficient) to G (least efficient)⁹. This result is determined by comparing the building's energy consumption and CO₂ emissions with those of a reference building with the same geometry, orientation, climate zone and use but envelope, HVAC and lighting features defined by standard building regulations¹⁰.

The principal characteristics by which the various regions of Spain differ are the climatic datasets and the procedures for the approval and registration of the official label.

To calculate the energy rating of a home or building, the climatic zone in which the building is located is taken into account. According to the Technical Building Code¹¹, climatic zones are classified as follows¹²:

- Winter climatic conditions on a scale from letter A (mildest climatic conditions) to E (harshest climatic conditions).
- Summer climatic conditions, on a scale from 1 (mildest climatic conditions) to 4 (harshest climatic conditions).

⁹ Qual DeEPC. Certificados de eficiencia energética de edificios. Available at: <https://qualrenovate.eu/es/services-products/energy-performance-certificates/energy-performance-certificates/>

¹⁰ ICAEN. Preguntas frecuentes. Available at: https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/energia/usos_energia/Antic_edificis-carpeta/page/preguntas_frecuentes/#faq-faq_cert_gen01

¹¹ Real Decreto 314/2006, approving the Technical Building Code (Código Técnico de la Edificación). Boletín Oficial del Estado, No. 74, published the 28/03/2006).

¹² ICAEN. Què és la certificació energètica? Available at: https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/energia/usos_energia/edificis/certificacio/que-es-la-certificacio-energetica/index.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Figure 4 Climatic zones in Spain according to the Technical Building Code

In addition, the methodologies for authorizing and registering the official label vary by region. Each regional authority operates its own platform, procedures, and fees for the validation of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)¹³.

Types of Certificates

EPCs in Spain may be classified according to several criteria: by building scope (entire building or individual dwelling unit); by construction phase (design stage, as-built, or existing building); and by use (residential or tertiary, including offices, retail premises, hotels, and hospitals).

An additional classification relates to the calculation method, distinguishing between simplified simulations (CE3X) and detailed simulations (HULC or EnergyPlus). Although Spanish regulations do not impose a specific method, they establish a framework permitting calculations to be carried out using recognized procedures.

The Building Renovation Passport (BRP) is not yet mandatory in Spain, as it was introduced under Directive (EU) 2024/1275, which has not yet been fully transposed. Its application will ultimately depend on the regional governments which may require it in specific situations such as major renovations, property transfers, or applications for public funding. For now, the BRP remains an emerging instrument. According to the EPBD, EU member states are required

¹³ Paula Paz (2025). Registro del Certificado Energético en cada Comunidad Autónoma. Certicalia. Available at: <https://www.certicalia.com/blog/registro-del-certificado-energetico-en-cada-comunidad-autonoma>

to establish procedures for its development. Consequently, its implementation is currently voluntary for building owners, unless national legislation establishes specific cases in which it is mandatory¹⁴.

Although there is no standardized methodology or unified software system for developing BRPs, they can be distinguished by the depth of assessment or their intended purpose — whether policy-driven or owner-driven —. However, no official classification has yet been established, as the concept is still under development.

On the other hand, improvement proposals for existing buildings are mandatory, despite they do not entail the achievement of a specific energy efficiency target. This differs from the BRP approach, which is intended to achieve a zero-emission building (ZEB) standard.

2.1.3.2 Energy-performance indicators

In Spain, the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) uses a set of standardized indicators to evaluate how energy-efficient a building is. These indicators are divided into principal and complementary to reflect the energy consumption, the environmental impact and the primary energy and thermal demand. The main indicators are¹⁵:

- CO₂ annual emissions [kg CO₂/m²·year]: amount of carbon dioxide released per year using fuels in buildings. These emissions vary depending on the energy source (natural gas, electricity, etc.).
- Primary non-renewable Energy Use [kWh/m²·year]: Measures the final energy consumed from heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water, and lighting (in tertiary use buildings) from non-renewable sources (fossil fuels such as natural gas, oil, coal...) including the losses during transformation, transport and distribution.

¹⁴ Editorial Team (2026). From policy to practice: how renovation passports empower Europe's Renovation Wave. BUILD UP. Available at: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/resources-and-tools/articles/how-renovation-passports-empower-europes-renovation-wave>

¹⁵ ICAEN. Què és la certificació energètica? Available at: https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/energia/usos_energia/edificis/certificacio/que-es-la-certificacio-energetica/index.html

Figure 5. Energy chain: demand, final energy and primary energy in buildings extracted from 16

Other indicators that complement the main ones explained above are¹⁷:

- CO₂ annual emissions [kg CO₂/m²·year] disaggregated by services (heating, cooling, hot water, and lighting (in tertiary use buildings)
- CO₂ annual emissions [kg CO₂/m²·year] disaggregated by electricity consumption
- Primary non-renewable Energy Use [kWh/m²·year] disaggregated by services (heating, cooling, hot water, and lighting (in tertiary use buildings)
- Annual energy demand for heating [kWh/m²·year]. Measures the energy required to heat the building to maintain a comfortable temperature.
- Annual energy demand for cooling [kWh/m²·year]. Measures the energy required to cool the building to maintain a comfortable temperature.

On the following image, it can be seen the shape of the EPC in Spain showing both types of indicators, the main ones on the left image and the complementary ones on the right image¹⁸:

¹⁶ Jansen S.C, Mohammadi S, Bokel R. (2020). Developing a locally balanced energy system for an existing neighbourhood, using the 'Smart Urban Isle' approach. Elsevier.

¹⁷ MITECO (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico) (2015). Calificación de la eficiencia energética de los edificios.

¹⁸ Serrano P. (Updated 2021). Contenido mínimo del certificado energético según el nuevo RD 390/2021. CERTIFICADOS ENERGETICOS.COM. Available at: <https://www.certificadosenergeticos.com/contenido-minimo-del-certificado-energetico>

Figure 6 EPC Shape and main and complementary indicators

EPC rating classes

Once the simulation is done and the data about the CO₂ emissions and the primary non-renewable Energy Use obtained, a letter on a scale from A to G will be given in EPCs in Spain to indicate the energy efficiency. Where A is the most efficient and G the least efficient.

The climate zone in which a building subject to certification is located has a significant influence on the resulting rating. Buildings situated in colder climate zones generally have higher thermal demands than those in more temperate regions. Consequently, two buildings with identical energy consumption and CO₂ emissions values may receive different ratings if they are located in different climate zones. In other words, the same building located in Barcelona (climate zone C2, with milder conditions) and in La Seu d'Urgell (climate zone E1, characterized by more severe climatic conditions) would achieve a lower rating in La Seu d'Urgell¹⁹.

2.1.3.3 Qualification of certifiers

In Spain, the qualification of the certifier responsible for issuing an accurate Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is regulated by Royal Decree no.

¹⁹ Casanovas, X. Pedreny, O. (2013). Certificar l'eficiència energètica dels edificis existents. RIARTE

659/2025²⁰, which repeals the definition of a competent technician established by Royal Decree no. 390/2021, which was based exclusively on qualifications, whereas the new one is based on the knowledge and professional skills required to issue an EPC.

In this way, to become accredited as a competent technician, individuals with university degrees, vocational training, and professional certification are distinguished. Depending on the qualification, the acquired knowledge must be supplemented by a training course comprising two modules:

- Module 1: Basic technical knowledge
- Module 2: Specific and administrative knowledge relating to energy efficiency certification in buildings

This division into modules allows students to take only one of the modules, depending on whether their qualification or professional certificate can prove the knowledge of the other module.

Qualifications are divided into three main groups:

- Qualifications that are automatically recognized as valid for practicing as a competent technician are those that enable the capacity to design building projects and to direct and supervise the execution of construction works. These include degrees in architecture, building engineering, engineering, and technical engineering.
- Other university degrees outside the energy field that must be supplemented with one (or both) of the modules: Environmental Sciences, Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Statistics, Computer Engineering, etc.
- Vocational training and professional certifications. These qualifications require the completion of supplementary training (module 1 and/or 2), depending on whether they can demonstrate prior competencies in energy efficiency. This category includes higher-level vocational training in fields related to energy and building facilities, as well as professional certifications and specialisation programmes (level 3).

Furthermore, all the competent technicians accredited to issue an EPC have to be registered in a centralised register (Registro Administrativo Centralizado de Técnicos Competentes) as it is defined in the article 25 of the Directive (EU) on the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD) 2024/1275. Each local region will be responsible for registering each qualified technician.

²⁰ Real Decreto 659/2025. Boletín Oficial del Estado, No. 176, published the 23/07/2025.

2.1.3.4 Other initiatives

Building's energy consumption report

This document is carried out in Catalonia and intended to facilitate the interpretation of energy performance certificates by providing clear, practical, and accessible information regarding the energy consumption of a building or dwelling. It also outlines the potential energy and economic savings that could be achieved through the implementation of the recommended improvement measures, particularly in the case of existing buildings.

The report is compiled using data derived from the energy efficiency certificate. It includes comparative analyses with the average values of similar certificates within the same climatic zone and, for existing buildings, also with those of the most energy-efficient buildings (energy rating A) recorded in the official Certificate Register.

The information contained in the building's energy consumption report is structured into several sections:

- Energy Consumption Comparison: This section compares the building's final energy consumption with the average consumption of buildings of the same typology (e.g., detached houses, apartment blocks) within the same climatic zone. For existing buildings, an additional comparison is made with A-rated buildings, which represent the highest level of energy efficiency. This analysis highlights the building's potential for energy improvement, as well as opportunities to enhance comfort and overall quality of life.
- CO₂ Emissions: This part identifies the energy sources used by the systems responsible for domestic hot water (DHW), heating, and cooling, and evaluates their respective contributions to the building's CO₂ emissions. If all energy is sourced from renewable resources, the total CO₂ emissions may be reduced to zero.
- Thermal Transmittance (U-values): The average U-values of the building's façades and windows are compared with the maximum values permitted under current regulations. This provides an indication of the building's insulation performance and its potential for further improvement.
- Additional Information: For existing buildings, this section includes the percentage of energy savings resulting from the implementation of the proposed measures, the estimated annual financial savings associated with the main proposed improvement in the EPC, and the building's annual economic surplus compared to the average of buildings A-rated of the same typology. For all certified buildings, it also provides an

estimate of the annual energy consumption, whether the building has renewable energy installations and which sources they are, specifies if electric vehicle charging points are available, and notes whether the building is connected to a district heating network.

The report also includes a QR code that allows direct access to the digital repository where the certificate is registered (making it easy to verify its authenticity). A graphic example of the Building's energy consumption report can be seen in the following image:

Figure 7 Shape of the Building's energy consumption report

CE3X Add-on for Generating an Energy Audit

In response to the requirement to produce an energy audit for all buildings owned by the Generalitat de Catalunya, ICAEN has promoted the development of an add-on integrated into the CE3X building energy certification software. This tool enables the generation of an energy audit directly from the certification process.

The audit add-on facilitates the collection of the data required to produce a basic energy audit and generates an .XML file containing both the energy certification data and the additional information necessary for the audit. Furthermore, it supports the standardisation of audit content and format, as well as their digitalisation.

2.2 National initiatives of EPC and BRP in other EU countries

2.2.1 Portugal

2.2.1.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Portugal, the EPC framework was originally established by Decree-Law No. 78/2006 and has since been updated and replaced by subsequent^{21, 22, 23} amends the system and partially transposes EPBD 2024. Regarding BRP, Portugal is obliged to transpose this requirement into national law. The transposition process appears to be²⁴.

In Portugal an EPC is required for new buildings and buildings undergoing major renovation -both at design stage and before obtaining the occupancy permit-. It is also required for existing buildings before sale or rental, and for large public buildings above 250m² floor area. (Certain exceptions apply, as specified in Article 18(2) of Decree-Law 101/2020). An EPC may also be required for buildings applying for energy-related funding or tax benefits. These certificates are generally valid for 10 years for residential and small service buildings, and for some large commercial buildings its validity is shorter. To

²¹Source: <https://www.sce.pt/legislacao/>

²²Decreto-Lei N.º 101-D/2020, de 7 de dezembro: Estabelece os requisitos aplicáveis a edifícios para a melhoria do seu desempenho energético e regula o Sistema de Certificação Energética de Edifícios, transpondo a Diretiva (UE) 2018/844 e parcialmente a Diretiva (UE)

²³ Decreto-Lei n.º 11/2025 de 19 de fevereiro: Transpõe parcialmente a Diretiva (UE) 2024/1275, relativa ao desempenho energético dos edifícios, e altera o Decreto-Lei n.º 101-D/2020, de 7 de dezembro.

²⁴ Source: <https://www.adene.pt/>

register an EPC on the SCE portal, a fee must be paid (fees paid are distributed annually as follows: 87 % to ADENE, 10 % to the Environmental Fund, and 3 % to DGEG).

The assessment of the energy performance of buildings is carried out considering the energy needs associated with specific uses (as indicated in the EPBD), such as space heating and cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water, and in some cases (non-residential) lighting. These uses are determined to directly or indirectly optimize the levels of health, thermal comfort, and indoor air quality of building occupants. The calculation methodology is established by law, as set out in the SCE Manual. This SCE Manual must be reviewed at intervals not exceeding two years, or whenever technical or regulatory changes justify it. It considers the specific characteristics of the buildings covered, describes the national choices, and incorporates the annexes of the relevant general ISO/EN standards for its application. Portugal defines 9 climatic zones for EPC calculations, combining 3 winter and 3 summer categories, which are used to determine heating, cooling, and reference building energy performance.

Portugal has a single national certification system, although there are different formats of the energy certificate depending on the type of building use (residential and non-residential). A physical inspection of the building is always required.

The data obtained for preparing an EPC come from a combination of sources, mainly:

- On-site data collection about the general building characteristics (location, geometry, building envelope composition...) and its systems (heating, cooling and DHW systems, ventilation systems and renewal installations).
- Building documentation (architectural and engineering plans available, year of construction, technical datasheets of the installed equipment ...).

The meteorological data used in EPC calculations come from standardized reference datasets based on historical measurements from the official national meteorological agency. Occupancy is estimated using standardized profiles and schedules to predict energy use. Energy bills may also be included to supplement the assessment, but they are optional and do not replace the calculated results.

2.2.1.2 Energy-performance indicators

There are several energy indicators for Portugal EPC, and some of them some differ depending on the use of the building. The common indicators are:

- Primary energy consumption for heating (kWh/m²·year)

- Primary energy consumption for cooling (kWh/m²·year)
- Primary energy consumption for domestic hot water (kWh/m²·year)
- Renewable energy contribution for each use analysed (%): share of the building's energy consumption covered by renewable sources in each type of use (heating, cooling...).
- Total self-consumed renewable energy (%): The portion of renewable energy produced on-site and consumed directly in the building.
- Total CO2 emissions (Ton/year): An indicator that reflects the amount of greenhouse gases released into the atmosphere as a result of energy consumption in the various uses considered in the building.
- Reference building comparison shows how the building's performance compares with a new-compliant reference building, providing context for the rating

In the case of residential EPCs there also the following specific indicators:

- Nominal annual useful energy needs for heating (kWh/m²·year)
- Nominal annual useful energy needs for cooling (kWh/m²·year)
- Total useful energy for domestic hot water preparation (kWh/year)
- Total electrical energy required for the operation of the fans (kWh/year)
- Total renewal energy for regulated uses (kWh/year)
- Total renewal energy for other uses (kWh/year)
- Nominal annual overall primary energy needs (kWhEP/m²·year): this is the overall primary energy consumption of the building for the regulated uses (heating, cooling, domestic hot water...).

In the case of non-residential EPCs there the following specific indicators:

- Energy efficiency indicator (kWhEP/m²·year): Primary energy consumption in the building (for all uses considered).
- Energy efficiency indicator for type S consumption (kWhEP/m²·year): Primary energy consumption in the building for cooling, heating and domestic hot water.
- Energy efficiency indicator for type T consumption (kWhEP/m²·year) : Primary energy consumption in the building for other uses considered (such as lighting and ventilation).
- Renewable energy efficiency indicator (kWhEP/m²·year): Renewal primary energy consumption in the building for regulated uses.
- Renewal Energy produced for other uses (kWh/year)

Based on the indicators, buildings obtain an energy efficiency class; there are 6 levels of energy efficiency class (rating from A+ to F). Higher classes correspond to lower energy consumption and better performance.

Figure 8 Visual identity for first page of Portuguese EPCs: residential format (left) and non-residential format (right).

The rating is primarily determined by comparing the building's non-renewable primary energy consumption with that of the reference building defined by national regulations. Therefore, in Portugal, the EPC rating is not based on fixed absolute consumption thresholds (e.g., specific kWh/m²·year values) and it depends on factors such as the building type (residential/non-residential), geometry and orientation or the building's climate zone.

In addition to the energy-performance indicators, Portugal EPC report provides other interesting information, both to customers and technicians:

- It verifies if the building elements accomplish technical regulations: as it indicates the parameters of the building's technical systems, presenting both the actual values and the reference values required by national regulations for new building.

SISTEMAS TÉCNICOS E VENTILAÇÃO					
Descrição dos Elementos Identificados	Uso	Consumo de Energia [kWh/ano]	Potência Instalada [kW]	Desempenho Nominal/Sazonal*	
				Solução	Ref.
Split					
Multi-split, equipamento elétrico, com recurso a 4 unidades interiores instaladas na parede, com permuta de calor tipo ar-ar. O equipamento instalado é da marca XPTO, com a unidade exterior do modelo 1234 e as 4 unidades interiores do modelo 5678. O equipamento foi instalado em 2007 (ano de construção do edifício). De acordo com a informação disponibilizada os equipamentos têm sido sujeitos a operações de manutenção regulares, sendo o último registo datado de Março de 2013.	✖	2.900,00	96,00	4,50	3,20
	✔	1.500,00	112,00	3,98	2,80
Sistema do tipo Split, composto por 4 unidades iguais, cada uma delas com uma potência para aquecimento de 24,00 kW e para arrefecimento de 28,00 kW.					
*Valores maiores representam soluções mais eficientes.					

Figure 9 Visual identity for EPCs in Portugal: residential format (left) and non-residential format (right).

- **Establish relationships between potential energy efficiency improvements and associated benefits.** It assesses the additional benefits of the various improvement measures proposed in the EPC, beyond energy savings, such as improvements in acoustic comfort, aesthetics, and indoor air quality.

Figure 10 Visualisation of improvement measures in Portuguese EPCs: it shows energy savings and associated co-benefits.

2.2.1.3 Qualification of certifiers

Decree-Law No. 102/2021²⁵ sets the requirements for practicing as a technician within Portugal's Building Energy Certification System (SCE). To act as a qualified technician (PQ), candidates must hold a relevant academic degree, have at least five years of professional experience, and pass an examination administered by ADENE.

The system distinguishes between two categories of qualified technicians. The PQ-I category applies to residential buildings and small commercial or service

²⁵ Decreto -Lei n.º 101 -D/2020, de 7 de dezembro (estabelece os requisitos de acesso e de exercício da atividade dos técnicos do Sistema de Certificação Energética dos Edifícios).

buildings with HVAC systems of up to 30 kW, and requires a degree in architecture, engineering, or technical engineering, along with professional experience in building design or construction. The PQ-II category applies to larger commercial or service buildings and requires a degree in engineering or technical engineering, as well as experience in the design, construction, maintenance of HVAC systems, or energy auditing. The content and evaluation criteria of the qualifying examination are defined by ministerial order Portaria No. 28/2022

In Portugal, an EPC issued by a non-certified technician is invalid, subject to fines and may expose the issuer to civil liability.

2.2.1.4 Other initiatives

- CasA+ (Decision support tool for renovation)²⁶

CasA+ is a digital, non-regulatory platform developed by ADENE that builds on Portugal's EPC (SCE) system to support building renovation decisions. It transforms EPC data into practical guidance by suggesting energy efficiency measures, estimating savings and costs, and linking users to certified professionals and financing options.

Unlike the static EPC, CasA+ acts as a one-stop-shop and decision-support tool, making energy performance information more actionable and aligned with renovation planning needs. It is part of broader EU-driven efforts to improve EPC usability and support deeper building renovation.

2.2.2 Italy

2.2.2.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Italy, the national framework for EPCs is based on a calculation procedure defined by the UNI/TS 11300 standards²⁷. These standards provide the technical basis for assessing the energy performance of buildings and for producing the official certificate. The Italian approach is therefore strongly calculation-based rather than based on measured consumption. In practice, only calculated demand certificates exist, EPC are not based on measured consumption.

²⁶ Portal CasA+ - Para casas mais eficientes e confortáveis: <https://portalcasamais.pt>

²⁷ Italy. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico. *Decreto 26 giugno 2015: Adeguamento del decreto del Ministro dello sviluppo economico, 26 giugno 2009 – Linee guida nazionali per la certificazione energetica degli edifici. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana*, no. 162, Supplemento Ordinario no. 39, July 15, 2015

The energy uses considered in the calculation include space heating, domestic hot water, cooling, lighting, and mechanical ventilation. Demand of mechanical ventilation is incorporated within the heating demand calculation rather than being treated as a fully separate end use. The result is a standardized assessment of the building's overall energy performance.

A key feature of the Italian EPC framework is the use of a dynamic threshold based on a so-called reference building. This reference building has the same geometry, orientation, and building service system types as the real building under assessment. However, its thermal characteristics, especially the U-values of building elements, are standardized and differ from those of the actual building. The energy demand of this reference building must therefore be calculated separately. Compliance is achieved when the non-renewable primary energy demand of the real building meets the level defined by this reference building. In other words, the reference building provides a moving benchmark tailored to the specific building being assessed, instead of relying on one fixed national threshold for all buildings.

This framework is also linked to minimum energy performance requirements. In addition to the requirement that non-renewable primary energy demand must not exceed that of the reference building with the real building service systems, there are further conditions that must be met. These include minimum U-values for different categories of building elements, moisture protection verification, summer thermal protection requirements, and minimum shares of renewable energy. The EPC system is therefore not only a labeling instrument but also part of a broader regulatory framework for building energy performance²⁸.

The result pages of the EPC are nationally standardized. This ensures that the certificate itself is presented in a uniform format throughout the country and can be easily recognized. At the same time, the detailed calculation outputs and interim results may differ depending on the region and on the software used. Since calculations are performed through software implementing UNI/TS 11300, the layout and extent of technical documentation can vary. This creates a system in which the public-facing certificate is uniform, but the technical background documentation can differ in presentation and depth.

Regarding BRPs, no nationally widespread model appears to be in use in Italy. In contrast to the EPC, which is clearly defined and standardized at the national level, a comparable national Building Renovation Passport framework is not yet commonly established. This means that the EPC remains the main standardized instrument for documenting and communicating building energy performance in Italy.

²⁸ Comitato Termotecnico Italiano Energia e Ambiente. "UNI/TS 11300." Accessed March 24, 2026.

2.2.2.2 Energy-performance indicators

The Italian EPC system is based on non-renewable primary energy demand. Both compliance assessment and EPC classification rely on comparison with a reference building, so the system is relative rather than based on one fixed national threshold.

For EPC classes, the rating is derived from the ratio between the real building's primary energy demand and that of a separately calculated reference building. This reference building has the same geometry and orientation as the real building, but it is calculated with standard building services, not the actual ones. The class thresholds are therefore dynamic. For example, class B corresponds to the reference demand, class C to 1.2 times the reference demand, and class D to 1.5 times the reference demand.

The calculation includes the main end uses considered in the Italian methodology: heating, domestic hot water, cooling, lighting, and mechanical ventilation. Since the EPC is based on calculated demand only, the indicators describe standardized building performance and not actual occupant-related energy consumption²⁹.

In addition to the rating classes, the Italian framework includes further performance requirements, such as envelope-quality thresholds, summer thermal protection, moisture protection, and minimum renewable-energy shares³⁰.

2.2.2.3 Qualification of certifiers

EPC certifiers must have a qualifying professional background and must also be independent from the planning phase. In practice, the certifier must not be the same person who was responsible for the building design.

Some professional groups are automatically qualified, especially those with a background in mechanical engineering, building services engineering, or energy engineering. Their education is considered sufficient for carrying out EPC assessments.

Other professionals may qualify through an 80-hour training course followed by a final examination. This examination includes both a written test and a project

²⁹ Italy. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico. Decreto 26 giugno 2015: Adeguamento del decreto del Ministro dello sviluppo economico, 26 giugno 2009 – Linee guida nazionali per la certificazione energetica degli edifici, Allegato 1. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, no. 162, Supplemento Ordinario no. 39, July 15, 2015.

³⁰ Italy. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico. Decreto 26 giugno 2015: Applicazione delle metodologie di calcolo delle prestazioni energetiche e definizione delle prescrizioni e dei requisiti minimi degli edifici. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, no. 162, Supplemento Ordinario no. 39, July 15, 2015.

exercise, so that theoretical knowledge and practical competence are both assessed. Once qualified, certifiers are not subject to yearly renewal requirements³¹.

2.2.2.4 Other initiatives

In Italy, several initiatives aim to strengthen the role of EPCs and to connect certification more closely with renovation policy, digital data collection, and advisory tools. Three particularly relevant developments are SIAPE, as well as the projects tunES, PnPE2 and Passaporto dell'immobile. Taken together, these initiatives show that Italy is moving beyond the EPC as a stand-alone certificate toward a broader information and renovation-support system.

A key initiative is SIAPE (Sistema Informativo sugli Attestati di Prestazione Energetica). This national tool was established by the decree of 26 June 2015 and is managed by the National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA), which is a public body aimed technological innovation. Its purpose is to provide a more detailed picture of the state of energy renovation in the national building stock. SIAPE centralizes EPCs from the registries of the regions and autonomous provinces into a single national database. This is particularly important in the Italian context, where certification practice still shows regional differences. SIAPE therefore does not replace regional implementation, but it creates a national information layer that supports monitoring, statistics, and policy evaluation³².

A second relevant initiative is tunES (“Tuning EPC and SRI instruments to deliver full potential”), a LIFE project in which ENEA participates alongside six other national energy agencies. Rather than redefining the legal nature of the EPC, tunES treats the certificate as part of a broader policy and decision-support architecture linked to the revised EPBD, Building Renovation Passports, and Smart Readiness Indicators³³. Its contribution lies in examining how EPC-related information can be made more understandable, accurate, trusted, and operationally useful through better data infrastructure, integration with other instruments, stakeholder consultation, and evidence-based policy design. In this framework, the EPC is not approached as a stand-alone compliance document, but as an input into renovation-oriented governance: tunES develops problem analyses, objective trees, policy options, and impact-

³¹ Italy. Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica 16 aprile 2013, n. 75: Regolamento recante disciplina dei criteri di accreditamento per assicurare la qualificazione e l'indipendenza degli esperti e degli organismi a cui affidare la certificazione energetica degli edifici, a norma dell'articolo 4, comma 1, lettera c), del decreto legislativo 19 agosto 2005, n. 192. Gazzetta Ufficiale della Repubblica Italiana, no. 149, June 27, 2013.

³² ENEA. “SIAPE – Sistema Informativo Nazionale degli APE.” April 16, 2019.

³³ European Commission, CINEA. “tunES/101120926: Tuning EPC and SRI Instruments to Deliver Full Potential.” *LIFE Public Database*. Accessed March 24, 2026.

assessment methods intended to strengthen the role of EPC data in supporting deeper and additional renovation, improving administrative efficiency, and guiding building owners and other market actors toward more informed action³⁴
³⁵.

Another development is linked to PnPE2 and the Passaporto dell'immobile. This passport is conceived as a broader building-information instrument that combines cadastral, energy, and plant-system data. Its role goes beyond that of a normal EPC. The idea is to create a national one-stop shop connecting EPCs with incentives, statistics, and advisory tools³⁶. In this sense, the Passaporto dell'immobile moves toward a BRP-type approach, since it is intended not only to document current status but also to support renovation planning and decision-making over time^{37 38}.

2.2.3 Germany

2.2.3.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Germany, the national framework for EPCs is based on the DIN 18599 standard. This standard defines the methodology for calculating the energy performance of buildings and is especially suited to complex non-residential buildings³⁹. For residential buildings, simplified calculation methods are also possible, reflecting the lower technical complexity of many housing types. In addition to the EPC framework, Germany also has a more developed context for Building Renovation Passports (BRPs). These are defined through several BAFA EBW guidelines rather than through a single unified national EPC-style model. This means that, unlike the EPC, the BRP framework is connected to advisory and funding structures rather than being represented by one universally used certificate format^{40 41}.

³⁴ European Commission, CINEA. "tunES/101120926: Tuning EPC and SRI Instruments to Deliver Full Potential." *LIFE Public Database*. Accessed March 24, 2026.

³⁵ Vogt, Georg, Tatiana Novikova, and Karolina Junak. *Tuning EPC and SRI Instruments to Deliver Full Potential: Final Report*. n.d.

³⁶ ENEA. "MiTE ed ENEA lanciano il Portale nazionale sulla prestazione energetica degli edifici." April 13, 2022.

³⁷ ENEA and Comitato Termotecnico Italiano Energia e Ambiente. *Executive Summary 2024: Rapporto sulla Certificazione Energetica degli Edifici*. Rome: ENEA, 2024.

³⁸ ENEA and Comitato Termotecnico Italiano Energia e Ambiente. *Executive Summary 2025: Rapporto annuale sulla certificazione energetica degli edifici*. Rome: ENEA, 2025.

³⁹ Germany. *Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG)*, § 21 "Berechnung des Jahres-Primärenergiebedarfs eines Nichtwohngebäudes." *Gesetze im Internet*. Accessed April 7, 2026.

⁴⁰ BAFA. *Bundesförderung der Energieberatung für Wohngebäude (EBW)*. Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle. Accessed April 7, 2026.

⁴¹ BAFA. *Merkblatt für die Erstellung des individuellen Sanierungsfahrplans (iSFP)*, Förderprogramm Energieberatung für Wohngebäude (EBW). Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle. Accessed April 7, 2026.

The German EPC framework uses a dynamic threshold based on a reference building. This reference building has the same geometry and orientation as the actual building but differs in its thermal and technical characteristics. It is assigned standardized U-values and standardized building service systems. The energy demand of this reference building must therefore be calculated separately, and the resulting value serves as the benchmark for compliance. Depending on the building context, this benchmark must be undercut by different percentages. The relevant threshold can vary according to whether the case concerns a renovation or a new construction, whether public funding is involved, and whether the building is public or private. The German system therefore uses the reference building not as a fixed national benchmark, but as a tailored comparative model whose required degree of undercutting depends on the specific regulatory framework^{42 43}.

The final EPC result pages are nationally standardized and, for public buildings, must be displayed. This ensures a consistent presentation of energy information across the country. Unlike in systems where regional authorities have some influence over implementation, Germany has no regional differences in the calculation methodology itself. The calculation rules are nationally standardized by DIN 18599, which creates a high degree of formal consistency. However, as in many standardized systems, the software-generated technical outputs underlying the certificate are not regulated in detail. As a result, the layout and extent of interim results and calculation documentation can differ between software tools, even though the official certificate format remains uniform⁴⁴.

The German methodology covers the main building energy uses in a comprehensive way. These include heating, domestic hot water, cooling, mechanical ventilation, and lighting. This broad scope is particularly relevant for non-residential buildings, where ventilation often represents a substantial share of total energy demand. The emphasis on DIN 18599 reflects this broader systems perspective, which is one reason why the method is particularly associated with more complex buildings⁴⁵.

⁴² Germany. *Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG)*, Anlage 1 “Technische Ausführung des Referenzgebäudes (Wohngebäude).” *Gesetze im Internet*. Accessed April 7, 2026.

⁴³ Germany. *Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG)*, Anlage 2 “Technische Ausführung des Referenzgebäudes (Nichtwohngebäude).” *Gesetze im Internet*. Accessed April 7, 2026.

⁴⁴ Germany. *Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG)*. August 8, 2020. *Gesetze im Internet*. Accessed April 7, 2026.

⁴⁵ DIN. *Auslegungen zu DIN V 18599 bzw. DIN TS 18599*. DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung. Accessed April 7, 2026.

Another important characteristic of the German system is that both demand-based and consumption-based certificates exist. For substantial renovations and for new buildings, calculated demand certificates are mandatory. In these cases, the building's theoretical energy performance under standardized conditions must be assessed. For other existing buildings, real consumption certificates may also be used. This introduces more flexibility than in systems that rely exclusively on calculated demand^{46 47}.

Overall, the German framework combines a nationally standardized technical methodology, a flexible regulatory use of the reference building, and a dual approach to certification through both demand and consumption certificates. In parallel, BRPs are not embedded in one single national model but are instead shaped by BAFA EBW guidelines, linking them more closely to renovation advice and funding practice.

2.2.3.2 Energy-performance indicators

The German EPC framework uses non-renewable primary energy demand (kWh/m²a) as a main compliance indicator. Building performance is assessed against a reference building with the same geometry and orientation but with standardized U-values and building services. The required performance level depends on the context, since the reference-building demand must be undercut by different percentages depending on factors such as new construction, renovation, state-owned buildings, or access to public funding.

Besides primary energy, the framework also includes additional technical requirements. These include threshold values for building-envelope performance by element category, moisture protection verification, and, for new buildings, summer thermal protection.

The EPC rating classes, however, are not based on primary energy. They are derived from the absolute final energy demand per square meter and year. The class limits are fixed values, for example A < 50 kWh/m²a, B < 75, C < 100, and D < 130 for residential buildings. This means that Germany distinguishes between the indicator used for regulatory compliance and the indicator used for the public EPC label.

Overall, the German system combines a relative compliance method based on the reference building with an absolute classification system for the certificate itself.

⁴⁶ Germany. Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG), § 80 “Ausstellung und Verwendung von Energieausweisen.” Gesetze im Internet. Accessed April 7, 2026.

⁴⁷ Germany. Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG), § 82 “Energieverbrauchsausweis.” Gesetze im Internet. Accessed April 7, 2026.

2.2.3.3 Qualification of certifiers

Under the state-building-law route referenced in § 88(1) no. 1 GEG, the decisive requirement is typically authorization to prepare and sign thermal-protection / energy-saving compliance documents in the building-permit system, usually through Bauvorlageberechtigung or entry in a chamber-administered list of Nachweisberechtigte for Wärmeschutz, with the exact mix of degree, experience, and recognition requirements varying by federal state ⁴⁸.

In practice, many professionals active in refurbishment, BRP (individueller Sanierungsfahrplan iSFP), subsidized energy improvements, and technically demanding non-residential projects are also entered in the dena Energy Efficiency Experts List (EEE-List). The dena list operates as the quality-assurance and access framework for federal support programmes, with standardized admission checks and regular renewal requirements. To be listed, EPC certifiers need both a relevant professional background and substantial additional training. Qualification is not based only on academic degree but also on formal energy-related training. The required training usually comprises 280 to 440 hours, depending on the applicant's prior university qualification. It ends with a final examination consisting of a written exam, project work, and an oral exam. In addition, certification is linked to ongoing professional activity. Every 3-year period, certifiers must complete 24 hours of follow-up training and carry out at least one energy consultation. The German system therefore places strong emphasis not only on initial qualification but also on continued professional development ⁴⁹.

2.2.3.4 Other initiatives

In Germany, there are important initiatives that go beyond the standard EPC framework and broaden the assessment of building performance or renovation planning. Two particularly relevant examples are the QNG-related assessment for subsidized new buildings and the *individueller Sanierungsfahrplan* (iSFP). While both instruments extend the information base available to owners and policymakers, they do so in different ways: the QNG approach enhances assessment criteria for new buildings, whereas the iSFP is not an EPC, but rather a standardized building renovation roadmap (BRP).

⁴⁸ Germany. Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG), § 88 “Ausstellungsberechtigung für Energieausweise.” Gesetze im Internet.

⁴⁹ Germany. Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie und zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien zur Wärme- und Kälteerzeugung in Gebäuden (Gebäudeenergiegesetz – GEG), Anlage 11. Gesetze im Internet.

A first important development is the QNG assessment. For new buildings, this subsidy scheme is linked not only to energy efficiency but also to wider sustainability requirements. In this context, support is tied to the condition of low greenhouse gas emissions. The certificate used for the life-cycle assessment in this context resembles a conventional EPC in its presentation, but it goes significantly further in content. Most importantly, the relevant threshold is no longer defined only by operational energy demand. Instead, it is based on the greenhouse gas emissions of the whole building. This broader approach includes not only emissions during building operation, but also emissions associated with construction materials, their replacement over the life cycle, and their end-of-life treatment. In addition, it also considers greenhouse gas emissions from refrigerants. The QNG-related assessment therefore represents a substantial extension of the traditional EPC logic, because it shifts attention from operational energy use alone to the climate impact of the building across its full life cycle^{50 51}.

A second major initiative is the *individueller Sanierungsfahrplan* (iSFP). Unlike the EPC, the iSFP is not an energy certificate, but a nationally standardized instrument for renovation advice. It is better understood as a building renovation passport (BRP)-type tool. Its purpose is to present the results of energy advice in a clear, visualized, and easy-to-understand form for building owners. The iSFP is used mainly for residential buildings and supports both step-by-step renovation strategies and comprehensive refurbishment concepts. In this way, it provides a structured pathway for future renovation rather than a snapshot-style rating of current building performance. Its importance lies in making long-term renovation planning more accessible and more practical for households^{52 53}.

Taken together, these two initiatives show that Germany's building-performance framework extends beyond the classic EPC. The QNG assessment broadens performance evaluation toward whole-life greenhouse gas emissions, while the iSFP provides a standardized roadmap for renovation. Especially in the case of the iSFP, it is important to distinguish clearly between EPCs as certification instruments and BRP-type instruments as renovation planning tools.

⁵⁰ Qualitätssiegel Nachhaltiges Gebäude. *QNG-Handbuch*. Version 1.3. 2024.

⁵¹ Qualitätssiegel Nachhaltiges Gebäude. *Gebäudeanforderungen: Besondere Anforderungen im öffentlichen Interesse gemäß Anlage 3 zum QNG-Handbuch*. 2024.

⁵² Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle. *Merkblatt für die Erstellung des individuellen Sanierungsfahrplans (iSFP)*. January 8, 2024.

⁵³ Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle. "Bundesförderung Energieberatung für Wohngebäude." Accessed March 24, 2026.

2.2.4 Austria

2.2.4.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

Austria's official EPC's governance is split between federal and provincial levels. The federal portal explains that the duty to present and hand over an EPC in property transactions is governed by the Energieausweis-Vorlage-Gesetz, while the conditions under which an EPC must be prepared are laid down in the building-law provisions of the individual Länder⁵⁴. At the technical level, the provinces have largely harmonised their energy rules around the OIB Guidelines, especially OIB Guideline 6 on energy saving and thermal protection⁵⁵. In practice, sellers and landlords must provide an EPC that is no more than ten years old; if only a flat or business unit is transferred, Austria allows the use of an EPC for that unit, for a comparable unit in the same building, or for the whole building. The result is a formally national EPC regime for disclosure and market use, but one whose calculation and form remain partly shaped by provincial building law⁵⁶.

2.2.4.2 Energy-performance indicators

For residential buildings, the first page of the Austrian EPC shows the main performance indicators: specific heating demand, primary energy demand, CO₂ emissions, and the overall energy-efficiency factor (fGEE), all classified on a scale from A++ to G. The second page provides more detailed building and climate data together with additional demand indicators such as domestic hot-water demand, heating energy demand, and final energy demand. For non-residential buildings, the content is extended further, for example by adding cooling demand. Except for new buildings, Austrian EPCs also include recommendations for measures, which gives the certificate a limited improvement-planning function in addition to rating performance⁵⁷.

2.2.4.3 Qualification of certifiers

Austria does not rely on a single nationwide "energy assessor" profession; instead, the federal portal lists a set of professions that are legally entitled to issue EPCs. These include master builders, several technical trades, relevant engineering offices, civil engineers, and architects. The same official list also specifies narrower scopes for some professions: for example, chimney sweeps are limited to existing residential buildings and may not certify new buildings or

⁵⁴ oesterreich.gv.at. "Allgemeines zum Energieausweis." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁵⁵ Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik. "OIB-Richtlinie 6: Energieeinsparung und Wärmeschutz." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁵⁶ oesterreich.gv.at. "Vorlage- und Aushändigungspflicht." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁵⁷ oesterreich.gv.at. "Inhalt eines Energieausweises." Accessed March 26, 2026.

permit-requiring alterations, while stove builders are limited to one- and two-family houses. This means Austrian certifier qualification is profession-based rather than exam-based, although the exact issuance conditions still depend on the applicable provincial building law.

2.2.4.4 Other initiatives

The *klimaaktiv Sanierungsfahrplan* is a national Austrian, but non-mandatory, instrument developed within the federal *klimaaktiv* programme to support the stepwise renovation of existing buildings rather than one-off refurbishment projects. It is presented by *klimaaktiv* as a process guide for high-quality renovation and the gradual replacement of fossil energy systems. The tool is designed for cases in which renovation is implemented over several stages, and *klimaaktiv* states that the necessary measures can be distributed over a period of up to 15 years following an initial assessment of the building stock. Methodologically, the Sanierungsfahrplan is based on the *klimaaktiv* criteria catalogue and is complemented by a dedicated process guide, which helps structure decision-making, sequencing, and implementation. The Sanierungsfahrplan is now embedded in a wider toolbox for renovation and heating-system conversion, together with portfolio analysis, action guides, and technical solution catalogues for municipalities and owners of building portfolios. The instrument appears particularly relevant for projects where decisions are phased, financially constrained, or institutionally complex, e.g. in multi-family housing or municipal building stocks⁵⁸.

2.2.5 Croatia

2.2.5.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Croatia, the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) system is regulated under the national Building Act (2019) and further specified by the Energy Efficiency in Buildings Act (NN 155/25) and related by-laws governing the energy performance of buildings. The system is aligned with the requirements of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and represents a key instrument for improving the energy efficiency of the national building stock. The updated legal framework strengthens the role of EPCs through increased digitalization, improved data management and closer alignment with the objectives of the EPBD recast.

58 Schrattecker, Inge, and Franziska Trebut. "klimaaktiv Sanierungsfahrplan: Ein Leitfaden für die schrittweise Sanierung." Accessed March 26, 2026.

The issuance of an EPC is mandatory in several cases:

- New buildings, where the certificate is required upon completion
- Buildings or building units that are sold or rented
- Buildings undergoing major renovations

Energy performance certificates are issued by authorized natural persons or legal entities, who must be licensed by the competent Ministry. The certification process is based on standardized methodologies and must follow national technical regulations.

A centralized national EPC database is maintained and managed by the Energy Institute Hrvoje Požar (EIHP). This registry ensures traceability, transparency, and quality control of issued certificates, while also supporting policy monitoring and future system improvements.

Currently, the EPC in Croatia primarily functions as a static assessment tool, largely based on calculated energy performance derived from building characteristics and technical systems. While this approach provides a standardized evaluation, it has limitations in reflecting actual operational performance and user behaviour.

The Building Renovation Passport (BRP) has not yet been systematically implemented in Croatia. Existing EPCs include basic recommendations for energy improvements; however, they do not provide a comprehensive, step-by-step roadmap for deep renovation over time.

At present, there is no full integration between EPCs and long-term renovation planning tools, which limits the role of EPCs as strategic instruments for guiding building renovation pathways.

2.2.5.2 Energy-performance indicators

The energy performance of buildings in Croatia is assessed through a set of standardized indicators defined by national legislation and aligned with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). The methodology is primarily based on calculated energy performance, which evaluates the building's physical characteristics and technical systems rather than actual measured energy consumption⁵⁹.

⁵⁹ Pravilnik o energetsom pregledu zgrade i energetsom certificiranju, Official Gazette of the Republic of Croatia. Available at: <https://www.zakon.hr/c/podzakonski-propis/45406/pravilnik-o-energetsom-pregledu-zgrade-i-energetsom-certificiranju-%E2%80%93-procisceni-tekst>

The core indicators included in the Croatian EPC are:

- Primary energy consumption (kWh/m²·year): This indicator represents the total primary energy required to operate the building, taking into account energy conversion and distribution losses. It is a key parameter for evaluating the building's environmental impact and compliance with regulatory requirements.
- CO₂ emissions (kg CO₂/m²·year): The EPC includes an estimation of greenhouse gas emissions associated with the building's energy use. This indicator reflects the carbon intensity of the energy sources used and supports climate policy objectives.
- Energy demand for building services (kWh/m²·year): The certificate provides a breakdown of energy needs for key building functions, including: Heating, Cooling, Domestic hot water (DHW). This allows for a more detailed understanding of where energy is consumed within the building.
- Share of renewable energy (%): This indicator shows the proportion of energy supplied from renewable sources (e.g., solar, biomass, heat pumps) relative to the total energy demand, highlighting the building's contribution to sustainable energy use.

Energy performance of buildings in Croatia is expressed through an energy class scale ranging from A+ (highest performance) to G (lowest performance). The classification is based on the calculated annual specific energy demand for heating ($Q_{h,nd}$), expressed in kWh/m²·year, and complemented by primary energy indicators in line with EPB standards.

- A+ – ≤ 15 kWh/m²
- A – 15 – 25 kWh/m²
- B – 25 – 50 kWh/m²
- C – 50 – 100 kWh/m²
- D – 100 – 150 kWh/m²
- E – 150 – 200 kWh/m²
- F – 200 – 250 kWh/m²
- G – > 250 kWh/m²

In addition to these quantitative indicators, the EPC also includes recommendations for energy efficiency improvements, such as upgrading

insulation, replacing technical systems, or integrating renewable energy technologies. These recommendations are generally indicative and do not follow a structured long-term renovation pathway.

It is important to note that the Croatian EPC system is currently based on calculated (theoretical) performance, which ensures consistency and comparability across buildings but may not fully reflect actual energy use influenced by occupant behaviour and operational conditions.

Furthermore, the current framework does not incorporate:

- Life-cycle assessment (LCA) indicators, which would account for embodied energy and emissions over the building's lifespan
- Financial indicators, such as investment costs, payback periods, or cost-effectiveness of recommended measures.

ENERGETSKI CERTIFIKAT ZGRADE
 prema Pravilniku o energetskom pregledu zgrade i energetskom certifikatu (NN /)

Ime zgrade: _____
 Adresa energetske opremljene (dijel) zgrade: _____
 Ulica i kućni broj: _____ Raštrani broj: _____ Mjesto: _____

PODACI O ZGRADI nova postojeća rekonstrukcija
 Vrsta zgrade (prema Pravilniku): odaberi vrstu zgrade prema Pravilniku iz padajućeg izbornika
 Vrsta zgrade prema sličnosti tehničkih sustava: odaberi vrstu zgrade prema Pravilniku iz padajućeg izbornika
 Vlasnik / investitor: _____
 I.č.br.: _____ k.č.: _____
 Površina korisne površine grijanog dijela zgrade A_c : _____ Godina izgradnje / rekonstrukcije: _____
 Građevinska (bruto) površina zgrade $[m^2]$: _____ Mjerska metarološka postaja: _____
 Faktor obilja f_s $[m^2]$: _____ Referentna klima: _____

ENERGETSKI RAZREDI ZGRADE

Specifična godišnja potrebna toplinska energija za grijanje Q_{kise} $[kWh/(m^2 \cdot a)]$	Specifična godišnja primarna energija E_{kise} $[kWh/(m^2 \cdot a)]$
D 128,88	C 82,81

Uspitati „nZEB“ ako zgrade zadovoljava zahtjeve za zgrade gotovo nulte energije propisane važećim TPBUETZZZ ¹

Pojedinačno zaštić. kulturno dobro/unutar zaštić. kult.-spovj(es. cjeline): unutar zaštićene kulturno – povijesne cjeline

Specifična godišnja emisija CO₂ $[kg/(m^2 \cdot a)]$ ¹: 145

ROK VAŽENJA CERTIFIKATA / PODACI O OSOBI KOJA JE IZDALA ENERGETSKI CERTIFIKAT

Oznaka energetskog certifikata	Datum izdavanja	Datum važenja
Ime i prezime ovlaštene osobe	Registarski broj	
Ime i prezime imenovane osobe a ovlaštanoj pravnoj osobi ili ime i prezime ovlaštene fizičke osobe / potpis		

PODACI O OSOBAMA KOJE SU SUDJELOVALE U IZRADI ENERGETSKOG CERTIFIKATA

Ime i prezime ovlaštene osobe	Gradjevinski	Strojarski	Elektrotehnički
Ime i prezime ovlaštene osobe			
Registarski broj			
Potpis			

¹ Za objava i izračunavanje podataka i algoritamski programi za izračunavanje podataka i izdava tehničkih sustava

ENERGETSKI CERTIFIKAT str. 1/4

Figure 11 The visual identity of first page for EPC in Croatia.

2.2.5.3 Qualification of certifiers

In Croatia, Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) can be issued exclusively by authorised natural persons or legal entities who meet the requirements defined by national legislation. The certification system is designed to ensure a

high level of professional competence and reliability in the assessment of building energy performance.

To become an authorised EPC certifier, candidates must fulfil several key requirements:

- Relevant educational background: Applicants must hold a university degree in a technical field, such as engineering, architecture, construction, or related disciplines, ensuring adequate knowledge of building physics, energy systems, and construction practices.
- Completion of accredited training programmes: Candidates are required to successfully complete a specialised training programme focused on energy performance assessment of buildings. These programmes are delivered by training providers appointed by the competent Ministry for a fixed period.
- Passing a professional exam: After completing the training, candidates must pass a professional examination, which verifies their theoretical knowledge and practical ability to perform EPC calculations and assessments in accordance with national methodologies.

Once these conditions are met, the candidate is granted authorisation and entered into the national registry of certified experts, which is maintained at the central level. This registry ensures transparency and allows public access to information on qualified certifiers.

2.2.5.4 Other initiatives

In addition to the established Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) system, Croatia is progressively developing and participating in several initiatives that are closely related to Building Renovation Passports (BRP), digitalization of building data, and the future integration of life-cycle assessment (LCA) principles.

One of the key national frameworks is the Long-Term Renovation Strategy, which sets out a roadmap for the decarbonization of the building stock by 2050. The strategy promotes deep renovation, improved energy performance monitoring, and the gradual introduction of more comprehensive tools for renovation planning. Although not yet formally implemented, the strategy provides the strategic basis for the future development of BRP-like approaches in Croatia⁶⁰.

⁶⁰ Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets of the Republic of Croatia, Long-Term Strategy for Renovation of the National Building Stock until 2050. Available at:

Croatia is also actively involved in several EU-funded projects that aim to enhance EPC systems and introduce elements of Building Renovation Passports.

The application of life-cycle assessment (LCA) in the building sector in Croatia is currently at an early but developing stage. While LCA is not yet integrated into the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) framework or national building regulations, several initiatives and trends indicate a gradual shift towards its adoption. At the national level, LCA principles are increasingly recognized through strategic and research-oriented activities, rather than through mandatory regulatory requirements. The Long-Term Renovation Strategy of the building stock acknowledges the importance of reducing not only operational energy use but also the overall environmental impact of buildings, which implicitly supports the future integration of life-cycle approaches. At present, Croatia does not have a dedicated national tool for life-cycle assessment (LCA) of buildings comparable to those developed in some other EU Member States. The application of LCA is therefore largely based on the use of internationally recognized methodologies and software tools.

2.2.6 Czech Republic

2.2.6.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In Czech Republic, the official EPC is the Průkaz energetické náročnosti budovy (PENB). The Ministry of Industry and Trade explains that the PENB classifies buildings from A to G based on the energy needed for their typical use, and that the calculation is theoretical rather than based on utility bills so that buildings remain comparable. The current methodological basis is Decree No. 264/2020 Coll., which replaced the earlier 2013 decree and entered into force on 1 September 2020 as the implementing regulation to the Energy Management Act. The PENB is required for new buildings, major changes to completed buildings, sales and rentals, and certain public-authority buildings. The certificate is valid for ten years, unless a major building change or a change in heating, cooling or domestic-hot-water preparation triggers earlier replacement

⁶¹ ⁶²

https://mpgi.gov.hr/UserDocsImages/dokumentni/EnergetskaUcinkovitost/Long_Term_Renovation_Strategy_EN.pdf

⁶¹ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. “Průkaz energetické náročnosti budovy.” Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁶² Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. “Plnění požadavků na energetickou náročnost budov od 1. září 2020.” Accessed March 26, 2026.

2.2.6.2 Energy-performance indicators

Under Section 3 of Decree 264/2020 Coll., the building energy performance indicators per m² are: non-renewable primary energy, total delivered energy, delivered energy by technical system (heating, cooling, ventilation, humidity control, hot water and lighting), the average heat-transfer coefficient, the U-values of individual envelope elements, and the efficiency of technical systems. The Ministry further explains that the PENB's graphic part classifies the building according to non-renewable primary energy, while also showing the classes of the other indicators. It additionally includes the indicator of specific heating need, which can be used to place the building within standards such as low-energy or passive-house level, and it shows the percentage split of delivered energy by energy carrier ⁶³.

2.2.6.3 Qualification of certifiers

EPCs may be prepared only by an authorized energy specialist. The Ministry states that only a specialist entered in the official list has the right to perform the activity and issue the relevant documents. Both natural persons and legal persons may hold authorization, but for legal persons the expertise requirement is fulfilled through an employed authorized specialist. For natural persons, the Ministry sets education-and-experience thresholds: for example, a relevant university degree plus three years of practice, a relevant higher-vocational qualification plus five years, or a relevant secondary qualification plus six years. The authorization procedure for natural persons includes a professional examination, and the Ministry explains that the exam currently consists of a written test and an oral examination under the specialist-activity regulation ⁶⁴ ⁶⁵ ⁶⁶.

2.2.7 Denmark

2.2.7.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

The Danish system for energy performance certification of buildings (EPC) is based on three key legislative documents. The Act on the Promotion of Energy

⁶³ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. "Vyhláška č. 264/2020 Sb., o energetické náročnosti budov." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁶⁴ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. "Energetičtí specialisté." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁶⁵ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. "Jak se stát energetickým specialistou." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁶⁶ Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. "Seznam energetických specialistů." Accessed March 26, 2026.

Savings in Buildings⁶⁷ sets out the fundamental rules of the system, including the obligations of building owners, implementation oversight, penalty provisions, qualification requirements for certified experts, and the management of the national EPC register. The Executive Order on the Energy Labelling of Buildings⁶⁸ provides detailed regulation of the EPC methodology, the procedures for preparing EPC reports, documentation and data requirements, mandatory training for energy consultants, and mechanisms for internal and external quality control. A central methodological basis is also provided by the Handbook for energy consultants⁶⁹, which is a mandatory technical handbook containing calculation methods, algorithms, input data requirements, catalogues of U-values, emission factors, and precise definitions of energy-performance indicators that must be applied in EPC assessments.

EPC is mandatory in several cases. When a building or unit is sold, the EPC must be made available to the buyer before the contract is signed. For rental agreements lasting more than four weeks, the certificate must be provided to the tenant before the lease is concluded. In the case of new constructions, an EPC is required before the building can be approved for use and must be submitted to the municipality. Public buildings larger than 250 m² must hold a valid EPC, which must also be clearly displayed for users. Likewise, buildings over 600 m² that are frequently visited by the public must have the EPC physically displayed.

In Denmark, an Energy Performance Certificate is valid for up to 10 years, but it becomes invalid sooner if major changes affecting the building's energy performance are carried out, such as significant renovations or upgrades of technical systems. The minister may also establish additional conditions for validity, including situations requiring a new certificate and the requirement that the EPC be properly registered in the national register.

The Danish EPC is always calculated using a standardized methodology, as defined in BEK 549/2023 and the HB2023. This means that the energy rating is based on a modelled energy calculation and a building inspection, using mandatory procedures, catalogues and calculation rules specified in HB2023. An exception is only possible for newer single-family houses, where the regulation allows the EPC to be issued without a physical building inspection in certain cases.

⁶⁷ Act on the Promotion of Energy Savings in Buildings. Lov om fremme af energibesparelser i bygninger (LBK 1253/2025). Source: <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2025/1253>

⁶⁸ Executive Order on the Energy Labelling of Buildings. Bekendtgørelse om energimærkning af bygninger (BEK 549/2023). Source: <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2023/549>

⁶⁹ Handbook for Energy Consultants. Håndbog for Energikonsulenter (HB2023). Source: <https://www.hbemo.dk/haandbog-for-energikonsulenter-hb2023>

2.2.7.2 Energy-performance indicators

The technical indicators of the Danish EPC are defined exclusively in the Handbook for energy consultants (HB2023), which serves as the mandatory methodological basis referenced by national legislation. EPC calculations include:

- delivered energy (Edel, kWh/m²·year) covering heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting;
- the calculation of heating demand (Q_{h,nd}, kWh/m²·year) under standardized conditions to evaluate the thermal performance of the building envelope;
- primary energy (EP, kWh/m²·year) is determined using Danish primary-energy conversion factors;
- CO₂ emissions (kg CO₂/m²·year), calculated on the basis of energy flows and fuel-specific emission factors provided in HB2023's catalogue;
- construction-related performance indicators comprise U-values (W/m²K), sourced from the HB2023 U-value catalogue, which defines thermal transmittance for walls, roofs, floors, windows and doors;
- linear thermal bridges (Ψ-values, W/m·K), which must be applied in the EPC to account for transmission losses at joints and edges of building components.

The Danish energy-efficiency classes are defined in HB2023 and are based on the requirements of the building regulations BR2010, BR2015 and BR2020.

- Class A2020: corresponds to the BR2020 standard (nearly zero-energy building – nZEB), has the lowest primary-energy demand and represents the highest energy-efficiency class.
- Class A2015: corresponds to BR2015, indicating very low energy consumption typical of modern low-energy buildings.
- Class A2010: corresponds to BR2010, indicating well-insulated buildings with low energy demand.
- Class B: includes modern, well-maintained buildings with relatively low energy needs.
- Class C: represents average buildings that comply with the minimum requirements of older building regulations.

- Classes D–G: cover progressively lower levels of energy performance, with Class G representing the least efficient buildings, typically characterised by poor insulation and outdated technical systems.

The threshold values for each class are shown in the table below.

Scale step	Limit value in kWh/m ² year
A2020	27
A2015	$< 30.0 + 1000/A$
A2010	$< 52.5 + 1650/A$
B	$< 70.0 + 2200/A$
C	$< 110 + 3200/A$
D	$< 150 + 4200/A$
E	$< 190 + 5200/A$
F	$< 240 + 6500/A$
G	$> 240 + 6500/A$

A is the heated area in m².

Figure 12 Scale for housing in Denmark (Source: Handbook for energy consultants (HB2023))

The Danish energy performance certificate is a standardized official document that presents the building's energy rating together with a concise technical report. The first page displays the rating, basic building information, a summary of the calculated energy use, annual energy costs and CO₂ emissions, along with several key recommendations provided by the energy consultant.

The report then includes a summary of potential savings, covering the expected annual energy savings, emission reductions and estimated investment costs for individual measures, distinguishing between those that are economically viable and those that are less so. The core part of the certificate consists of a detailed technical description of the building, covering construction elements and technical systems, and, where necessary, simple schematic drawings.

For each proposed measure, the certificate specifies its description, the expected energy and financial savings, CO₂-reduction, estimated costs and implementation time. It also provides an overview of the standardized calculation of energy costs.

The visual appearance of the Danish Energy Performance Certificate is shown in the image below.

Figure 13 Visual identity of first page for EPC in Denmark⁷⁰

2.2.7.3 Qualification of certifiers

The Danish EPC system defines the qualifications of EPC experts through clearly specified legal and technical requirements. The Act on the Promotion of Energy Savings in Buildings (LBK 1253/2025) stipulates in Article 24 the mandatory registration, certification and accreditation of energy consultants and companies authorised to carry out EPC assessments, and establishes the framework for supervision of their work. The BEK 549/2023 regulation further details, in Chapters 6 and 12, the requirements for certified companies, rules for internal and external quality control, and supervisory procedures, including the possibility of issuing warnings or revoking a certificate. The key technical document, the Handbook for Energy Consultants (HB2023), prescribes the training programmes Energy Consultant I and Energy Consultant II, the mandatory training content, and the catalogue of required professional competences, such as knowledge of building thermal properties, technical systems, and calculation methodologies.

To become an energy consultant, an individual must hold an appropriate technical qualification (e.g., engineer, architect, building constructor or a related

⁷⁰ Visual identity of first page for EPC in Denmark. Source: <https://naturstyrelsen.dk/media/hoiophee/energimaerke.pdf>

profession) and must successfully complete the prescribed training, which includes theoretical modules and a practical examination. Consultants are also required to undergo regular professional development, as refresher training is mandatory every three years. In addition, they must be employed by a certified company that has an established quality-management system in accordance with DS/EN ISO 9001, as required by BEK 549/2023.

Supervision of EPC professionals is strictly regulated. LBK 1253/2025, in Articles 30–32, defines supervisory powers, administrative measures and fines in cases of non-compliance. BEK 549/2023 additionally requires regular internal audits and external reviews of 5–10% of all issued EPCs, ensuring consistent quality and adherence to the prescribed methodology.

2.2.7.4 Other initiatives

The Danish Building Renovation Passport – BRP is still in the implementation phase and is currently not mandatory. The Danish version of the BRP will be a digital document that brings together key information about a building and provides a step-by-step renovation roadmap as well as an overview of its energy and environmental profile. The system will form part of the National Building Renovation Plan, which is expected to be finalized in 2026, and will remain voluntary and separate from the EPC, which continues to be a mandatory instrument.

Denmark has fully implemented the digitalization of its Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) system. A national digital database has been established, providing complete access to all issued EPCs. Access to EPC data is further expanded through the EMOData API offered by the Danish Energy Agency, enabling professional use of EPC data by researchers, companies and institutions. In addition to digitalization, Denmark is also carrying out measures to improve the quality of EPC data. Altogether, this means that Denmark already operates a fully digitalized EPC system, a public data platform, API access and structured data flows.

Alongside digitalization, Denmark has also abolished the measured EPC method. The methodology based on actual measured energy consumption was discontinued due to methodological unreliability and extremely limited use in practice. As a result, the Danish EPC system has been fully transitioned to the standardized calculation-based methodology defined in HB2023.

2.2.8 France

2.2.8.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

In France, the Energy Performance Certificate is called the Diagnostic de Performance Énergétique (DPE). This national scheme is mainly anchored in

the French Construction and Housing Code⁷¹, which establishes the legal obligation for EPCs (DPE) and in ministerial orders (especially Arrêté of 31 March 2021)⁷² that specify calculation methods and certification procedures.⁷³ Regarding the Building Renovation Passport (BRP), France does not yet have a formal national system in place, although mandatory energy audits (since 2023) are conceptually similar, as they provide structured renovation pathways for building upgrades.⁷⁴

The French Construction and Housing Code makes EPCs (DPE) mandatory for property sales and transfers, rentals, new constructions or off-plan sales, major renovations, and for large public buildings over 250m². Certain exemptions or specific provisions apply to buildings used less than four months per year, rural lease contracts and seasonal rental agreements, as well as some historic monuments, while small dwellings under 50m² are subject to adapted DPE calculation rules. In addition, the Climate and Resilience Law transform the DPE into a regulatory instrument that determines rental eligibility and market access by introducing a progressive rental ban for low-performing dwellings: class G from 2025, class F from 2028, and class E from 2034, thereby strengthening its enforceability. The DPE may also be required to access certain public financial support schemes for energy renovation. Modern DPEs are generally valid for 10 years, provided no major renovation is carried out.

France EPC uses the standardized calculation method “Calcul de la Consommation Conventionnelle des Logements” (3CL) defined by the Arrêté of 31 March 2021 (and its updates) and explained in the government-issued 3CL guide. The calculation estimates energy consumption and CO₂ emissions based on EPBD requirements; Building geometry and orientation, Insulation and envelope characteristics (walls, roof, windows), Heating, cooling, ventilation, and hot water systems, for standardized occupancy and energy usage assumptions. Lighting energy is included in calculations only for non-residential or public buildings exceeding 250 m² (specially, if it has centralised system). France is divided into 8 main climatic zones (4 winter zones and 4 summers zones; labeled H1a, H1b, H1c, H2a, H2b, H2c, H2d, and H3). These zones are used in the DPE calculation to adjust heating and cooling energy needs, reflecting differences in temperature, solar radiation, and seasonal variation across the country.

⁷¹ Code de la construction et de l'habitation: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>

⁷² Arrêté du 31 mars 2021 relatif au diagnostic de performance énergétique pour les bâtiments ou parties de bâtiments à usage d'habitation en France métropolitaine // Arrêté du 31 mars 2021 relatif aux méthodes et procédures applicables au diagnostic de performance énergétique et aux logiciels l'établissant: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>

⁷³ ADEME website: <https://observatoire-dpe-audit.ademe.fr/faq>

⁷⁴ Build up: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/fr/resources-and-tools/articles/anticipation-du-passeport-de-renovation-en-france-avant-lecheance>

- France has a single national certification system. Although there are different formats of the energy certificate depending on the type of building use (residential and tertiary)⁷⁵

- The data obtained for preparing an EPC come from a combination of sources. At least, on-site data collection about the general building characteristics (location, geometry, building envelope composition...) and its systems, as a physical inspection of the building is always required. In addition, building documentation is used (architectural and engineering plans available, year of construction, technical datasheets of the installed equipment...). Occupancy and weather data in the French EPC are standardized assumptions defined in the 3CL methodology, not real measurements.

The data obtained for preparing an EPC come from a combination of sources, mainly: On-site data collection about the general building characteristics (location, geometry, building envelope composition...) and its systems (heating, cooling and DHW systems, ventilation systems and renewal installations). In addition, data from building documentation (architectural and engineering plans available, year of construction, technical datasheets of the installed equipment ...).

The meteorological data used in EPC calculations come from standardized reference datasets based on historical measurements from the official national meteorological agency. Occupancy is estimated using standardized profiles and schedules to predict energy use.

2.2.8.2 Energy-performance indicators

Both models of EPCs, residential and tertiary, include the following two energy indicators:

- Primary energy consumption (kWhEP/m²/year): this accounts for the amount of energy for uses related to heating, cooling, domestic hot water (DHW), ventilation, and lighting when applicable. It is a single value that includes the type of energy (renewable or non-renewable) through conversion factors to primary energy.
- Greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂/m²/year): calculated from the same energy uses, reflecting CO₂ emissions based on the energy source.

In addition, residential EPCs include other indicators and complementary information:

- Final energy consumption (kWh/m²/year): this accounts for the amount of delivered energy for uses related to heating, cooling, DHW, ventilation,

⁷⁵ <https://rt-re-batiment.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/modeles-des-dpe-a788.html>

and lighting when applicable. It includes both renewable and non-renewable energy.

- Primary energy consumption used for heating (kWhEP/year): this accounts only for the primary energy used for heating.
- Primary energy consumption used for DHW (kWhEP/year): this accounts only for the primary energy used for domestic hot water.
- Primary energy consumption used for cooling (kWhEP/year): this accounts only for the primary energy used for cooling.
- Primary energy consumption used for lighting (kWhEP/year): this accounts only for the primary energy used for lighting.
- Primary energy consumption used for auxiliaries (kWhEP/year): this accounts only for the primary energy used for fans and pumps.

Moreover, the residential EPC shows the estimated annual energy cost for each use, rates the energy efficiency of the building envelope elements (on four levels), and proposes several recommendations regarding user behaviour and renovation actions to improve the energy performance of the building, distinguishing between priority (essential actions) and recommended (optional actions).

Figure 14 Visual identity of different pages of French residential EPCs, showing the QR code, the rating system and several energy indicators (detailed energy consumption data by type of use including cost-estimation).

The French EPC (DPE) uses a 7-level A to G rating scale based on absolute thresholds for:

- Primary energy consumption (kWhEP/m²/year)
- Greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂/m²/year)

However, no official source explicitly presents the minimum and maximum values for each class in a single consolidated table. Since the 2021 reform, the final DPE rating corresponds to the worst result between the two indicators (energy or CO₂)

2.2.8.3 Qualification of certifiers

In France, EPC (DPE) diagnosticians must be formally trained (minimum 56 hours), professionally accredited through COFRAC-recognized certification bodies (valid for 7 years), and insured. Candidates must pass an exam composed of theoretical and practical components. Two types of accreditations exist: without mention, allowing diagnostics in individual residential buildings, and with mention, required for collective residential buildings and non-residential (tertiary) buildings, the latter including additional training (minimum +21 hours). They are responsible for on-site inspections, applying the official calculation methodology, and submitting the certificate to ADEME, including a QR code for traceability. Non-compliance (e.g., using non-accredited professionals) may result in fines for both property owners and diagnosticians.⁷⁶

At least since 2025, all DPE certificates include a unique QR code. This QR code links to a central digital record of the certificate, allowing authorities, buyers, and tenants to quickly verify its authenticity and details. It helps prevent fraud, such as the use of fake or outdated certificates in property transactions. The QR code system for French DPE certificates was introduced through implementing amendments to the Arrêté du 31 mars 2021, notably the Arrêté du 20 juillet 2023, as part of the digital traceability system linked to the ADEME national DPE database.

2.2.8.4 Other initiatives

- Energy Audits (existing before EPBD 2024)⁷⁷

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) introduces the concept of a “Renovation Passport”, understood as a tailored roadmap to guide building owners towards deep, step-by-step renovation. In France, although this concept

⁷⁶ Source: <https://entreprendre.service-public.gouv.fr/vosdroits/F38442>

⁷⁷ Build up website: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/fr/resources-and-tools/articles/anticipation-du-passeport-de-renovation-en-france-avant-lecheance>

is not implemented as a formal Building Renovation Passport per se, it is effectively reflected by the mandatory energy audit.

Both EPC and Energy audits, are based on calculated and modelled energy data (not measured consumption). While the EPC (DPE) provides a static snapshot of a building's performance, classifying it from A to G and providing only general improvement recommendations, the energy audit is a dynamic, forward-looking planning tool. It is mandatory since 1 April 2023 for the sale of single-family homes or buildings in sole ownership rated F or G (the so-called "energy sieves"), and will be extended to class E in 2025 and class D in 2034.

The French regulatory energy audit must provide at least two renovation scenarios tailored to the specific characteristics of the building:

1. single-step deep renovation pathway, aiming at comprehensive performance improvement;
2. multi-step renovation pathway, allowing costs to be spread over time while ensuring technical consistency.

For each step in the renovation pathway, the audit must include an estimate of costs and a description of available financial incentives (national and local schemes). These costs are also compared with expected energy savings and the theoretical impact of the proposed measures on energy bills.

Postes de travaux concernés	Performance énergétique et environnementale globale du bâtiment	Économies d'énergie par rapport à l'état initial	Dépenses d'énergie estimées/an	Coût estimé des travaux (**TTC)
Avant travaux	149 88 F		de 600€ à 500€	
Scénario 1 (détails p.9)	138 6 B	-76% (cumulatif)	de 600€ à 500€	+ 36 000 € - 55 300 €
Scénario 2 (détails p.11)	126 18 B	-76% (cumulatif)	de 600€ à 500€	+ 24 000 € - 36 000 €
Deuxième étape :	126 18 B	-76% (cumulatif)	de 600€ à 500€	+ 12 800 € - 19 200 €

Figure 15 Visual identity of the French Energy Audits, focus on recommended renovation actions to improve the energy performance of the building in different phases, it includes renovation costs and economic estimation of energy savings

2.2.9 Greece

2.2.9.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

Greece's official EPC scheme is the Πιστοποιητικό Ενεργειακής Απόδοσης (PEA), implemented under the national Regulation on the Energy Performance of Buildings (KENAK) and the legal framework for Energy Inspectors. The Ministry of Environment and Energy states that building energy inspections were institutionalised through KENAK and Presidential Decree 100/2010, while the current EPBD implementation framework is anchored in Law 4122/2013, later amended by Law 4685/2020^{78 79}. The Technical Chamber of Greece (TEE) hosts the technical implementation environment for KENAK, including the technical guidelines (T.O.T.E.E.) and the dedicated calculation software, while the official BuildingCert platform functions as the national register of inspectors and archive of inspections. In operational terms, the scheme is used both for regulatory compliance and for market transactions: the Ministry requires a valid PEA for any building offered for sale or lease, and from 1 January 2021 the energy class must be stated in all advertisements. Greece also runs a formal quality-control regime: the Ministry's inspection departments in Northern and Southern Greece carry out random and complaint-based checks on PEAs, with at least 5% of certificates subject to review^{80 81 82}.

2.2.9.2 Energy-performance indicators

In Greece, the KENAK calculation methodology does not rely only on envelope thermal properties, but also on heating, cooling and domestic hot water systems, the use of renewable energy sources, passive heating and cooling, shading, indoor air quality, adequate daylighting, and overall building design. Public-facing official descriptions make clear that the PEA's headline outputs include the building's computed annual total energy consumption and its annual CO₂ emissions, while the market-facing output shown in advertisements is the building's energy class. Official BuildingCert material further indicates that the rating is based on the calculated specific primary energy consumption in

⁷⁸ Ministry of Environment and Energy. "Ενεργειακή Επιθεώρηση." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁷⁹ Ministry of Environment and Energy. "Κανονισμός Ενεργειακής Απόδοσης Κτιρίων." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸⁰ Technical Chamber of Greece. "Νομοθεσία (KENAK)." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸¹ Ministry of Environment and Energy. "Με «ενεργειακό πιστοποιητικό» όλες οι αγγελίες πώλησης/μίσθωσης ακινήτων από 1.1.2021." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸² Ministry of Environment and Energy. "Αποτελέσματα Ελέγχων." Accessed March 26, 2026.

kWh/m², and that PEAs must include ranked recommendations for improvement
83 84

2.2.9.3 Qualification of certifiers

In Greece, EPCs are issued by registered Energy Inspectors, whose profession was established through Presidential Decree 100/2010. The TEE's KENAK legislation page shows that the qualification framework includes both the decree itself and a joint ministerial decision on the education and examination procedure for Energy Inspectors. The official BuildingCert register publicly shows that the profession has historically been structured by engineering qualification and licence class, distinguishing at least A-class and B-class licences: the public registry interface states that A-class inspectors may inspect residential buildings and related systems up to 100 kW, whereas B-class inspectors may inspect buildings of all categories and uses^{85 86}. The same public interface also shows that registration is tied to a formal national registry and digital authentication, while the BuildingCert homepage notes that, from 12 July 2025, a new ministerial decision regulates the qualifications for registration and the operation of the registry and archive.

2.2.9.4 Other initiatives

The Greek Electronic Building Identity (Ηλεκτρονική Ταυτότητα Κτιρίου) is relevant to the enhanced-EPC discussion because it operates as a digital building logbook that consolidates core building information in a permanent electronic record. According to the Ministry of Environment and Energy, the system entered full operation on 1 January 2021 on a voluntary basis for one month and became mandatory from 1 February 2021, ending its earlier pilot status. It is implemented through the digital platform operated by the Technical Chamber of Greece (TEE), and the filing is carried out by an authorized engineer for either a whole building or an individual subdivided property unit. Greek legislation specifies that the file includes, among other things, the building permit and its revisions, the approved drawings, the accessibility study where required, the Energy Performance Certificate, any construction-control certificate, declarations concerning the regularization of unauthorized works, and plans reflecting the actual built condition. Once completed, the system generates a Certificate of Completeness and a unique electronic code, which

⁸³ BuildingCert. "ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΚΗ ΕΠΙΘΕΩΡΗΣΗ ΚΤΙΡΙΩΝ." PDF guide. Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸⁴ BuildingCert. "ΥΠΕΚΑ - Αρχείο Ενεργειακών Επιθεωρήσεων." Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸⁵ BuildingCert. "ΥΠΕΚΑ - Μητρώο Προσωρινών Ενεργειακών Επιθεωρητών & Αρχείο Ενεργειακών Επιθεωρήσεων." Public registry interface. Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸⁶ BuildingCert. "ΥΠΕΝ - Μητρώο Ενεργειακών Επιθεωρητών & Αρχείο Ενεργειακών Επιθεωρήσεων." Accessed March 26, 2026.

can also be used to verify authenticity and reissue the certificate. The Ministry describes the system as a tool for increasing transparency in property transactions and reducing bureaucracy by giving owners a digital “radiography” of the asset. The legal framework also requires the record to be updated after building works that require a permit or minor-works approval, which makes it a living record ^{87 88}.

The D²EPC project reconceptualises the EPC as a dynamic, data-driven instrument rather than a static asset rating. Coordinated by the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), the project develops EPC methodologies informed by measured operational data, smart metering, and a digital twin/BIM-based framework. It integrates indicators beyond energy demand alone, including environmental, financial, and user-centred comfort indicators, with explicit attention to thermal comfort, daylight, indoor air quality, and life-cycle-related dimensions. The project also developed a digital platform capable of issuing next-generation EPCs while supporting forecasting, benchmarking, alerts, and tailored recommendations for renovation and operation ^{89 90}.

A complementary line of development is represented by iBRoad2EPC, coordinated by Sympraxis Team P.C. in Greece. Whereas D²EPC focuses on operational enhancement, iBRoad2EPC addresses the limited strategic value of conventional EPCs for long-term renovation planning. The project integrates elements of the Building Renovation Passport (BRP) and the Digital Building Logbook (DBL) into EPC schemes, thereby repositioning the certificate as a decision-support instrument for staged deep renovation. It also enriches EPC content with indoor environmental quality, comfort-related parameters, smart-building dimensions, and, where possible, measured energy use. Equally important is its emphasis on implementation, including training modules for energy experts and auditors ⁹¹.

The most comprehensive initiative in thematic scope is SmartLivingEPC, also coordinated by CERTH in Thessaloniki. This project aims to develop a digitally issued certificate that combines designed and actual performance within a broader evaluative framework. Its methodological ambition is particularly

⁸⁷ Technical Chamber of Greece (TEE). “Ηλεκτρονική Ταυτότητα Κτιρίου (Electronic Building Identity Platform).” Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸⁸ Ministry of Environment and Energy. “Law 4495/2017: Control and Protection of the Built Environment.” Government Gazette A 167/03.11.2017. Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁸⁹ D²EPC Consortium. “Next-generation Dynamic Digital EPCs for Enhanced Quality and User Awareness.” Coordinated by CERTH. Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁹⁰ Ioannidis, Dimosthenis, et al. “D2EPC: BIM-based Digital Twin Framework for Energy Performance Certificates.” Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH). Accessed March 26, 2026.

⁹¹ Sympraxis Team P.C. “iBRoad2EPC: Integrating Building Renovation Passports into EPC Schemes.” Accessed March 26, 2026.

relevant for future EPC reform because it incorporates life-cycle performance, building smartness, actual technical-system performance, water consumption, and noise/acoustic indicators. It is also designed to interoperate with digital logbooks and building renovation passports⁹².

⁹² SmartLivingEPC Consortium. "SmartLivingEPC: A New Concept for Next-Generation Energy Performance Certificates." Coordinated by CETH. Accessed March 26, 2026.

2.2.10 Malta

2.2.10.1 General framework of EPC and BRP

The Maltese framework for energy performance certificates is governed by the main legal act S.L. 623.01 – Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations⁹³⁹⁴, which has been amended several times (LN 47/2018, 134/2020, 409/2021, 231/2022, 305/2023) to improve energy efficiency and strengthen alignment with European obligations. In 2023, the Energy Performance of Buildings (Amendment) Regulations, LN 1786/2023⁹⁵ were also adopted. This amendment does not replace the main act but supplements it in accordance with Directive (EU) 2018/844, introduces new minimum energy efficiency requirements, and establishes stricter technical standards for buildings constructed after 1 July 2024. The key technical documents supporting the legislation are Technical Document F (2023), divided into three parts (Part 1: Dwellings, Part 2: Non Dwellings, Part 3: Technical Systems), which set mandatory minimum energy performance requirements for buildings and technical systems. The entire legal framework is based on the full implementation of two EU directives: Directive 2010/31/EU (EPBD) and Directive (EU) 2018/844, which establish minimum standards for building energy performance and guide Member States towards renovating the building stock and improving energy management.

The issuance of an Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) in Malta is legally required in several situations. For all new buildings, an asset rating EPC, based on the building as actually constructed, must be obtained before the building is completed. In addition, in certain cases, particularly when selling property prior to construction, a design rating EPC is required, prepared on the basis of the design documentation. An EPC is also mandatory for any sale or new rental of a building or part of a building, regardless of its size or type. A special obligation applies to public buildings with visitors and a floor area greater than 250 m². For these buildings, the EPC must not only be obtained but also visibly displayed on

⁹³ S.L. 623.01 – Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations (LN 47/2018, LN 134/2020, LN 409/2021, LN 231/2022, LN 305/2023). Building and Construction Authority Act (Cap. 623). <https://bca.gov.mt/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/SL-623.01-Energy-Performance-of-Building-Regulations.pdf>

⁹⁴ S.L. 623.01 – Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations (LN 47/2018, LN 134/2020, LN 409/2021, LN 231/2022, LN 305/2023). Building and Construction Authority Act (Cap. 623). <https://bca.gov.mt/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/SL-623.01-Energy-Performance-of-Building-Regulations.pdf>

⁹⁵ Energy Performance of Buildings (Amendment) Regulations, 2023 – LN 1786/2023. <https://bca.gov.mt/news-2/publication-of-the-energy-performance-of-buildings-amendment-regulations/>

site. In advertisements for the sale or rental of property, the EPC energy indicator must be stated, ensuring transparency for buyers and tenants. The regulation also establishes several exemptions, including protected cultural properties (e.g., Grade 1 and Grade 2 buildings), places of worship, very small buildings with a net floor area below 50 m², temporary structures with a lifespan of less than two years, and certain industrial or agricultural buildings with low energy demand.

The Energy Performance Certificate is valid for ten years from the date of issue, except in cases where significant changes are made to the building that may alter its energy performance. A new EPC is required when major renovation works are carried out that affect the thermal characteristics of the building envelope or its technical systems, or when key energy systems, such as heating, cooling, or ventilation, are replaced. Re issuance is also required in the event of a substantial change in the building's use or when its geometry or an essential part of its structure is modified. The purpose of these provisions is to ensure that the EPC always reflects the actual state of the building and its true energy performance.

In Maltese legislation, three types of Energy Performance Certificates are used, differing according to the timing and purpose of issuance. The design rating EPC is intended for the design stage and is issued before the building is constructed, with calculations based on the planned design. It is primarily required for the sale of properties that have not yet been built. The asset rating EPC is prepared after the building has been completed and is based on actual, as built data, making it the final and most important form of EPC. For certain single family houses, the law also permits a representational assessment, in which a reference calculation or a representative model may be used instead of an individual site inspection, provided specific conditions are met.

The Renovation Passport is not introduced as a mandatory instrument in Maltese legislation. In Subsidiary Legislation 623.01 (Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations), it is mentioned primarily as an additional, optional tool that building owners and professionals may use to plan staged energy renovations. As a concept, it provides guidance for preparing a long term renovation plan that includes a sequence of measures extending to 2050, along with milestone targets for intermediate periods such as 2030 and 2040. The purpose of the Renovation Passport is to facilitate strategic, phased renovation in line with EU objectives for achieving nearly zero energy buildings. However, the LN 1786/2023 Amendment does not introduce this document as a mandatory practice, meaning the Renovation Passport remains a purely voluntary option for those who wish to plan improvements systematically and over the long term.

2.2.10.2 Energy-performance indicators

Energy-performance indicators are presented below.

- Total primary energy (kWh/(m²·year)): Represents the total amount of primary energy required for the operation of the building, including heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, and domestic hot water.
- Non renewable primary energy (kWh/(m²·year)): The amount of primary energy from fossil or other non renewable sources, calculated according to national primary energy factors.
- Renewable primary energy (kWh/(m²·year)): Energy from renewable sources, including energy produced on site or supplied from the grid, treated separately from non renewable sources.
- Greenhouse gas emissions (kg CO₂eq/(m²·year)): A numerical indicator expressing the building's emissions, which may also serve as a supplementary energy performance indicator.
- Annual heating energy (kWh/(m²·year)): The energy required to heat the building under standardised reference conditions.
- Annual cooling energy (kWh/(m²·year)): The energy needed to cool the building under reference climatic conditions defined in the national methodology.
- Annual ventilation energy (kWh/(m²·year)): The energy consumed for mechanical ventilation and air treatment.
- Annual domestic hot water energy (kWh/(m²·year)): The energy required to produce sanitary hot water, based on typical building use.
- Annual lighting energy (kWh/(m²·year)): An indicator mainly used for non residential buildings, representing the energy required for artificial lighting.
- On site energy production (kWh/(m²·year)): Energy generated directly by the building itself (e.g., PV systems), accounted for separately as a contribution from renewable sources.
- Primary energy weighting factors (unitless): Nationally defined factors for converting delivered energy into primary energy, differentiated for renewable and non renewable sources.
- Typical use indicators: Standardised usage and occupancy profiles that ensure calculation consistency and comparability.
- Technical system performance indicators (kWh/(m²·year) or COP/SEER/SCOP): Efficiency ratings of HVAC, DHW, and lighting systems in accordance with European standards and the national methodology.

Energy efficiency classes are based on the value of primary energy and provide a standardized method for evaluating the energy performance of buildings. Although the regulation itself does not define letter classes (e.g., A, B, C), it stipulates that classes must be derived from the calculated primary energy indicator and must comply with the national EPC software iSBEM mt. The regulation also requires that minimum energy performance requirements for each building type be reviewed and updated at least every five years, ensuring alignment with evolving construction standards and European requirements.

In Malta, the energy classes shown on the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) are determined using the national iSBEM mt methodology, developed and maintained by the Building and Construction Authority (BCA). Legislation defines only the energy performance indicators, not the classes themselves, therefore, the classes are generated internally by the software. For each building, iSBEM mt first calculates the primary energy per square metre (kWh/m²·year), then compares this value with the performance of a “notional building” with standardized characteristics, which serves as the national benchmark. Based on this comparison, the software generates an EPC index – a normalized value that represents the building’s energy class in Malta. Since Malta does not use a publicly published A–G scale for primary energy, the EPC displays the class indirectly through an index arrow indicating the building’s performance relative to the notional reference. In contrast, the CO₂ emissions section of the EPC includes a clearly defined and publicly displayed A+–G scale, which is entirely separate from the primary energy class and does not affect the EPC index. As a result, the determination of energy classes in Malta is entirely dependent on the internal iSBEM mt calculation rather than on numerical thresholds published in legislation or technical documents.

The first page of the Maltese energy performance certificate is shown on the image below.

Figure 16 Visual identity of first page for EPC in Malta⁹⁶

2.2.10.3 Qualification of certifiers

Energy Performance Certificates may only be issued by appropriately trained and registered professionals. The regulation (S.L. 623.01) stipulates that architects and mechanical, electrical, or civil engineers are qualified for this task, provided they have successfully completed the accredited training required by the Building and Construction Authority (BCA). These professionals are listed in the official national register of EPB assessors, which is maintained by the BCA. Registration is not permanent. An EPB assessor must periodically renew their accreditation, as Regulation 25(6) specifies that registration must be renewed at intervals determined by the BCA and upon payment of the applicable fee. In addition, in accordance with Regulation 25(9)(a), the BCA may require mandatory periodic training. Failure to attend such training may result in temporary or permanent removal from the register.

The regulation also establishes a strict control system for EPC issuance. All assessors are subject to mandatory random checks, which must be carried out using a statistically representative sample based on a 95% confidence level and

⁹⁶ Visual identity of first page for EPC in Malta. Source: <https://bca.gov.mt/epcs/>

a maximum 5% margin of error. If irregularities are identified, the BCA may require the assessor to correct the errors, impose disciplinary measures, or even revoke their authorisation, with possible sanctions including financial penalties. This system ensures the quality, independence, and credibility of energy performance certificates.

2.2.10.4 Other initiatives

Malta is strengthening its Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) system primarily through participation in European projects such as CrossCert, which aims to create a more reliable, user friendly, and comparable EPC framework and introduces concepts such as the integration of real energy use data. Updates to the technical framework, including Technical Document F 2024, further influence EPC development by introducing stricter energy performance standards and consequently more demanding calculation requirements. The Building Renovation Passport (BRP) appears in Maltese legislation as an optional tool for long term building renovation planning, but the scheme has not yet been implemented in practice. Similarly, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is not currently part of Maltese regulation or the EPC methodology. It remains a developing concept discussed mainly in professional and research contexts related to the future of sustainable construction. Overall, both LCA and BRP represent the future direction of EPC system development in Malta and are expected to gain importance with the continued implementation of EU policy measures and the ongoing digitalisation of the construction sector.

3 EU FUNDED PROJECTS EPC/BRP

Over the last years, the EU has focused attention on financing projects facilitating the process of building renovation across Europe to reduce energy consumption and in turn associated emissions. The EU instruments and programmes developed to allocate funding in this focus area include Life, Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe. Through these programs, many projects have been developed considering pilots sites, while attempting to extrapolate methodologies, processes or information to serve other regions spread over the EU as a whole. In an ever-evolving legal framework and fluctuating situations arising, the objectives of each project have been to attempt to address some of the most relevant challenges of the time. To ensure continuity in the findings and the work of each project, subsequent projects have built upon past ones to optimize their outcomes. A brief review of some relatively recent projects that relate to EPC & BRP are described below.

3.1 EUB Superhub

[EUB Superhub](#) is a Horizon project that was active between June 2021 and December 2024 and formed by partners located in Germany, Italy, France, and Austria. EUB Superhub’s main objective was to develop a scalable methodology and digital building logbook (DBL) giving an “EUB e-passport” rating across energy, sustainability and smartness, holding EPCs and other certificates over the building lifecycle. To do so, the project has studied the current energy assessment schemes and certification methods available in the EU, to develop common criteria of certificates. Ultimately, the intent is for all Member States to be able to use the methodology and framework developed.

The figure below presents the different online tabs that direct users towards different platforms and tools developed by the project.

Figure 17 EUB Superhub – webpage screenshot of available tools and their description

The E-cockpit: is an open-access data hub that is cloud-based and geo-referenced and that enables digitalisation of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and sustainability ratings. Platform users (notably: policymakers, investors, and building owners) can view key building information and assess sustainability, smart readiness, and energy performance.

The Planning and Verification Tool (PVT): is a platform module designed to assist users in evaluating, simulating, and optimizing energy performance. It enables building owners, auditors, and planners to assess current energy efficiency, explore possible retrofitting options, and verify building performance metrics using real data and simulation models.

The Virtual Marketplace: is a matchmaking platform that connects building owners with service providers, including auditors, consultants, and funding organisations.

The E-training module provides educational resources, including e-learning materials, video tutorials, and webinars, aimed at training experts in energy efficiency, sustainability, and smart building solutions.

The project deliverables of potential interest to IEBRA that were developed include:

- D1.3 - Next generation certification: stakeholder needs and expectations: Is a report that focuses on national policies, initiatives, and current transition challenges related to next generation Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs).
- D2.1 - Use case scenarios and definitions: Is a report that focuses on defining use cases, user roles, and access rights for the platform to identify use case scenarios that meet the requirements of different users and support the development of platform functions.
- D2.2 - Definition of common transnational indicators and assessment metrics for the E-Passport: Is a report that defines and describes a core set of transnational Key Performance Indicators for the next generation of assessment and certification framework of buildings energy performance (EPCs), complemented by other sustainability indicators, all of them forming a harmonized building passport.

D2.5 - The EUB SuperHub Transnational en energy Hub: This deliverable illustrates the EUB SuperHub certification scheme, a roadmap to implement it across EU and a guide to assess the KPIs of the EUB e-Passport. All the aspects of a certification scheme such as quality control, verification, monitoring and inspection procedures, are described accordingly to the different stages of the EUB SuperHub certification process.

3.2 CrossCert

[CrossCert](#) is a Horizon project that was active between September 2021 and November 2024 and formed by partners located in ten EU countries, notably: Austria, Spain, Greece, Croatia, Poland, Bulgaria, Malta, Denmark, Slovenia, UK. CrossCert's main objective was to develop a product testing methodology for the new energy performance certificate (EPC) for buildings. To do so, it performed cross-testing between the current energy certificates and the new approaches/ concepts/ initiatives (140 buildings in 10 countries). In turn, it prepared policy recommendations that include improvements in accuracy, usability and harmonisation. The aim of the process was to enable the linking of next-generation EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs.

CrossCert's deliverables of interest to IEBRA are available on their project webpage as well as on Zenodo, and include:

- D3.4 Cross country comparison recommended improvements in different EPCs: The objective of this document is to identify and evaluate the results of previous and current European projects that have worked towards the enhancement of the Energy Performance Certification. It retrieves the information from those projects that have tested the current EPCs at a country level and/or have introduced improvements and/or have proposed new approaches, and new Key Performance Indicators or have tested new software for the energy assessment of buildings.
- CrossCert Final results: Is a document that recaps the key technical aspects of EPC methodologies, including calculation inputs and outputs, KPIs, performance gap, renovation measures, and quality verification methods to provide possible improvement suggestions for future EPCs and highlight the difficulties in achieving harmonisation across Europe.

3.3 TunES

[TunES](#) is a Life project that was active between September 2023 and September 2025 and formed by partners located in Austria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland and Slovenia. The main objective of the TunES project was to optimise Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) regulation to integrate it with the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) roll-out in 7 national Energy Agencies and develop guidance for other Member States. The core project outcome were seven national policy measure packages. On the EU-level, the comprehensive guidance strategy developed allows other stakeholders to access the cases and all tools for effective replication.

Deliverables for the TunES project were uploaded and are accessible on Zenodo. Some of the relevant deliverables to IEBRA include:

- EPC & SRI Practice collection: Which is a collection of existing practices relating to design, deployment and implementation of EPC and SRI.
- Report on survey and interview results: This report presents survey and interview results carried out online and with experts (including academics, industry professionals, and government authorities). With the objective to assess EPC regulation and SRI integration, the findings indicate the need for improved standardisation, training, and awareness to enhance EPC and SRI effectiveness.
- Policy-measure selection tool: Enabling the identification of compliance to EPBD and providing policy options.

3.4 TIMEPAC

[TIMEPAC](#) is a Horizon project that was active between July 2021 and October 2024 and focused on scenarios in six EU countries, Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, Slovenia and Spain. Its main objective was to enhance the full EPC process (generation, storage, analysis, exploitation) to deliver holistic, flexible digital EPCs, treating buildings as dynamic, occupant centric assets.

TIMEPAC also developed an array of training material categorized in the six groups shown on the image below, and accessible through their webpage:

TIMEPAC Academy

The TIMEPAC Academy further develops and uses the new EPC improvement tools and training materials (click on the Training scenario boxes to access).

Training scenarios

<p>Advanced methods and tools for holistic energy renovation of buildings</p> <p>Professional certifiers, architects, energy agencies, ESCOs</p>		
<p>Operational optimisation of building energy performance based on activities during EPC generation</p> <p>Professional certifiers, energy auditors, building managers, owners, tenants, energy agencies, ESCOs</p>		

Figure 18 TIMEPAC's training and webinar categories

The project's material and deliverables are available on their webpage, under the reports, academy and resources tabs. The following documents were identified as potentially relevant to the IEBRA project:

- [D3.3 Report on building Renovation Passports from enhanced EPC data](#);
- [Generating enhanced EPCs with BIM data](#); and
- [Creating building Renovation Passports from data repositories](#).

3.5 EPC RECAST

[EPC RECAST](#) is a Horizon 2020 project that was active between September 2020 and June 2024 and focused on pilots located in Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Luxembourg, Slovakia. The main project objective was to develop a structured process and toolbox for new-generation EPCs that better assesses building energy performance, retrofit needs, and financing opportunities. The EPC RECAST project software tools were designed to assist assessors to create the next generation of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs).

The collaborative web platform; KROQI was designed for the construction sector to enable smooth data exchange and collaboration, and to allow assessors to manage EPC RECASTXML files easily, run simulations and generate RoadMaps. The figure below represents the software chain that transforms the characteristics of the housing recorded by the assessor into a consolidated and reliable EPC. This figure shows that the KROQI platform is used at several stages of the software chain: for the collection and consolidation of information and parameters, to access to simulation tools and the roadmap, and also for the recording and sharing of the project's EPCs.

Figure 19 Representation of EPC RECAST process: from Input to EPC creation.

One of the options provided by the platform is the renovation roadmap that considers the existing and final renovation stages to produce a roadmap, as seen on the figure below.

Figure 20 Example of Renovation Roadmap summary

Deliverables of interest can be accessed on the EPC RECAST website, and include:

- EPC RECAST certification tool/platform: Is a report that explains the structure and main components of the developed platform.
- EPC RECAST Certificate and Renovation Roadmap Consolidated version: Is a consolidated report specifying the proposed EPC template, including KPIs, rating scale, introduction of additional indicators as IAQ, SRI, costs, use of metered energy and integrating the renovation roadmap.

3.6 D²EPC

D²EPC is a Horizon 2020 project that was active between September 2020 and August 2023 and focused on pilots located in Greece, Germany, and Cyprus. D²EPC's main objective was to create dynamic and digital EPCs based on near-real-time data, with indicators for energy, smart readiness, wellbeing, comfort, finance and sustainability, using BIM/GIS and cloud architecture. It proposed a framework based on the smart-readiness level of buildings and the corresponding data collection infrastructure and management systems. It used the operational data and the 'digital twin' concept to advance Building Information Modelling, to calculate a novel set of energy,

environmental, financial and human comfort/ wellbeing indicators, and through them the EPC classification of the building in question.

The created platform enabled users to monitor live data streams from integrated Internet of Things devices on their buildings and access 3D digital models of their buildings sourced from BIM files and digital representations.

Figure 21 Flowchart representing the D²EPC digital platform services

A deliverable of potential interest to IEBRA accessible on the D²EPC website, is listed below:

- D1.8: Aspects of Next generation EPC's definition v3: is a report that identifies technical challenges that currently exist to overcome them and set the grounds for the next generation dynamic EPCs.

3.7 X-tendo

[X-tendo](#) is a Horizon 2020 project that was active between September 2019 and August 2022 with partners in UK, Belgium, Poland, Austria, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Denmark, Estonia, Romania, and pilots in nine of these member states. X-tendo set itself to develop and test next-generation EPC features in 9 countries around Europe and assist the implementation of the features into the existing EPC schemes. X-tendo's toolbox introduced ten features of energy performance certificates, informed by large end-user surveys, to provide public authorities with improved compliance, reliability, usability and convergence of next-generation energy performance assessment and certification.

The ten features that were introduced include: Smart Readiness, Comfort, Outdoor air pollution, Real energy consumption, District energy, EPC Database, Logbook, Enhanced recommendations, Financing schemes and One-stop-shops. Four cross cutting criteria (quality and reliability, user friendliness, economic feasibility and consistency with international standards) were used to

evaluate the performance of each of the 10 features developed. For each of the features tested, specific outputs such as reports, calculation spreadsheets were prepared and can be retrieved from the project's webpage. A document of potential interest to IEBRA, accessible on the project website is the following:

- [EPC Assessing their status and potential](#): is a document that provides an overall description of the use and integration of EPCs in EU member states.
- Exploring innovative indicators for the next- generation energy performance certificate features: a preliminary scope of new proposed indicators for the EPC.
- [Specifications of energy performance certificates data handling: understanding the value of data](#): This report summarised to the main objective of each the feature, the methods and technical specifications, good practice example and interaction with other features regarding features of EPC databases, building logbooks, tailored recommendations, financing options and one-stop shops.

3.8 Smart Living EPC

[Smart Living EPC](#) is a Horizon Europe project that was active between July 2022 and June 2025, focusing on pilots located in Spain, Estonia, Cyprus and Greece, and partner countries that include: Spain, Estonia, Cyprus, Greece, Austria, Ireland, Belgium, Italy, Romania, Netherlands. The Smart Living EPC project aimed to deliver a certificate issued with the use of digitized tools and which retrieves the necessary assessment information for the building shell and building systems from BIM literacy, including enriched energy and sustainability related information for the as designed and the actual performance of the building. The new certification scheme developed also expanded over the existing scope, covering aspects related to water consumption, as well as noise pollution and acoustics.

The architecture of the SLEPC web platform developed by the project is presented below.

Figure 22 SLEPC platform architecture

The SLEPC platform allows the visualization of a range of results, notably the building asset results, such as energy data, comfort (acoustic, thermal, visual),

indoor air quality and can calculate the total asset rating classification of the building. Additionally, the users can perform a building SRI assessment, as well as obtain the operation-based energy, cost and economic indicators and total operational rating building classification. A few of the available platform visualizations are shown on the figures below:

Figure 23 Images of the SLEPC platform result pages

Of potential overlap with the IEBRA project, are the following deliverable accessible from the project webpage:

- D1.1 From EPC schemes gaps and opportunities to SmartLivingEPC requirements, recommendations and market needs: Is a document that elaborates on the EPC rating schemes and associated challenges and opportunities, prepared at the start of the project.

- D5.1 SmartLivingEPC Digital Platform: Components development, Integration and Acceptance Tests: is a report that presents the functional description and insights of the online SLEPC platform.

The project is interesting specially for the new EPC concept, the dual rating based on design performance and measured energy used and the integration of 3D digital data.

3.9 Chronicle

[Chronicle](#) is a Horizon Europe project that was active between July 2022 and December 2025, focusing on pilots located in Spain, Ireland, Denmark, Greece and Switzerland. The project aimed to support the sustainable design of new and existing construction projects by focusing on efficient renovation procedures and investment decision-making processes. To do so, it elaborated a holistic framework for assessing the life-cycle performance for different building variants. A set of 9 digital tools were developed to support digitalisation of the building sector, and focus on improving building performance, monitoring energy consumption and developing more cost-effective, long-term maintenance and renovation plans.

The tools developed are listed below:

- Common Data Environment (CDE) is a cloud-based data management framework that facilitates data sharing across the CHRONICLE's various components, adhering to standardised semantic interoperability principles.
- Digital Twin framework: aims to accurately model and simulate the building's processes based on real life data, monitoring buildings operations and environmental conditions, collected through an IoT network installed on site.
- ChroViewREN (Renovation Planner): designed to help building professionals and owners plan renovations of buildings.
- ChroViewREN (Investment Appraiser): forecasts value and liabilities related to buildings' performance as well as energy saving investments.
- ChroViewDBL (Dynamic Building Logbook): is an information repository for all relevant building data.
- ChroViewFM (3D Visualization & Monitoring Platform for Facility Managers): enables the three-dimensional visualisation of the building and the monitoring of near-real time data.

- ChroViewPlus (App for Professionals): to assist Owners/Investors and Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) with expert recommendations and in-depth insights to effectively reduce energy consumption
- ChroViewOcc (App for Residents): mobile app that enables building residents to understand and improve their energy consumption.

The document accessible on Chronicle's website that describes the Building logbook could be of relevance to IEBRA:

- D4.1 CHRONICLE Dynamic Building Logbook: Is a document that provides a summary of the elements that establish the origin of DBL, associated requirements and its architecture.
- D4.2 Enhanced Building Performance Assessment tool and user-friendly Uis (pending EU approval): offers a detailed description of the 3 user interfaces defined and their needs, functionality overview of the platform, technical description and examples for the pilot of Greece, and for the main stakeholders :building designers, owners and ESCOs.
-

3.10 IBRoad2EPC

[IBRoad2EPC](#) is a Horizon 2020 project that was operative between September 2021 and August 2024, and was tested in Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain. Its main objective was to explore energy performance assessment schemes and certification practices with the aim of promoting and showcasing the integration of Building Renovation Passport elements into EPC schemes. iBRoad2EPC builds on the results of the iBRoad project (2017-2020) which developed a model for the Building Renovation Passport (BRP).

The IBRoad2EPC created a platform for energy auditors to issue renovation passports, but it can also be used by software developers for building an interface between these and their own databases or tools, and public authorities wishing to take iBRoad2EPC up to integrate it into their national policy framework. Access to the iBRoad2EPC platform is available upon request. The flow diagram below represents the platform architecture.

Figure 24 Architecture of the iBRoad2EPC of API based client-server system

A typical software overview page upon accessing the platform is presented below:

Figure 25 Building Renovation Timeline from 2022 to 2050 (iBroad2EPC)

Legend:

1. Header with the contact details of the issuer.
2. Welcome text and brief introduction to iBroad2EPC.
3. Each house symbol represents one renovation step, from the current building state to the target one.
4. Icons represent the technical building equipment, such as heating, cooling, domestic hot water and ventilation systems.
5. Building components or equipment that shall be renovated are highlighted in the respective renovation step.
6. The renovation measures that are foreseen are briefly described. One renovation step can comprise several renovation measures.
7. The year when the renovation step should be implemented is a static preset based on each country's intermediate targets.
8. All completed measures remain green, so that the house becomes greener and greener over time.

9. The target efficiency is shown in the last step.
10. Footer with disclaimer and further information.
11. Tabs to facilitate navigating through the document.

Once the auditor has entered all the building information and the foreseen renovation, the according renovation steps are produced, as shown in the pictures below.

English ▼
Log out ▼

RENOVATION STEPS

● Project details
○ Renovation measures
○ IEQ
○ SRI

Next step

Current state ✎

Energy Energy sources : Final energy demand : kWh/m²a GHG emissions : kg/m² Energy costs : 0 €/a

▼

Renovations to be done by: ASAP ✎

Costs Maintenance costs : € 0 Energy related costs : € 0 Funding : € 0

Energy Energy sources : 1. Gas Final energy demand : 0 kWh/m²a GHG emissions : 0 kg/m² Energy costs : 0.0 €/a

▼ 1. Floor - Insulation on the basement ceiling ✎

Insulation of the cellar ceiling from below. Depending on the surface of the ceiling, the piping underneath and the overall usage of the basement you should consider different insulation materials. Also check for height restrictions.

▲ 2. Heating - External air-water heat pump ✎

Installation of an air-water heat pump. This uses outside air as a heat source. The outdoor unit of the heat pump is installed outdoors. Attention must be paid to the sound diffusion in the neighbourhood. The pipes are led into the heating room through openings in the outer wall. They must be well insulated. Heat pumps can also be used for cooling. The flow temperature in the heating circuit must be lowered as much as possible so that the heat pump can run efficiently.

⚙️ Preparations for later renovations steps ▼

+ Add measure

▼

Renovations to be done by: 2025 ✎

▼

Renovations to be done by: 2040 ✎

Costs Maintenance costs : € 0 Energy related costs : € 0 Funding : € 0

Energy Energy sources : 1. Electricity Final energy demand : 0 kWh/m²a GHG emissions : 0 kg/m² Energy costs : 0.0 €/a

+ Add measure

Regulation targets

All buildings should be nZEB/ZEB by 2050. ✎

+ Add step

Create the overview document

Figure 26 Renovation steps defined in the iBRoad2EPC tool as input for a Building Renovation Passport

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 iBRoad2EPC
Projects
Test User | Log out

PROJECT: TEST

[Download enhanced EPC pdf](#)
[iBRoad2EPC document](#)
[Edit](#)

RENOVATION PLAN

Current state

Renovations to be done by: ASAP

1. Roof - Roof insulation

Insulation of the roof surface together with the renewal of the roof tiles. The new insulation will be installed on top of the slab/framework.

 Preparations for later renovations steps

Renovations to be done by: 2025

1. Window - Replacement of the windows

Replacement of all windows that are older than 10 years. If you replace the windows without insulating or having insulated your external walls, ask your energy adviser for possible thermal bridges and related risk of mould. Also ask if the minimum ventilation is guaranteed any longer. The new windows must be connected to the masonry in a long-lasting airtight manner. Foaming with installation foam is usually not sufficient.

 Preparations for later renovations steps

2. External wall - External insulation (ETICS System)

Insulation of the entire external wall on the outside with an "External Thermal Insulation Composite Systems" (ETICS). The components of ETICS, such as cement, insulation boards, armoured and plaster, are adjusted to each other and together form a certified system. Polystyrene foam, mineral fibre or renewable insulation materials are usually used as insulation.

 Preparations for later renovations steps

3. Renewable energy sources - PV system

Installation of a PV system on the roof. If possible, the entire suitable roof area should be utilised. The electricity generated is primarily used in the building via an inverter and alternatively fed into the public grid via an additional electricity meter. Get advice on the different types of PV modules.

Figure 27 Building Renovation Plan – Phased Renovation Measures (iBRoad2EPC)

Figure 28 iBRoad2EPC software output - Overview includes all renovation steps and the measures contained in each step, regulation targets and project details

The project website disposes of a range of produced documents that could provide interesting insight, notably:

- Accelerating deep renovation in the EU with renovation passports: This document provides an implementation guide for EU renovation policies.
- EPCs – Energy Performance Certificates & LTRs – Long-Term Renovation Strategies: is a report that focuses on the relevance and link of Long-Term Renovation Strategies (LTRS) to recommendations being provided in Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) as well as Building Renovation Passports (BRPs).
- Training toolkit: is a document that describes how the software functions.

3.11 EPBD WISE

[EPBD.wise](#) is an **ongoing** Life project that has been operative since October 2023 and is planned to end in June 2026. The geographies it focuses on are Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Ukraine. It focuses on providing direct support to local authorities in six European countries (listed above) to design and implement the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).

3.12 SMARTER EPC

[Smarter EPC](#) is an **ongoing** Life project that has been operative since October 2023 and is planned to end in June 2026. It does not have specific focus geographies but focuses on Europe more broadly. Smarter EPC aims to create an open platform offering seven tools for issuing EPCs and SRIs, connecting stakeholders with tools developed by NextGenEPC research programmes and the 2021-CET-SMARTREADY Life call. The platform will provide access to EPC tools from D²EPC, SmartLivingEPC, UCERT, and SRI tools from Smart², easySRI, SRI2Market, and UCERT, enabling smart data input and tool selection for EPC and SRI issuance.

So far, it has produced an atlas that provides a platform linking a wide range of EPC and SRI calculation tools across all EU member states. Additionally, a number of links are provided to other tools developed by other Horizon, or Life projects. It has also gathered a range of resources and outputs (EPC and SRI) in a repository saved on the project website.

3.13 GreenRenoV8

[GreenRenoV8](#) is an **ongoing** 3 year long Life project that is composed of 9 partners located in Slovenia, Italy, Austria, Belgium, Spain and Greece. Its main objective is to examine sustainable building renovation, encompassing energy efficiency, seismic considerations, and the complete life cycle of carbon emissions.

3.14 EU Project summary tables

Table 1 General information about EU Projects focusing on EPC and BRP:

Name	EU Funding	Website Link	Themes					Applicability	Start & end date
			EPC	enhanced EPC	Building passports	financial aspects	LCA		
EUB SuperHub	Horizon	https://eubsuperhub.eu/	x		x	x	x	Partners Germany, Italy, France, and Austria. Applicability to all member states	06/2021 - 12/2024
CrossCert	Horizon	https://www.crosscert.eu/	x	x	x			Partners: in 10 European countries (Austria, Spain, Greece, Croatia, Poland, Bulgaria, Malta, Denmark, Slovenia, UK)	09/2021- 11/2024
tunES	Life	https://empirica.com/tunes/	x	x	x			Member states (partners): Austria (AEA), Croatia (EHIP), Greece (CRES), Hungary (EMI), Italy (ENEA), Poland (KAPE) and Slovenia (JSI) Guidance provided for other member states.	09/2023 - 09/2025
TIMEPAC	Horizon	https://timepac.eu/	x	x	x	x	x	Scenarios across six European countries: Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, Slovenia and Spain	07/2021 - 10/2024
EPC RECAST	Horizon2020	https://epc-recast.eu/		x		x		Pilots: Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Luxembourg, Slovakia	09/2020 - 06/2024
D²EPC	Horizon2020	https://www.d2epc.eu/en	x	x	x	x	x	Pilots: six buildings in 3 countries: Greece, Germany, and Cyprus.	09/2020 - 08/2023
X-tendo	Horizon2020	https://x-tendo.eu/	x	x	x	x		Partners in: UK, Belgium, Poland, Austria, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Denmark, Estonia, Romania. Projects: Tested with twenty-nine test projects in nine different member states to demonstrate the potential of each feature.	09/2019 - 08/2022
Smart Living EPC	Horizon Europe	SmartLivingEPC Home	x	x	x	x	x	Pilots: Spain, Estonia, Cyprus, Greece Partner Countries: Spain, Estonia, Cyprus, Greece, Austria, Ireland, Belgium, Italy, Romania, Netherlands.	07/2022 - 07/2025
Chronicle	Horizon	https://www.chronicle-	x	x	x	x	x	Pilots: (Spain, Ireland, Denmark, Greece and Switzerland)	07/2022 -

Name	EU Funding	Website Link	Themes					Applicability	Start & end date
			EPC	enhanced EPC	Building passports	financial aspects	LCA		
	Europe	project.eu/							12/ 2025
iBRoad2EPC	Horizon 2020	https://ibroad2epc.eu/	x	x	x			Tested in: Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain	09/2021 - 08/2024
EPBD.wise	Life	https://www.bpie.eu/epbdwise/	x	x	x	x	x	Countries: Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Ukraine Replicable model across Europe	10/2023 - 06/2026 ONGOING
Smarter EPC	Life	SmarterEPC - Life Projects R2M Solution	x	x	x	x	x	All member states	10/2023 - 06/2026 ONGOING

Table 2 Summary of REU project's relevant information to IEBRA

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
EUB SuperHub	Develop a scalable methodology and digital building logbook (DBL) giving an "EUB e-passport" rating across energy, sustainability and smartness, holding EPCs and other certificates over the building life-cycle.	The deliverables that were deemed relevant include: https://eubsuperhub.eu/activities D1.3 - Next generation certification: stakeholder needs and expectations D2.1 - Use case scenarios and definitions D2.2 - Definition of common transnational indicators and assessment metrics for the E-Passport	European Skills Registry - https://skillsregistry.eu/ Recognition and comparability of qualifications and skills in the construction sector, that evaluates the <u>competence, skills, and knowledge of professionals</u> in sustainable building within the construction sector, to provide a <u>Skills passport</u> (standardized tool to describe completed studies and qualifications in the field of sustainable energy). And provides <u>Courses</u> : comprehensive collection of	The EUB superhub Platform : https://app.eubsuperhub.eu/ E-cockpit : View essential information about existing building stock, including EPCs, Smart Readiness (SRI), and more. Planning and Verification Tool Claim your buildings, upload related information, choose what data to share publicly and perform building analysis concerning CO2 emission energy ratings, smartness, and more. Virtual Marketplace : Get in contact with building users,	

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
			national qualification courses, training materials, and curriculum related to sustainable energy skills.	auditors, solution, funding providers as well as other market actors and service providers. E-training: Get access to lessons on platform usage and advanced training materials for experts in the energy, sustainability, and smart solutions fields	
CrossCert	Develop a product testing methodology for the new energy performance certificate for buildings. To do so, it performs cross-testing between the current energy certificates and the new approaches/ concepts/ initiatives (140 buildings in 10countries). Prepares policy recommendations that include improvements in accuracy, usability and harmonisation.	Deliverables of interest: https://www.crosscert.eu/our-solutions/deliverables * crossCert_D3.4_Cross country comparison recommended improvements in different EPCs https://www.crosscert.eu/our-solutions/results * CrossCert_Final resultsThe crossCert partners are making available an open database of building data for selected buildings in the EU and UK countries participating in crossCert.Project database - the building data is housed in Zenodo or can be accessed from crossCert Knowledge Exchange Centre (KxC) : https://www.crosscert.eu/our-solutions/open-database-for-epc-testing To infographics webpage: https://www.crosscert.eu/our-solutions/infographics-1	The project was structured around two key tests: C-building testing (comparing methodologies across similar climates) and L-building testing (local assessments focusing on performance gaps). The testing aimed to assess the feasibility of harmonising EPC processes across Europe by highlighting differences in calculation methods, data use, and the role of default values.		* The People-centred View on the Energy Performance Certificates . The EPC system is a functional network of stakeholders and institutions that enable, co-create and otherwise support the existence and functioning of the national EPC scheme* Design Thinking for Impactful & Meaningful Design of EPC Products & Services . People-centred iterative problem-solving approach that emphasizes empathy, collaboration, and experimentation. It's essential to maintain a people-centred mindset, involving stakeholders at every stage* Addressing the Assessors . The EPC Assessor's Journey maps the key steps by which they progress in their career and contribute towards keeping the EPC system in function.* Making EPCs attractive : promotion and marketing strategies should be considered
tunES	To optimise Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) regulation and	Deliverables available on zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/	Structuring work into five building blocks to better collect, share, implement and		A combination of online surveys and expert interviews with stakeholders, including academics, industry professionals, and

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
	integrate it with the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) roll-out in 7 national Energy Agencies and develop guidance for other Member States. The core outcome are seven national policy measure packages . On the EU-level, a <u>comprehensive guidance strategy</u> allows other stakeholders to access use cases all tools for effective replication.	<p>tunes/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p> <p>* tunES D2.1 Report on Survey and Interview Results</p> <p>Document detailing information sources: https://empirica.com/tunes/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2025/05/2502-tunES-EPC-SRI-Practice-Collection.pdf</p> <p>Description of other EPC related projects https://empekom-my.sharepoint.com/:w/g/personal/georg_vogt_empirica_com/E_XBR1sjCbg5IpaGjBwrhiAgBhz_Z2ZyYWs8p1p0kAKsLiw?rttime=BjL8L5A-3Eg</p>	replicate good practice: Understanding EPC, Upgrading EPC, Databases & Tools, SRI Development & Deployment, and Integration of Instruments to maximise harmonisation, coherence and synergies. Available tools: https://empirica.com/tunes/guidance/		government authorities
TIMEPAC	Enhance the full EPC process (generation, storage, analysis, exploitation) to deliver holistic, flexible, through-life-updated, interoperable digital EPCs , treating buildings as dynamic, occupant-centric assets.	<p>Timepac Academy - hosts webinars and in-class courses based on the knowledge acquired over the course of the project devising future scenarios for enhanced EPCs. https://timepac.eu/academy/</p> <p>A number of factsheets & guidelines are made available: https://timepac.eu/resources/</p>	Use of BIM models to generate and improve EPCs. Integrating BIM and EPC fully is a long-term goal that faces several challenges, with one of the main hurdles being the interoperability between different modelling and simulation tools. To progress toward this goal, we have formulated a set of guidelines for calculating EPCs from BIM models using existing technologies. These guidelines have the potential to foster the development of standardized	Thirty BIM models, five per country, were generated and assessed using the guidelines. The models represented different types of buildings, such as residential, office, educational, and commercial, with different scales, geometric and spatial complexity (Figure 3), and source materials (e.g. drawings, models and other documents). They were created using two BIM software tools (Revit and Cype) and imported into three EPC software tools (Edilclima EC700, Cypetherm HE Plus, and ETU)	

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
			and reliable protocols for utilizing BIM in energy performance certification across the European Union.		
EPC RECAST	Develop a structured process and toolbox for new-generation EPCs that better assess building energy performance, retrofit needs, and financing opportunities. The EPC RECAST project software tools assist assessors to create the next generation of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs).	<p>Deliverables of interest can be accessed here: https://epc-recast.eu/deliverables/ * EPC RECAST certification tool/platform * EPC RECAST Certificate and Renovation Roadmap Consolidated version</p> <p>The KROQI platform, a collaborative web platform designed for the construction sector enables smooth data exchange and collaboration, and an interface allows assessors to manage EPC RECASTXML files easily, run simulation and generate RoadMap.</p>	<p>Data collection harmonization: define a European and harmonized protocol in the form of a "Data Model" for the description of the building. Develop and integrate enrichment and verification methods into this protocol and link this protocol to existing technical components, all to facilitate and make the data collected more reliable</p>	<p>Online Assessor Interface: Interface accessible via the KROQI platform, facilitates energy performance calculations and simulation setups. It allows direct import of on-site data via BIMEO technology. Simulation results, detailing energy consumption by source and end-use, are generated and stored in CSV format for further analysis.</p> <p>Renovation Roadmap interface is also accessible via the KROQI online platform. Two modes of use are available, depending on the context of the building being studied: single-family house and collective building.</p>	<p>Policy Advisory Board (PAB) involved at key milestones of the project in order to gather constructive feedback and guidance for the technical activities conducted in EPC RECAST.</p> <p>The board is formed by experts from key decision-making public and local authorities involved in the definition and implementation of EPC national and/or regional legislation in particular from each pilot country.</p>
D ² EPC	<p>Create dynamic, digital EPCs based on near-real-time data, with indicators for energy, smart readiness, wellbeing, comfort, finance and sustainability, using BIM/GIS and cloud architecture.</p> <p>D²EPC relies upon the</p>	<p>The deliverables that were deemed relevant include: https://www.d2epc.eu/en/project-results#workpackage-1 *D1.8: Aspects of Next generation EPC's definition v3</p>	<p>Tool structure: Three different user roles have been determined defining eligible actions. The EPC Assessor is eligible to perform actions related to building performance assessment. The Building Tenant role is limited to viewing the calculated results. The Authority role, which is reserved for accessing</p>	<p>The D²EPC WebGIS tool visualises generated EPCs in a GIS environment, empowering users to perform various types of spatial and attribute queries.</p> <p>The D²EPC backend, includes: Flask20, SQLAlchemy21, Marshmallow22, Pandas23.</p> <p>For IT interest: The D²EPC</p>	

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
	<p>smart-readiness level of the buildings and the corresponding data collection infrastructure and management systems. It builds upon actual data and the 'digital twin' concept to calculate energy, environmental, financial and human comfort indicators and through them the EPC classification of the building in question. The project delivers a user-friendly platform that enhances transparency, encourages behavioural change, and supports informed investment decisions.</p>		<p>parties with a wider overview of the building assessment results, are allowed to execute extended functionalities of the Energy Performance Benchmarking tool.</p> <p>Since all the D²EPC tools have been developed as Python software packages, they have been integrated into the backend. On the other side, the D²EPC Repository serves as the common storage location for user input data (personal information, BIM files, calculation parameters etc.), configuration parameters, device measurements and service outputs. It is based on PostgreSQL²⁴, which is an open-source DBMS+N9</p>	<p>backend, includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flask²⁰, which has been used to design the various API routes that correspond to platform functionalities. • SQLAlchemy²¹, an open-source SQL toolkit and object-relational mapper (ORM), which has been used to link the backend with the D²EPC Repository. • Marshmallow²², an ORM/ODM/framework-agnostic library for converting complex datatypes, such as objects, to and from native Python datatypes. • Pandas²³, a data analysis and manipulation tool, which has been used for data structuring and post-processing. 	
X-tendo	<p>X-tendo and its toolbox introduce ten features of the next generation of energy performance certificates, informed by large end-user surveys, to provide public authorities with improved compliance, reliability, usability and convergence of next-generation energy performance assessment and certification.</p>	<p>Deliverable: * EPC Assessing their status and potential</p>	<p>Indicators for which tools and reports were prepared:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Smart readiness 2. Comfort (excel tool) 3. Outdoor air pollution 4. Real Energy Consumption (excel tool). 5. District Energy 6. EPC Database 7. Building logbook 8. Enhanced recommendations 9. Financing options 10. One stop shops 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New technical features used within EPC assessment processes and enabling the inclusion of new indicators on EPCs 2. Innovative approaches to handle EPC data and maximise their value for building owners and other end-users 	<p>To develop a framework of 10 "next-generation EPC features" aiming to improve compliance, usability and reliability of EPCs - a full insight into what end-users want and need was conducted including: (potential future) building owners and occupants. Final sample size was 2,563, with varying sample sizes of 501 to 519 per country.</p>

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
Smart Living EPC	<p>SmartLivingEPC project aims to deliver a certificate which will be issued with the use of digitized tools and retrieve the necessary assessment information for the building shell and building systems from BIM literacy, including enriched energy and sustainability related information for the as designed and the actual performance of the building. The new certification scheme will also expand its scope, covering aspects related to water consumption, as well as noise pollution and acoustics.</p>	<p>Deliverables of interest can be accessed here: https://www.smartlivingepc.eu/en/project-results * D1.1 From EPC schemes gaps and opportunities to SmartLivingEPC requirements, recommendations and market needs</p>	<p>Asset Rating Calculation Methodology - The SLEPC assessment system utilizes a scoring mechanism to convert basic energy consumption into a comprehensible and comparative energy performance classification. Operational Rating Calculation Methodology - The final rating calculation for the Operational assessment has selected 15 indicators (of an initial 70). These chosen metrics cover a broad range of aspects coming from the initial assessment: energy consumption, human wellbeing, and Life Cycle Cost (LCC), included in list below and taken from D3.3 and outlines aforementioned indicators.</p>	<p>SmartLivingEPC (SLEPC) Web Platform - integrates <u>Added Value AI tools</u>. As well as advanced user interfaces and visual analytics created to facilitate information visualization for end-users. All SLEPC components—including the <u>Asset Rating engine</u> and <u>Operational Rating engine</u>, as well as the <u>SLEPC Digital Twin</u>, <u>Common Information Exchange Model</u> will be integrated into a unified operational framework. It acts as a central hub for collecting building data, performing assessments, and generating certificates that incorporate Smart Readiness Indicators (SRI), sustainability metrics, and actual operational performance</p>	
Chronicle	<p>Aims to deliver a holistic framework for assessing the life-cycle performance for different building variants. We support the sustainable design of new and existing construction projects by focusing on efficient renovation procedures and investment decision-making processes.</p>	<p>Deliverables: https://www.chronicle-project.eu/resources/ * D4.1 CHRONICLE Dynamic Building Logbook</p>	<p>9 tools developed</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Common Data Environment (CDE) 2 & 3. Digital Twin framework 4. ChroViewREN (Renovation Planner) 5. ChroViewREN (Investment Appraiser) 6. ChroViewDBL (Dynamic Building Logbook) 7. ChroViewFM (3D Visualization & Monitoring Platform for Facility Managers) 8. ChroViewPlus (App for 	<p>To achieve this, we will develop digital tools to measure and improve the building performance. The tools will help to monitor energy consumption and to develop more sustainable, cost-effective, long-term maintenance and renovation plans.</p>	

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
			Professionals) 9. ChroViewOcc (App for Residents)		
iBRoad2EPC	<p>Explore energy performance assessment schemes and certification practices with the aim of promoting and showcasing the integration of Building Renovation Passport elements into EPC schemes.</p> <p>iBRoad2EPC builds on the results of the iBRoad project (2017-2020) which developed a model for the Building Renovation Passport (BRP) iBRoad2EPC aims to bridge the Building Renovation Passport with the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC).</p>	<p>Deliverables of interest can be accessed here: https://ibroad2epc.eu/our-work/#</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Accelerating deep renovation in the EU with renovation passports * EPCs – Energy Performance Certificates & LTRs – Long-Term Renovation Strategies 	<p>Some of the developed software tool structure, content, approach or methodology could be of interest. The report linked below explains iBRoad2EPC software tools specifications and is accompanied by an excel spreadsheet containing the country specific templates and main content of the database. https://ibroad2epc.eu/portfolio-items/specification-for-the-ibroad2epc-software-tools/</p>	<p>For 6 tested countries, comprehensive guides supporting national implementation have been developed and made available.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Training toolkit — Training toolkit for energy experts January 2024 * iBRoad2EPC training material for construction professionals — Using iBRoad2EPC for staged renovation design and construction April 2023 * Webinar for construction professionals – part 1 * Webinar for construction professionals – part 2 * iBRoad2EPC Advisory package for public authorities June 2024 * Webinar for public authorities 	
EPBD.wise	<p>EPBD.wise provides direct support to local authorities in six European countries (Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Ukraine) to design and implement the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).</p>	<p>Resources available on publication tab, which includes a large array of documents https://www.bpie.eu/knowledge-hub/#publications</p>			
Smarter EPC	<p>Smarter EPC aims to create an open platform offering</p>	<p>Resources of interest: The atlas provides a platform</p>	<p>SmarterEPC is developing a digital interface allowing smart</p>	<p>The SmarterEPC project has reached a major milestone with</p>	

Name	Main Objective	Project information of potential relevance to IEBRA	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Co creation and stakeholder engagement methods used
	<p>seven tools for issuing EPCs and SRIs, connecting stakeholders with tools developed by NextGenEPC research programmes and the 2021-CET-SMARTREADY Life call. The platform will provide access to EPC tools from D2EPC, SmartLivingEPC, UCERT, and SRI tools from Smart², easySRI, SRI2Market, and UCERT, enabling smart data input and tool selection for EPC and SRI issuance</p>	<p>that links a wide range of EPC and SRI calculation tools across all EU member states. Links are provided to many tools developed by other Horizon, or Life projects. https://www.epc-sri-atlas.eu/</p> <p>Resources and outputs (EPC and SRI) are available in a repository saved at the report centre: https://lifeprojects.r2msolution.com/smarterepc-support-centre/</p>	<p>data collection for all input data required for the calculation of EPC and SRI. The SmarterEPC hub will connect this input data interface with existing tools calculating EPC and SRI scores and will present their results in an integrated way.</p>	<p>the presentation of its innovative joint certificate at CASE 2025, demonstrating how <u>Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Smart Readiness Indicators (SRI) can be potentially integrated</u> into a single, user-friendly document.</p> <p>EU Smart Readiness Indicator webpage https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator_en</p>	

3. SOFTWARE SOLUTIONS FOR EPC

3.1. Overview of EPC software landscape in Europe.

Despite that the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) provides a common EU-level framework intended to harmonize principles and requirements, the European software ecosystem for EPCs is characterized by enormous diversity, and shaped by national legislations, methodological approaches, and different degrees of digitalization adopted by member states.

These differences make software development extremely challenging regarding design, approval, and integration within national registers. For this reason, EPC software is typically developed either by national software developers, familiar with its own national regulations, or directly by the official agencies responsible for the certification system.

As a direct consequence of this fragmented landscape, 86 different EPC software tools have been documented within this deliverable, across the 27 EU Member States.

3.2. National regulations and methodological approach for EPC software.

The analysis of national EPC regulations and calculation methodologies has been crucial towards understanding how EPC software is developed around Europe. The two tables included in this section summarize regulations and calculation methodologies for each country and highlights the heterogeneity between the approaches of member states despite the EU EPBD common framework.

Currently there is no European repository that consolidates all national EPC legislation, calculation guidelines and methodological reference into a single, harmonized source. The absence of a centralized documentation repository for Europe significantly complicates the understanding and comparison of national systems, as well as the development of cross-country software tools.

Table 3 List of main regulations in EU countries.

Country	Technical document	Year	Link
Austria	OIB Guideline 6	2025	https://www.oib.or.at/richtlinien/oib-richtlinien-2025/oib-richtlinie-6/
Belgium	Flanders Het Energiebesluit van 19 november 2010	2010	https://www.vlaanderen.be/epc-pedia/epc-regelgeving
	Wallonia Décret du 28 novembre 2013 relatif à la performance énergétique des bâtiments	2013	https://wallex.wallonie.be/files/pdfs/20/19400_D%C3%A9cret_relatif_%C3%A0_la_performance_%C3%A9nerg%C3%A9tique_des_b%C3%A2timents_16-07-2024-31-12-2098.pdf

		Arrêté du Gouvernement wallon du 15 mai 2014 portant exécution du décret	2023	https://wallex.wallonie.be/files/pdfs/22/20131_Arr%c3%aat%c3%a9_du_Gouvernement_wallon_portant_ex%c3%a9cutio_n_du_d%c3%a9cret_du_28_novembre_2013_relatif_%c3%a0_la_performance_%c3%a9nerg%c3%a9tique_des_b%c3%a2iments_01-01-2026-.pdf
	Brussels	CoBraCE (Brussels Code for Air, CLimate and Energy Management)	2013	Le Code Bruxellois de l'Air, du Climat et de la maîtrise de l'Energie (CoBrACE) Professionnel - Bruxelles Environnement
	Bulgaria	Ordinance No. RD-02-20-3 of 9.11.2022 on the technical requirements for the energy performance of buildings	2022	https://www.mrrb.bg/bg/naredba-rd-02-20-3-ot-9-11-2022-g-za-tehnikeskite-iziskvaniya-kum-energijite-harakteristiki-na-sgradi/
	Croatia	Ordinance No.88/2017 on Energy Audits and Energy Certification of Buildings (Pravilnik o energetskom pregledu zgrade i energetskom certificiranju)	2017	https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/clanci/sluzbeni/2017_09_88_2093.html
	Cyprus	The Regulation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Law of 2006 (Law 142(I)/2006)	2010	https://www.cylaw.org/nomoi/indexes/2006_1_142.html
	Czech Republic	Decree 264/2020 on energy performance	2020	https://aplikace.mv.gov.cz/sbirka-zakonu/SearchResult.aspx?q=264/2020&typeLaw=zakon&what=Cislo_zakona_smlouvy
	Denmark	Building Regulations BR18 (Art 25-298 + appendix)	2018	https://www.bygningsreglementet.dk/tekniske-bestemmelser/11/krav/
	Estonia	Minimum requirements in Energy Performance in Buildings (Hoone energiatõhususe miinimumnõuded)	2025	https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/119022025004
		Requirements for issuing energy performance certificates and energy performance certificates (Nõuded energiamärgise andmisele ja energiamärgisele)	2025	https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/108052025002
	Finland	Act on the Energy Performance Certificate of a Building (Laki rakennuksen energiatodistuksesta)	2013	https://www.finlex.fi/fi/lainsaadanto/2013/50
	France	RE2020-Décret n° 2021-1004	2021	https://rt-re-batiment.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/re2020-r320.html
	Germany	Gebäudeenergiegesetz (GEG)	2020	https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/geg/index.html
	Greece	KENAK regulation	2017	https://tekerk.gr/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/fek-2367b_12-07-2017_neos-kenak.pdf
			2018	https://www.elinvae.gr/sites/default/files/2019-07/181b_2018.1517828555673.pdf
	Hungary	9/2023 (V.25) ÉKM rendelet	2023	https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2023-9-20-8X
		176/2008. (VI. 30.) Korm. rendelet	2008	https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2008-176-20-22
	Ireland	S.I. No. 183/2019 - European Union (Energy Performance Of Buildings) Regulations 2019	2019	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2019/si/183/made/en/print?
	Italy	DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 19 agosto 2005, n. 192	2005	https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2005:192
		Decreto interministeriale 26 giugno 2015 - Adeguamento linee guida nazionali per la certificazione energetica degli edifici	2019	https://www.mimit.gov.it/index.php/it/normativa/decreti-interministeriali/decreto-interministeriale-26-giugno-2015-adeguamento-linee-guida-nazionali-per-la-certificazione-energetica-degli-edifici

Latvia	Ēku energoefektivitātes likums (Law on energy performance of buildings, Nr.222)	2020	https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/253635
	Ēku energoefektivitātes aprēķina metodes un ēku energosertifikācijas noteikumi / Latvian Building Energy Performance Calculation Methodology (Noteikumi Nr. 631)	2021	https://likumi.lv/ta/id/322436-eku-energoefektivitates-aprekina-metodes-un-eku-energosertifikacijas-noteikumi
Lithuania	Building Technical Regulation STR 2.01.02:2016 "Design and Certification of Energy Performance of Buildings"	2016	https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/15767120a80711e68987e8320e9a5185/asr
Luxembourg	Règlement grand-ducal EPC	2021	https://legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/rqd/2021/06/09/a439/fo
Malta	Technical Document F - BCA	2024	https://bca.gov.mt/guidance-documents/
Netherlands	NTA 8800:2025	2021	https://www.nen.nl/en/nta-8800-2025-nl-344705
Poland	Templates for energy performance certificates are provided in Regulation of the Minister of Development and Technology (Dz.U. 2023 poz. 697)	2024	https://sip.lex.pl/akty-prawne/dzu-dziennik-ustaw/metodologia-wyznaczenia-charakterystyki-energetycznej-budynku-lub-18176491
Portugal	Decreto-Lei n.º 118/2013, de 20 de agosto- Sistema de Certificação Energética dos Edifícios, o Regulamento de Desempenho Energético dos Edifícios de Habitação e o Regulamento de Desempenho Energético dos Edifícios de Comércio e Serviços,	2013	https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/pt/areas-setoriais/energia/eficiencia-energetica/edificios/
Romania	Metodologia de calcul al performanței energetice a clădirilor, indicativ Mc 001-2022	2023	https://www.mdpa.ro/subarticles/7/anunt03032023
Slovakia	Vyhláška č. 35/2020 Z. z.	2020	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5ef4e0ad-a3ff-4bdb-88da-2d47a5405983/language-sk
Slovenia	PURES regulation	2022	https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina/2022-01-1635
Spain	RD 390/2021(Calculation method)	2021	https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2021-9176
	Codigo Técnico de la Edificación - CTE- HE - Ahorro de Energía	2006	https://www.codigotecnico.org/DocumentosCTE/AhorroEnergia.html
Sweden	Boverkets föreskrifter och allmänna råd (BFS 2018:11) om energideklaration för byggnader (Also known as BED).	2018	https://rinfo.boverket.se/BFS2007-4/pdf/BFS2018-11.pdf

3.2.1. Methodologies

Also, the methodological landscape for EPC across Europe is highly varied: most countries rely on quasi-steady monthly or annual methods, some complement them with dynamic hourly simulations, and a smaller group employ mandatory national simulation engines embedded in their official tools. Although

many countries base their EPC methodologies on common EN/ISO standards, each member state adapts these standards differently, defining its own national parameters, climatic files, reference values, default efficiencies, and primary energy factors. This diversity has direct implications for EPC software, influencing development and technical capabilities and creating significant interoperability challenges when adapting the software and comparing results across countries.

Furthermore, some countries prescribe or require national simulation engines, which act as authoritative source of calculation. Mandatory engines improve consistency and reduce methodological variability between tools but not necessarily simplify the development of tools and put a limit in the developer's ability to innovate beyond the current EPCs.

The EPC methodologies identified in this section fall in two categories: quasi-steady (monthly-annual) methods and dynamic simulation (hourly) methods.

1. Quasi-steady (monthly or annual) method:

Most EU countries apply this method as the main approach for EPC calculations. These methods are closely aligned with long-standing EN and ISO standards, especially: EN ISO 52016-1 (energy needs for heating and cooling), EN ISO 52010 (external climatic data), EN 15316 series (HVAC systems), EN ISO 13790 (legacy methods still referenced in many national systems).

Quasi-steady methods typically model monthly (or annual) energy balances for heating, cooling, hot water, ventilation and auxiliary systems. Their main advantages include, lower development and computational effort, simplified implementations within regulatory frameworks, compatibility with simplified audits and residential building assessments, and lower entry data requirements. However, these methods can be limited when evaluating buildings performance specially with complex HVAC systems, advanced controls, or variable occupant behaviour, as they do not capture hourly interactions between climate, occupancy and system response.

2. Dynamic (hourly) method:

A smaller but growing number of countries incorporate or require dynamic hourly methods, which offer more accurate modelling of real building performance. Dynamic simulation is presented as an alternative method with more precise thermal modelling under real climatic conditions, better representations of advanced HVAC systems, renewables and building automation and capability of calculating indicators beyond energy use (indoor comfort or overheating risk) facilitating the understanding of the building behaviour at hourly scale and making easier to apply more efficient improvement measures depending on this behaviour.

Table 4 Calculation methodology by country.

Country	Calculation method	Implementation manual	Simulation engine
Austria	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://www.oib.or.at/wp-content/uploads/oib-ri_6_september_2025.pdf	No
Belgium	Flanders	https://www.vlaanderen.be/epb-pedia/rekenmethode	No
	Wallonia	guide-peb-2021-2023.pdf	No
	Brussels	https://environnement.brussels/pro/documentation-et-outils/sites-web-et-outils-interactifs/outils-pour-les-conseillers-peb-et-les-architectes	No
Bulgaria	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual)	https://www.mrrb.bg/static/media/ups/articles/attachments/%D0%A0%D0%94-02-20-3_%D0%9D%D0%B0%D1%80%20%D0%B7%D0%B0%20%D0%95%D0%A5%20%D0%BD%D0%B0%20%D1%81%D0%B3%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B4%D0%B8-%D0%9A%D0%BE%D0%BD%D1%81%D0%BE%D0%BB%D0%B8%D0%B4%D0%B8%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B0%20%D1%81%20%D0%B8%D0%B7%D0%BC%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5%20%D0%BE%D1%82%201.03.2024424b7e2631a7b8633c46e64c6abb93f3.pdf	No
Croatia	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/clanci/sluzbeni/2017_09_8_8_2093.html	No
Cyprus	Quasi-steady (Monthly-SBEM)	https://bfu.meci.gov.cy/en/building-energy-performance-calculation-methodology/	SBEM
Czech Republic	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual) Dynamic	https://aplikace.mv.gov.cz/sbirka-zakonu/SearchResult.aspx?q=264/2020&typeLaw=zakon&what=Cislo_zakona_smlouv	No
Denmark	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual) Dynamic	https://www.bygningsreglementet.dk/tekniske-bestemmelser/11/krav/	BE18
Estonia	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic	https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/119022025002	No
Finland	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic	https://liitvntakatalogi.suomi.fi/en_GB/dataset/energiatodistusrekisteri-ara-svc	No
France	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic (modules)	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/orf/id/JORFTEXT000043353381	RE2020
Germany	Quasi-steady (Multi-period)	https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-08/LEITFADEN_ENERGETISCHE_GEBAEUDEBILANZIERUNG_NACH_DIN_V_18599.pdf	No
Greece	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://ypen.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/legacy/Files/Energeia/Eksinomisi/Kiriia/Egkrish_Efarmogh_OTEE4003_2017.pdf	No
Hungary	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual)	https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2023-9-20-8X	No
Ireland	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://www.seai.ie/ber	DEAP
			SBE

			M-ie
Italy	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual)	https://www.mimit.gov.it/index.php/it/normativa/decreti-interministeriali/decreto-interministeriale-26-giugno-2015-adequamento-linee-guida-nazionali-per-la-certificazione-energetica-degli-edifici	Cene d + Moto re 2.0
Latvia	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://likumi.lv/ta/id/322436-eku-energoefektivitates-aprekina-metodes-un-eku-energocertifikacijas-noteikumi	No
Lithuania	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/15767120a80711e68987e8320e9a5185/asr	No
Luxembourg	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic	https://meco.gouvernement.lu/fr/domaines-activites/energie/efficacite-energetique/informations-techniques.html	LuxE eB LES OSAI
Malta	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://bca.gov.mt/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/EPB-Calculation-Methodology-for-Residential-Buildings-Manual-EPRDM.pdf	No
		https://bca.gov.mt/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/EPB-Calculation-Methodology-for-Non-Residential-Buildings-User-Guide-SBEMmt.pdf	No
Netherlands	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic (modules)	https://installq.nl/files/brl/bijlagen/brl-9501-bindend-14102025-nog-niet-aangewezen.pdf	No
Poland	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual)	https://sjp.lex.pl/akty-prawne/dzu-dziennik-ustaw/metodologia-wyznaczenia-charakterystyki-energetycznej-budynku-lub-18176491	No
Portugal	Dynamic	https://www.dqeg.gov.pt/pt/areas-setoriais/energia/eficiencia-energetica/edificios/	PT- nZE B engi ne
Romania	Quasi-steady (Monthly/Annual)	mdlpa.ro/subarticles/7/anunt03032023	No
Slovakia	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://www.slov-lex.sk/static/pdf/2012/364/ZZ_2012_364.pdf	No
Slovenia	Quasi-steady (Monthly)	https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MNVP/Dokumenti/Graditev/TSG-1-004_2022_ure.pdf	No
Spain	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic	https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2021-9176	No
Sweden	Quasi-steady (Monthly) Dynamic	https://www.boverket.se/sv/energidklaration/	No

3.2.2. Type of results: formats

The analysis of EPC output formats across Europe reveals significant variation in the degree of digitalisation and interoperability of EPC data. While all national systems generate a PDF as the human-readable certificate, the availability of structured, machine-readable formats—and the extent to which these are publicly accessible—differs considerably among Member States.

A first group of countries provides XML, CSV or JSON outputs as part of their EPC systems, often accompanied by an official data schema or documentation. These machine-readable formats enable more advanced forms of data

processing, facilitate integration with digital building logbooks and renovation tools, and support automated quality checks. In some cases, EPC platforms also expose APIs, enabling programmatic access to the EPC database for validation, reporting or third-party service development.

A second group uses structured formats internally, for example to feed national EPC registries or perform compliance verification, but these data models are not publicly available. In these systems, developers and other stakeholders must rely primarily on the PDF output, limiting interoperability and restricting reuse of EPC data beyond the certification process itself.

Finally, a third group relies almost exclusively on PDF-only outputs, without any machine-readable formats or published schemas. This approach preserves basic certificate functionality but limits digitalisation, reduces comparability across jurisdictions and restricts the potential for large-scale analysis or integration with emerging digital services.

Table 5 Type of result by country.

Country	PDF	XML / CSV	JSON	API	XSD	Link
Austria						https://www.energieausweise.net/index.php/doku/energieausweis/xml/v6
Belgium	Flanders					
	Wallonia					
	Brussels					
Bulgaria						
Croatia						
Cyprus						
Czech Republic						
Denmark						
Estonia						
Finland						https://github.com/solita/ara-etp/wiki/Rajapintapalvelu
France						
Germany						
Greece						https://www.buildingcert.gr/files/arxeio_manual.pdf https://web.tee.gr/kenak/lojismiko-tee-kenak/
Hungary						
Ireland						
Italy						https://www.cti2000.eu/standard-xml/
Latvia						
Lithuania						

Luxembourg						
Malta						
Netherlands						Not publicly available
Poland						Not publicly available
Portugal						Not publicly available
Romania						
Slovakia						
Slovenia						
Spain						https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/energia/eficiencia/certificacion-energetica/documentos-reconocidos.html
Sweden						

3.3. Analysis of software solutions for EPC in Europe.

The following table represents the mapping of EPC software solutions across Europe, in total 86 software solutions have been identified in this section, spanning official tools developed or mandated by public authorities, approved solutions from private vendors and compliant tools that implement national methodologies without formal approval.

This diversity, while it can be understood as an “open market” opportunity, it also reflects the absence of a harmonised European approach to EPC software design and governance. Each country, in some cases sub-national regions, has developed its own ecosystem of tools. While these as allowed national systems to evolve in line with local needs, it has also resulted in significant barriers to interoperability, cross-border comparison and a promotion of strong pan-European software development companies, as well as innovation.

The software solutions identified can be broadly classified into three main categories:

- **Official tools:** developed or directly mandated by national or regional authorities and required for issuing EPCs. These tools guarantee conformity with national regulations and calculation methodologies but often offer limited flexibility and slower innovation as their evolution depends on administrative processes.
- **Approved tools:** commercial or third-party solutions that have been formally recognised by the competent authority as compliant with national EPC regulations and calculation methodologies. In these markets, software providers compete in terms of usability, features, BIM integration and support while remaining bound to a common national methodology.

- Compliant tools: solutions that follow national methods but are not explicitly approved by the administration.

3.3.1. BIM integration and digital maturity

The analysis of EPC software solutions shows strong disparities in digital maturity across Europe, particularly regarding the integration of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and advanced simulation workflows. While most EPC tools still rely on manual input and simplified geometrical descriptions, a growing number incorporates BIM/CAD-enabled functionalities—most commonly through IFC, gbXML, or CAD-based imports.

A clear pattern emerges from this cross-country review; BIM integration tends to be more developed in software tools that implement dynamic hourly simulation methods. This is due to the fact that dynamic simulation engines require richer input data to accurately represent thermal behaviour of buildings. To feed such detailed models, BIM becomes a natural ally, offering precise geometric descriptions, accurate envelope properties, and enriched object-based information that would be time-consuming to enter manually.

In practice, this means that countries with dynamic calculation requirements tend to exhibit a more advanced digital EPC ecosystem. The availability of BIM workflows in these contexts significantly improves the accuracy of the simulations. It also reduces input errors and allows the reuse of design-phase digital models for EPC purposes, thereby aligning EPC generation with broader digital construction practices.

In the other hand, in countries where EPC methodologies rely almost exclusively on quasi-steady monthly approaches, BIM integration is far less common. The methodologies do not require detailed representations of building geometry or hourly interactions and therefore offer little incentive to incorporate BIM-based data flows. As a result, these tools maintain largely analogue or semi-digital workflows, heavily dependent on manual data entry and simplified building descriptions.

The link between dynamic simulation and BIM is therefore not accidental but structural. Dynamic methods demand a level of detail that BIM can readily provide, while quasi-steady methods operate comfortably with simpler inputs. This creates a digital divide between member states: those moving towards dynamic models are naturally pushed into more mature digital ecosystems where BIM, digital logbooks and enriched data models become part of the workflow, where countries within quasi-steady methods tend to remain in semi-digital certification environments with limited automation and lower levels of data interoperability. This divergence has important implications for the development of enhanced EPCs. As the EPBD places increasing emphasis on

data interoperability, building logbooks, renovation passports and improved accuracy, the presence—or absence—of BIM integration becomes a key indicator for future innovation. Tools already operating with dynamic engines and BIM-enabled inputs are better positioned to evolve towards more sophisticated, interconnected digital ecosystems. In contrast, tools restricted to simplified approaches may face challenges in adapting to upcoming requirements for higher data quality, interoperability, and automation.

Table 6 Existing software solutions for EPC in Europe.

Country	Software	Type	BIM	Link	
Austria	ArchiPHYSIK	Approved	Yes	https://archiphysik.at/	
	GEQ	Approved	No	https://www.geq.at/	
	AX3000	Approved	Yes	https://www.ax3000.at	
	Ecotech Gebäuderechner	Approved	CAD	https://www.ecotech.cc/	
	Gebäudeprofi	Approved	CAD	https://www.etu.at	
Belgium	Flanders	EPB Software 3G	Official	No	https://www.vlaanderen.be/epb-pedia/epb-software/epb-software-3g
		EPB-Software Vlaanderen	Official	No	https://www.vlaanderen.be/epb-pedia/epb-software/epb-software-vlaanderen
	Wallonia	Logiciel PEB	Official	No	https://energie.wallonie.be/home/performance-energetique-des-batiments/pour-les-professionnels-outils-formations-et-agrements/outils/la-reglementation-wallonne---peb/logiciel-peb/version-15.5.1.html
	Brussels	PEB Logiciel	Official	No	https://environnement.brussels/pro/documentation-et-outils/sites-web-et-outils-interactifs/outils-pour-les-conseillers-peb-et-les-architectes
Bulgaria	EECalc	Compliant	No	No public link	
	EAB	Compliant	No	No public link	
Croatia	MGIPU Energetski certifikator	Official	No	https://mpgi.gov.hr/o-ministarstvu/djelokrug-50/energetsko-certificiranje-zgrada-8304/racunalni-program-za-odredjivanje-energetskog-svojtva-zgrade-8359/8359	
	EnCert -HR	Approved	No	https://www.encert.hr/	
Cyprus	iSBEM-Cy	Official	No	https://isbem-cy.software.informer.com/	
Czech Republic	Energetika - DEKSOFT	Approved	CAD	https://deksoft.eu/en/programy/programs	
Denmark	BE18	Approved	No	https://www.be18.sbi.dk/be/	
	Energy10	Approved	No	https://www.energy10.dk/	
Estonia	IDA ICE	Approved	Yes	https://www.equa.se/en/ida-ice/	
Finland	IDA ICE	Approved	Yes	https://www.equa.se/en/ida-ice/	

	RIUSKA/MAgiCAD Comfort & Energy	Approved	Yes	https://www.magicad.com/en/magicad-comfort-energy/
	Lamitor	Approved	No	https://lamitor.fi/
	EasyE	Approved	No	https://easve.fi/
	Aina Energy	Approved	No	https://ainaenergy.fi/
France	CYPE THERM RE202	Approved	Yes	https://info.cype.com/fr/software/cypetherm-re2020/
	ClimaWIN 2020	Approved	Limited	https://www.bbs-logiciels.com/climawin-logiciel-re2020/
	Pleiades	Approved	Yes	https://www.izuba.fr/logiciels/outils-logiciels/dpe-audit/
	U21/U22 - Win V6	Approved	No	https://produits.batiactu.com/publi/les-logiciels-perrenoud-pour-la-re2020-sont-dispon-261-195556.php
	ArchiWIZARD	Approved	Yes	https://gratec.com/fr/products/archiwizard/
	VisualTTH	Approved	Yes	https://support.fisa.fr/fiche/produit/1
Germany	Energieberater Wohnen & Gewerbe (Hottgenroth)	Approved	CAD	https://www.hottgenroth.de
	BKI Energieplaner	Approved	Limited	https://www.bki.de/energieplaner
	EVEBI (ENVISYS)	Approved	Limited	https://www.envisys.de/startseite/
	ZUB Helena	Approved	Limited	https://www.zub-systems.de
	IBP:18599	Approved	No	https://ibp-18599.de/
	Solar-Computer Energieeffizienz GEG	Approved	CAD	https://www.solar-computer.de/index.php?seite=produkte&sub=energie&software=software-energie-energieausweis-GEG-DIND18599-WG-NWG
Greece	TEE-KENAK	Official	No	https://web.tee.gr/kenak/logismiko-tee-kenak/
	4M-KENAK	Approved	CAD	https://4m.gr/el/brands-2/4
	Energy Building CAD	Approved	CAD	https://www.civiltech.gr/products/Energy/EnergyMain
	easyKENAK	Approved	No	https://www.easykenak.gr/
	3DR.KENAK	Approved	Limited	https://www.3dr.eu/product_landing_page/kenak-%CE%B5%CE%BD%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%B5%CE%B9%CE%B1%CE%B

		ed	ed	A%CE%AD%CF%82-%CE%BC%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%AD%CF%84%CE%B5%CF%82-%CE%B5%CF%80%CE%B9%CE%B8%CE%B5%CF%89%CF%81%CE%AE%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%B9%CF%82/
	IsZEB Certify	Approved	No	https://iszeb.gr/el/iszeb-certify
Hungary	Auricon Energetic	Approved	No	https://energetic.auricon.hu/
	ETAPP	Approved	No	https://etapp.hu/
	ArchiPHYSIK	Approved	Yes	https://www.archiphysik.at
	WinWatt	Approved	No	http://www.bausoft.hu/ww32.htm
Ireland	DEAP Software	Official	No	https://www.seai.ie/ber/support-for-ber-assessors/deap
	iSBEMie Neap	Official	No	https://www.seai.ie/ber/support-for-ber-assessors/neap
	G-ISBEM	Approved	CAD	https://www.g-isbem.com/
	DesignBuilder SBEM	Approved	Yes	https://designbuilder.co.uk/software/designbuilder-sbem-and-dsm-approved-versions
	Virtual Environment (IES) / BER Assesor	Approved	Yes	https://www.iesve.com/software/virtual-environment/applications/ber-assessor
Italy	Blumatica Energy	Approved	CAD	https://www.blumatica.it/software-certificazione-energetica-degli-edifici-ape-ed-age/
	TERMOLOG (Logical Soft)	Approved	Yes	https://service.logical.it/software-termotecnica/certificazione-energetica-degli-edifici
	APE Online	Approved	No	https://www.ape-online.it/
	TerMus / TerMus CE (ACCA)	Approved	Yes	https://www.acca.it/software-ape
	CYPETHER M.C.E. (CYPE)	Approved	Yes	https://info.cype.com/en/category/energy-efficiency/
	EC780 / Edilclima	Approved	No	https://www.edilclima.it/software/edilclima/termotecnica-energetica/
Latvia	Excel File	Official	No	No public link
Lithuania	NGR - SERT - 7 / NGR - PRO	Official	No	https://www.lei.lt/en/catalog/building-energy-efficiency-certification-program-nrg-sert/
Luxembourg	LuxEeB-Tool (Habitation)	Official	No	https://meco.gouvernement.lu/fr/domaines-activites/energie/efficacite-energetique/informations-techniques.html
	Lesosai (Habitation)	Approved	Yes	https://lesosai.com/

	LuxEeB-F (Functional)	Approved	Limited	https://ibp-18599.de/ipb18599-luxemburg/
Malta	EPC Government	Official	No	https://epc.gov.mt/calculation_software
Netherlands	Vabi EPA	Approved	Yes	https://www.vitec-vabi.com/vabi-epa/
Poland	CEEB platform by GUNB	Official	No	No public link
	AudytorOZC (Sankom)	Approved	Yes	https://pl.sankom.net/programy/audytor-ozc
Portugal	PTnZEB	Approved	No	https://www.peritosqualificados.pt/pt/sessoes-ptnzeb/
	ItCons	Approved	No	https://www.itecons.uc.pt/p3e/index.php
	Dentherm	Approved	No	https://www.densare.pt/index.php
	CYPETHER M SCE-Hab / CYPETHER M SCE-CS	Approved	Yes	https://info.cype.com/pt/software/cypetherm-sce-cs-plus/
Romania	AllEnergy PEC - Algorithm+	Compliant	No	https://www.algorithm.ro/software-performanta-energetica-cladiri-8/
	InteliEPB - Intelisoft Solutions	Compliant	No	https://www.inteliepb.ro/aplicatie-program-software-audit-energetic-certificate-energetice/
	ENERG+ - OAER	Compliant	No	https://energ-plus.ro/
Slovakia	DEKSOFT – ENERGETIKA / módulo EPC	Approved	No	https://deksoft.eu/sk/programy/energetika/energetickycertifikat
Slovenia	PURES 3	Official	No	https://www.energetika-portal.si/podrocja/energetika/energetske-izkaznice-stavb/izracun-energijske-ucinkovitosti-stavb/
Spain	CE3X	Approved	No	https://efinova.es/CE3X
	CERMA (Residencial)	Approved	No	https://productos.five.es/producto/cerma
	SG SAVE	Official region	No	https://www.placo.es/sg-save
	HULC	Approved	Limited	https://www.codigotecnico.org/Programas/HerramientaUnificadaLIDERCALENER.html
	CYPETHER M HE Plus	Approved	Yes	https://info.cype.com/es/software/cypetherm-he-plus/
	Tekton3D TK-CEEP	Approved	Yes	https://www.imventa.com/he-ahorro-de-energ%C3%ADa
Sweden	BV2 (Boverkets verktyg för energiberäkning)	Official	No	https://bv2.se/9/index.php

	IDA ICE	Approved	Yes	https://www.equa.se/en/ida-ice/
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3.3.2. Structural barriers in the EPC software development.

Although the presence of 86 EPC software solutions across the 27 EU member states could be interpreted as a sign of market openness, this perception overlooks the structural reality of the EPC ecosystem. The proliferation of tools is not the result of an integrated European market encouraging competition, but rather the consequence of deep regulatory fragmentation. Because each country applies its own calculation rules, reference values, data structures and validation mechanisms, software tools are developed in isolation from one another and serve strictly national, even regional needs. Instead of competing within a unified European market, developers operate within 27 disconnected micro-markets defined by local legislation.

Regulatory fragmentation increases the barriers for software developers, our analysis shows that only four vendors—CYPE, EQUA Simulation, ArchiPHYSIK and 4M—currently operate in multiple markets. The main reason is that any company aspiring to operate in more than one country must learn and implement entirely different methodological frameworks, maintain separate versions of their products and comply with multiple, often incompatible regulatory systems. This increases development time and maintenance costs and makes cross-border expansion prohibitively complex. This situation also suppresses innovation. Instead of investing in new features such as BIM integration, improved interoperability, dynamic simulation modules or AI-aided modelling, developers must devote substantial effort to understanding administrative details and reproducing divergent national conventions. Considerable resources are spent adapting software to different reference datasets, formats and XML structures—work that does not generate added value for users but is necessary to survive within each national framework.

3.3.2.1. CYPE's case study.

As part of I-EBRA project, CYPE's experience is relevant as software development company that has tailored EPC software tools for Spain, Portugal, France and Italy. In this context the company has had to develop four different national methodologies, each with its own regulatory conventions, language barriers, input structures, simulation engines, and data-validation rules. In addition, the software for the four countries has had to undergo four separate approval processes, one for each national context. In practical terms, this has required programming and maintaining three completely different calculation engines—France (RE2020), Portugal (PT-nZEB) and Spain (EnergyPlus) —as

well as four separate XML schemas, each aligned with the specific data structures and registry requirements of the corresponding national authority. Furthermore, CYPE's software has implemented dynamic calculation engines and supports BIM workflows, enabling more detailed simulations, advanced HVAC modelling and greater alignment with EPBD principles for enhanced EPCs, allowing the reuse of IFC and model-based information to automate data entry and improve the quality and consistency of EPC inputs. This dual focus on dynamic simulation and BIM places CYPE among a very limited group of vendors at the forefront of digital EPC software development in Europe.

Consequently, even in countries where CYPE is already present—such as France and Italy—the degree of market access remains limited, and commercial returns are modest compared to the development effort required. This underlines a key finding of this deliverable: multi-country EPC software development is technically feasible, but under the current fragmentation of the EPC ecosystem it is rarely economically viable, even for highly specialised companies that integrate dynamic simulation and BIM across their solutions.

3.4. Analysis of other types of software solutions related with EPBD: building digital logbooks, LCA.

The EPBD expands the EPC ecosystem by promoting two complementary digital solutions—Building Digital Logbooks (BDLs) and Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) tools—which enhance data availability, interoperability and whole-life performance assessment. BDLs act as a comprehensive “digital memory” of a building, centralising documentation such as EPCs, renovation history, material passports and digital twins, and the EPBD requires Member States to ensure their interoperability with Renovation Passports and SRIs. In parallel, the growing emphasis on whole-life carbon makes LCA tools increasingly important, as they quantify both embodied and operational carbon and increasingly leverage BIM-based workflows. However, both BDLs and LCA software remain less mature and more heterogeneous than traditional EPC tools, with uneven deployment across Europe and varying levels of standardisation. LCA tools additionally rely on specialised LCA databases (e.g. EPDs, EN-15804 datasets), which are essential for producing reliable whole-life carbon calculations. Together, these emerging tool categories are expected to become tightly integrated with next-generation EPC systems under the EPBD framework.

Table 7 LCA and DBL software solutions in Europe

Type	Name		BIM	Link
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LCA	One Click LCA	Software + DataBase	Yes	https://oneclicklca.com/
LCA	SimaPro	Software + DataBase	No	https://simapro.com/
LCA	OpenLCA	Software + DataBase	No	https://www.openlca.org/
LCA	Generador de Precios - CYPE	Database	Yes	https://generadordeprecios.info/
LCA	Open BIM Quantities - CYPE	Software	Yes	https://info.cype.com/en/software/open-bim-quantities/
BDL	Cléa	Software	No	https://clea.qualitel.org/
BDL	The Woningpas	Software	No	https://woningpas.vlaanderen.be/
BDL	BuildingUser	Software	No	https://buildinguser.com/

4 IDENTIFIED BEST PRACTICES

Prepared alongside the data guidelines for collection, processing, validation and sharing (D2.3), this whole best-practices-related report provides relevant data to support their development. In particular, information such as the identified EPC results, relevant KPIs, and effective procedures for data reporting and verification, helps shape the recommendations and guidelines and strengthens consistency between deliverables D2.3 and D2.1

In this last section, identified best practices are listed.

4.1 Transferable methodologies of existing initiatives

The analysis of partner contributions allowed the identification of a set of best practices that go beyond national specificities and can be transferred across different contexts. Key transferable methodologies include:

Progressive upgrade of EPC systems into renovation-oriented tools

Rather than developing entirely new instruments, several initiatives extend existing EPC methodologies with additional functionalities, such as lifecycle cost analysis and staged renovation scenarios. In many contexts, EPC systems are expected to gradually incorporate BRP-related elements in line with the EPBD recast. This incremental approach supports feasibility, cost-efficiency and institutional continuity.

Standardised and regularly updated calculation methodologies

Clearly defined national methodologies aligned with EU standards and periodically revised to reflect technological and regulatory changes represent an important best practice. Regular updates ensure consistency, credibility and long-term usability of EPC systems.

Multi-dimensional performance indicators

The use of multiple indicators, such as energy demand, CO₂ emissions and primary energy consumption, provides a more comprehensive understanding of building performance and supports more informed renovation decisions, while creating a basis for integrating additional indicators such as lifecycle emissions.

Integration with financial and policy instruments

Using EPCs as supporting elements for accessing renovation incentives increases their practical relevance and helps transform them from informational tools into instruments that facilitate renovation activity.

Combined use of calculated and measured EPCs

The structured use of both demand-based and consumption-based EPCs improves the robustness of assessments by combining standardised calculations with real operational performance.

Reference building approach

Assessing building performance relative to a standardized reference building supports comparability, flexibility across building types and alignment with regulatory thresholds, making this a highly transferable methodology.

Integration with digital building logbooks and data platforms

Linking EPC systems with broader digital ecosystems enables continuously updated tools that support renovation planning, monitoring and policy evaluation.

Standardised methodologies with flexible software implementation

Harmonised calculation rules combined with flexible software tools represent a transferable approach that supports both consistency and innovation.

Simplified calculation approaches and building typologies

Particularly relevant for residential buildings, simplified methods and typological approaches enable scaling EPC assessments across large building stocks while maintaining acceptable accuracy.

Phased and flexible renovation pathways

Step-by-step renovation roadmaps allow interventions to be aligned with technical and financial constraints and represent a core methodology underlying the BRP concept.

4.2 Transferable methodologies from EU funded projects

The past EU projects identified that relate to EPC and BRP were carried out across a wide range of partners located in different EU countries. Many projects focused on specific geographies, with implementation through pilots, yet encompassed challenges and solutions that are potentially applicable on an EU level. A summary of the main elements that were identified that could provide valuable insight on EPCs and BRPs to the IEBRA project are summarized below.

From the EPC standpoint, some projects focused on regulation and recommendations, such as CrossCert, that provides valuable insight on recommendations for improvements of new EPC for buildings and TunES that offers regulation suggestions to integrate EPCs into SRIs. For the ongoing EPBD WISE project, focus is placed on direct support to local authorities to implement the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). The levels of EPC accuracy and consideration of up-to-date content are also considered such as in TIMEPAC which focuses on how to build dynamic EPCs, D²EPC that focused on the creation of dynamic and digital EPCs based on near-real-time data and Smart Living EPC focus on the digital integration of EPCs, through the delivery of a certificate issued with the use of digitized tools.

SMARTER EPC is an ongoing project that builds on past projects to provide tools that can issue EPCs and SRIs. In terms of elaborating EPC related planning tasks, EPC RECAST developed a process and tools to better assess building energy performance, retrofit needs, and financing opportunities, and Chronicle worked ways to support the efficient renovation procedures and investment decision-making processes. Some projects explored and framed the type of indicators that EPCs should have, notably X-tendo which introduced ten features of energy performance certificates.

Some of the main aspects related to the BRP of potential interest include the development of a common criteria of energy certificates across Europe, developed by the SuperHub project. IBRoad2EPC for its part, focused on the integration of BRP elements into EPC schemes, showcased in their software that also produces building renovation steps upon inputting the building information data.

The best practices identified directly applicable to the development of an enhanced EPC are:

Development of modular and scalable digital tools, allowing gradual upgrades of EPC systems with additional functionalities such as renovation pathways, scenario comparison, and cost assessment. This ensures flexibility and easier integration into existing national frameworks.

Integrated data structures, where EPC data is combined with building characteristics, renovation measures, and, where possible, operational data. This approach improves the accuracy of assessments and enables more advanced functionalities, including personalized renovation recommendations.

Predefined renovation scenarios and automated calculations, which simplify the generation of renovation pathways and reduce the need for manual expert input. This significantly increases usability and scalability of tools.

User-centred design principles, ensuring that tools are adapted to different target groups (e.g. homeowners, public authorities, experts), with clear outputs, visualizations, and decision-support features.

4.3 Innovative technical solutions

The analysis of EPC software tools across Europe reveals several innovative technical solutions that can be considered best practices for the future development of enhanced EPCs. Although the European market remains highly fragmented, certain technologies and design approaches consistently appear in the most advanced tools and demonstrate clear added value for accuracy, interoperability and digital integration.

One of the most relevant innovations is the incorporation of dynamic simulation engines, replacing or complementing traditional quasi-steady calculation methods. Dynamic engines enable a more realistic representation of building behaviour, HVAC interactions and comfort conditions. Their adoption is closely linked to more advanced digital ecosystems, as they require richer datasets and higher modelling precision. This technical shift offers a substantial improvement in EPC reliability, especially for complex buildings.

Closely connected to dynamic simulation is the integration of BIM-enabled workflows. EPC software that imports IFC, gbXML or other model-based formats can automate large parts of the data-entry process by reusing geometric and construction information created during the design phase. This reduces human error, accelerates EPC generation and supports the long-term digitalisation of building information. BIM-based data reuse is also a key enabler for future EPBD instruments such as digital logbooks and renovation passports.

A further innovative practice is the use of structured, machine-readable data formats, such as XML, JSON or CSV, often supported by national schemas or APIs. Tools capable of exporting complete EPC datasets in structured formats contribute to higher interoperability, easier integration with national registries and more efficient quality-assurance processes. APIs, where available, allow automated validation and submission workflows, improving data consistency and reducing administrative burden.

Another important development is the use of modular software architectures, where the calculation engine, user interface and data-handling components are separated. This approach makes it easier to update individual modules when regulations change and facilitates the adaptation of tools to multiple national contexts. It is particularly relevant for developers that operate in several member states, who must maintain different methodologies, XML schemas and approval pathways simultaneously.

It is also important to consider the integration of predefined renovation scenarios and automated calculation workflows, which enable the generation of step-by-step renovation pathways with limited manual input. This significantly improves usability and scalability of EPC-related tools.

Finally, the definition and inclusion in the EPC of new indicators on for example comfort, outdoor air quality or smart readiness is also an innovation that should be highlighted. Overall, these innovations demonstrate that despite regulatory fragmentation, there is a clear technological trajectory towards dynamic simulation, BIM integration, structured data workflows, modular architectures and enhanced user guidance. Together, these elements form the basis of the most advanced EPC software solutions and point towards the capabilities required for next-generation enhanced EPCs.

4.4 Governance and implementation models

The governance analysis reveals several best practices that are essential for the effective implementation and future evolution of EPC and BRP systems. Key governance and implementation models include:

Strong regulatory frameworks with structured implementation systems

A robust legislative framework defining methodologies, obligations and compliance requirements provides a stable basis for the development and long-term functioning of EPC systems.

Centralised digital EPC registries and platforms

Digital registries and platforms support data collection, quality control, monitoring and policy evaluation, while providing a backbone for transparent and efficient system management.

Regulated and certified expert systems

The use of qualified professionals operating under defined certification requirements, often structured across different competence levels and supported by continuous training, is a key best practice for ensuring quality, reliability and credibility.

Dedicated institutions responsible for system management

National agencies or competent institutions responsible for database management, methodological updates and system control represent an important governance model supporting continuous improvement.

Quality control and verification mechanisms

Random checks, validation procedures and penalties for non-compliance are essential governance measures that strengthen the reliability and credibility of EPC systems.

On-site inspections and verification procedures

Mandatory inspections, or equivalent verification approaches, help ensure that EPCs are based on reliable and verified building data.

Multi-level governance models

Combining national coordination with regional or local implementation allows adaptation to local conditions while maintaining consistency through central data aggregation and monitoring.

Integrated digital platforms and one-stop-shop systems

Emerging governance models increasingly combine EPC data with other building-related information, advisory services and financing instruments, improving user engagement and facilitating renovation implementation.

Integration into broader strategic and policy frameworks

Linking EPC and BRP systems with long-term renovation strategies and wider policy frameworks ensures alignment with decarbonisation objectives and strengthens their strategic role in the energy transition.

REFERENCES

- Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the energy performance of buildings (recast), Official Journal of the European Union, 2024. Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202401275&pk_keyword=Energy&pk_content=Directive
- Energy Efficiency Act (ZURE), Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia, No. 158/2020, including subsequent amendments.
- Pravilnik o metodologiji izdelave in izdaji energetskega izkaznice stavb, Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia, No. 4/2023. Available at: <https://pisrs.si/pregledPredpisa?id=PRAV14831>
- Energy portal of the Republic of Slovenia. Calculation of energy performance of buildings. Available at: <https://www.energetika-portal.si/podrocja/energetika/energetske-izkaznice-stavb/izracun-energijske-ucinkovitosti-stavb/>
- Real Decreto 390/2021 on the energy certification of buildings, Boletín Oficial del Estado, No. 131, 02/06/2021. Available at: <https://www.boe.es>
- Anape (2025). Transposition of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive into Spanish legislation. Available at: <https://anape.es/actualidad/transposicion-de-la-directiva-de-eficiencia-energetica-de-edificios-a-la-normativa-espanola/>
- EPC Spain. Frequently Asked Questions on Energy Performance Certificates. Available at: <https://www.epc-spain.com/questions-about-energy-performance-certificate.html>
- QualDeEPC. Energy Performance Certificates of Buildings. Available at: <https://qualrenovate.eu/es/services-products/energy-performance-certificates/energy-performance-certificates/>
- ICAEN. Frequently Asked Questions on energy certification. Available at: https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/energia/usos_energia/Antic_edificis-carpeta/page/preguntes_frequents/#faq-faq_cert_gen01
- Real Decreto 314/2006 approving the Technical Building Code (Código Técnico de la Edificación), Boletín Oficial del Estado, No. 74, 28/03/2006. Available at: <https://www.boe.es>
- ICAEN. What is energy certification? Available at: https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/energia/usos_energia/edificis/certificacio/que-es-la-certificacio-energetica/index.html

- Paz, P. (2025). Registration of Energy Certificates in Spain. Certicalia. Available at: <https://www.certicalia.com/blog/registro-del-certificado-energetico-en-cada-comunidad-autonoma>
- BUILD UP (2026). From policy to practice: how renovation passports empower Europe's Renovation Wave. Available at: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/resources-and-tools/articles/how-renovation-passports-empower-europes-renovation-wave>
- Jansen, S.C., Mohammadi, S., Bokel, R. (2020). Developing a locally balanced energy system for an existing neighbourhood. Elsevier.
- MITECO (2015). Energy performance rating of buildings. Available at: <https://www.miteco.gob.es>
- Serrano, P. (2021). Minimum content of energy certificates according to RD 390/2021. Available at: <https://www.certificadosenergeticos.com/contenido-minimo-del-certificado-energetico>
- Casanovas, X., Pedreny, O. (2013). Certifying the energy efficiency of existing buildings. RIARTE.
- Real Decreto 659/2025, Boletín Oficial del Estado, No. 176, 23/07/2025. Available at: <https://www.boe.es>
- Portuguese Energy Certification System – Legislation. Available at: <https://www.sce.pt/legislacao/>
- Decreto-Lei No. 101-D/2020 establishing energy performance requirements for buildings. Available at: <https://dre.pt>
- Decreto-Lei No. 11/2025 transposing Directive (EU) 2024/1275. Available at: <https://dre.pt>
- ADENE – Portuguese Energy Agency. Available at: <https://www.adene.pt/>
- Decreto-Lei No. 101-D/2020 on certification system technicians. Available at: <https://dre.pt>
- Portal Casa+ – Efficient and comfortable homes. Available at: <https://portalcasamais.pt>
- Italy. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico (2015). National guidelines for building energy certification. Available at: <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it>
- Comitato Termotecnico Italiano. UNI/TS 11300 standards. Available at: <https://www.cti2000.it>
- Italy. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico (2015). National guidelines for energy certification (Annex 1). Available at: <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it>
- Italy. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico (2015). Methodologies for calculating energy performance. Available at: <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it>

- Italy. Presidential Decree No. 75/2013 on accreditation of experts. Available at: <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it>
- ENEA (2019). SIAPE – National Information System for EPCs. Available at: <https://www.enea.it>
- European Commission, CINEA. tunES project. Available at: <https://cinea.ec.europa.eu>
- Vogt, G., Novikova, T., Junak, K. Final Report on EPC and SRI instruments.
- ENEA (2022). National portal on building energy performance. Available at: <https://www.enea.it>
- ENEA (2024). Annual report on building energy certification. Available at: <https://www.enea.it>
- ENEA (2025). Annual report on building energy certification. Available at: <https://www.enea.it>
- Germany. Gebäudeenergiegesetz (GEG), §21. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- BAFA. Federal funding for energy consulting (EBW). Available at: <https://www.bafa.de>
- BAFA. Guidelines for renovation roadmaps (iSFP). Available at: <https://www.bafa.de>
- Germany. GEG Annex 1. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- Germany. GEG Annex 2. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- Germany. Gebäudeenergiegesetz (GEG), 2020. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- DIN. DIN V 18599 standards. Available at: <https://www.din.de>
- Germany. GEG §80. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- Germany. GEG §82. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- Germany. GEG §88. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- Germany. GEG Annex 11. Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de>
- Qualitätssiegel Nachhaltiges Gebäude (2024). QNG Handbook.
- Qualitätssiegel Nachhaltiges Gebäude (2024). Building requirements.
- BAFA (2024). Renovation roadmap guidelines.
- BAFA. Energy consulting programme. Available at: <https://www.bafa.de>
- Austria. General information on EPC. Available at: <https://www.oesterreich.gv.at>

- OIB. Guideline 6 – Energy saving and thermal protection. Available at: <https://www.oib.or.at>
- Austria. Obligation to provide EPC. Available at: <https://www.oesterreich.gv.at>
- Austria. Content of EPC. Available at: <https://www.oesterreich.gv.at>
- klimaaktiv. Renovation roadmap guide. Available at: <https://www.klimaaktiv.at>
- Croatia. Regulation on energy certification of buildings. Available at: <https://www.zakon.hr>
- Croatia. Long-Term Renovation Strategy 2050. Available at: <https://mpgi.gov.hr>
- Croatia. Long-Term Renovation Strategy 2050 (EN). Available at: https://mpgi.gov.hr/UserDocImages/dokumenti/EnergetskaUcinkovitost/Long_Term_Renovation_Strategy_EN.pdf
- Czech Republic. Energy performance certificate (PENB). Available at: <https://www.mpo.cz>
- Czech Republic. Energy performance requirements. Available at: <https://www.mpo.cz>
- Czech Republic. Decree No. 264/2020 Sb. Available at: <https://www.mpo.cz>
- Czech Republic. Energy specialists. Available at: <https://www.mpo.cz>
- Czech Republic. Certification of energy specialists. Available at: <https://www.mpo.cz>
- Czech Republic. Register of energy specialists. Available at: <https://www.mpo.cz>
- Denmark. Act on energy savings in buildings (2025). Available at: <https://www.retsinformation.dk>
- Denmark. Executive Order on energy labelling (2023). Available at: <https://www.retsinformation.dk>
- Denmark. Handbook for energy consultants (2023). Available at: <https://www.hbemo.dk>
- France. Construction and Housing Code. Available at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>
- France. Energy performance diagnosis regulation (2021). Available at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>
- ADEME. EPC FAQ. Available at: <https://observatoire-dpe-audit.ademe.fr>

- BUILD UP. Renovation passports in France. Available at: <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu>
- France. EPC models. Available at: <https://rt-re-batiment.developpement-durable.gouv.fr>
- France. Energy certification obligations. Available at: <https://entreprendre.service-public.gouv.fr>
- Greece. Energy inspection. Available at: <https://www.ypen.gr>
- Greece. Energy performance regulation. Available at: <https://www.ypen.gr>
- Greece. National legislation (KENAK). Available at: <https://www.tee.gr>
- Greece. Energy certificate requirement. Available at: <https://www.ypen.gr>
- Greece. Inspection results. Available at: <https://www.ypen.gr>
- BuildingCert. Energy inspection guide. Available at: <https://www.buildingcert.gr>
- BuildingCert. Registry of inspections. Available at: <https://www.buildingcert.gr>
- BuildingCert. Inspectors registry. Available at: <https://www.buildingcert.gr>
- BuildingCert. Energy inspectors registry. Available at: <https://www.buildingcert.gr>
- Technical Chamber of Greece. Electronic Building Identity. Available at: <https://www.tee.gr>
- Greece. Law 4495/2017. Available at: <https://www.et.gr>
- D²EPC project. Available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu>
- Ioannidis, D. et al. (2026). D2EPC framework. Available at: <https://www.certh.gr>
- iBRoad2EPC project. Available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu>
- SmartLivingEPC project. Available at: <https://cordis.europa.eu>
- Malta. Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations. Available at: <https://bca.gov.mt>
- Malta. EPBD Amendment Regulations (2023). Available at: <https://bca.gov.mt>

ANNEXES

ANNEX A - Overview of Partner Contributions on EPC and BRP Systems

National initiatives EPC and BRP								
n°	Country	General Framework of EPC and BRP	Energy-performance indicators	Qualification of certifiers	Data collection sources	Transferable methodologies	Innovative technical solutions	Governance and implementation models
1	Austria	<p>-Austria's EPC framework is split between federal and provincial levels, with federal law governing when an EPC must be presented in property transactions and provincial building laws setting the rules for when it must be prepared.</p> <p>-An EPC is generally required for property sales and rentals, and it must usually be no more than ten years old; for flats or business units, the EPC may cover the unit itself, a comparable unit, or the whole building.</p> <p>-EPC production varies by region, since Austria's provinces apply their own building-law provisions, although these are broadly harmonised through the OIB Guidelines, especially OIB Guideline 6.</p>	<p>Specific heating demand, primary energy demand, CO₂ emissions, and the overall energy-efficiency factor (fGEE); non-residential EPCs may also include cooling demand.</p>	<p>-In Austria, EPCs may be issued only by legally authorized professional groups, including master builders, certain regulated technical trades, engineering consultants, civil engineers, and architects.</p> <p>-The qualification system is therefore profession-based and regulated by legal scope of practice</p>	<p>- Blueprints</p>	<p>A stepwise renovation roadmap over up to 15 years</p>	<p>Using a structured criteria catalogue and process guide</p>	<p>A nationally coordinated but voluntary programme framework</p>

2	Croatia	<p>-EPC system is regulated under the national Building Act (2019) and aligned with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)</p> <p>-EPC is mandatory for: B7new buildings, buildings for sale or rent, major renovations</p> <p>-Certificates are issued by authorised experts or legal entities, licensed by the Ministry</p> <p>National EPC database managed by Energy Institute Hrvoje Požar (EIHP)</p> <p>-EPC currently represents a static assessment tool, mainly based on calculated energy performance</p> <p>-Building Renovation Passport (BRP) is not yet systematically implemented</p> <p>-No full integration between EPC and long-term renovation planning yet</p> <p>-Gradual alignment expected with EPBD recast (digitalisation, BRP, data integration)</p>	<p>-Energy class (typically A–G scale)</p> <p>-Primary energy consumption</p> <p>-CO₂ emissions</p> <p>-Energy demand (heating, cooling, DHW)</p> <p>-Share of renewable energy</p> <p>-Recommendations for energy efficiency improvements</p> <p>-Indicators are based on calculated performance, not real consumption</p> <p>-No integration of life-cycle assessment (LCA) or financial indicators</p>	<p>-EPCs issued by authorised natural or legal persons</p> <p>-Certification requires: relevant technical degree (engineering, architecture, etc.), completion of accredited training programmes, passing a professional exam</p> <p>-Training providers are appointed by the Ministry (fixed period)</p> <p>-Registry of certified experts maintained at national level</p> <p>-Quality control system exists (including supervision and potential removal from registry in case of misconduct)</p>	<p>- On-site building inspection conducted by a certified Energy Consultant, including measurements, visual assessment, and verification of construction elements and technical systems.</p> <p>- Building documentation such as architectural drawings, technical specifications, renovation records, installation manuals.</p>	<p>-Standardised EPC methodology aligned with EPBD framework</p> <p>-Use of national calculation methods consistent with EU standards</p> <p>-Centralised certification and database system (replicable model)</p> <p>-Quality control procedures (sampling and verification of EPCs)</p>	<p>-Currently limited level of innovation</p> <p>-EPC generation mainly based on: conventional calculation software, manual data input</p> <p>No widespread use of: BIM integration, digital building logbooks, real-time monitoring</p> <p>EPC database is centralised but: not fully interoperable, limited open data access (partial public access, GDPR constraints)</p> <p>Lack of integration with: smart readiness indicators (SRI), BRP, financial tools</p>	<p>-Centralised governance: Ministry responsible for legislation and licensing, EIHP responsible for EPC system management</p> <p>-Defined roles: certifiers (data generation), government (regulation and control)</p> <p>-Partial data openness: public access to selected EPC data, restricted technical and personal data due to GDPR</p>
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3	Czechia	<p>The PENB framework is governed by the Energy Management Act and its implementing Decree No. 264/2020 Coll., in force since 1 September 2020.</p> <p>In the Czech Republic, the official EPC is the PENB.</p> <p>It is required for new buildings, major renovations, sales, rentals, and some public buildings.</p> <p>The PENB is based on a theoretical calculation method, not actual utility bills.</p> <p>It is generally valid for 10 years, unless major building or system changes require renewal earlier.</p>	<p>The PENB uses indicators such as non-renewable primary energy, total delivered energy, and specific heating need.</p> <p>It also assesses heat-transfer performance, U-values, and technical system efficiency.</p> <p>Buildings are classified on an A to G rating scale.</p>	<p>PENBs may only be issued by an authorised energy specialist.</p> <p>Authorisation requires relevant education, professional experience, and a state examination.</p>	- Blueprints	Using a standardized theoretical calculation method	A multi-indicator EPC framework	A centrally regulated system with authorised energy specialists and a formal examination process
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4	Denmark	<p>-The Danish EPC system is regulated by: Act on the Promotion of Energy Savings in Buildings (LBK 1253/2025), Executive Order on the Energy Labelling of Buildings (BEK 549/2023), Handbook for energy consultants (HB2023),</p> <p>-EPCs are mandatory for sales, rentals over four weeks, new buildings, and public buildings above defined size thresholds.</p> <p>-EPC validity is up to 10 years but ends earlier if major energy-relevant changes occur.</p> <p>-Danish EPCs are always calculated using a standardized methodology, with limited exceptions for newer single-family houses.</p> <p>-BRP is under development but not yet mandatory.</p>	<p>-Danish EPCs use indicators defined in HB2023, including delivered energy, heating demand, primary energy, CO₂ emissions, U-values and linear thermal bridges.</p> <p>-Energy classes A2020–G are based on BR2010/2015/2020 requirements, with A2020 as the highest and G as the lowest class.</p> <p>-Indicators are based on calculated performance, not real consumption</p> <p>-No integration of life-cycle assessment (LCA)</p>	<p>-EPC experts must be registered, certified and accredited according to LBK 1253/2025 and BEK 549/2023.</p> <p>-They need a relevant technical degree</p> <p>-they must complete Energy Consultant I/II training which includes theoretical modules and a practical examination</p> <p>-they need to undergo refresher training every three years</p> <p>-they must work within a certified company (ISO 9001)</p> <p>-supervision includes audits and external reviews of 5–10% of EPCs</p>	<p>- On-site building inspection conducted by a certified Energy Consultant, including measurements, visual assessment, and verification of construction elements and technical systems.</p> <p>- Building documentation such as architectural drawings, technical specifications, renovation records, installation manuals, and municipal building files (BBR register).</p> <p>- Standardised technical catalogues and calculation inputs from HB2023 (U-value catalogues, thermal-bridge catalogues, emission factors, system performance data).</p> <p>- Official Danish energy-conversion and emission factors referenced in BEK 549/2023 and HB2023.</p> <p>- Digital register data from the national BBR building register and other publicly available national databases.</p>	<p>- Fully digitalised national EPC system with open data access (API), enabling reuse of EPC data across sectors.</p> <p>- Integrated link between EPC data and the national building register (BBR), ensuring high data accuracy.</p> <p>- Structured digital BRP concept (Ejendomspas) providing a step-by-step renovation roadmap (in development, but advanced compared to other countries).</p>	<p>Denmark is developing a voluntary digital BRP to be integrated into the National Building Renovation Plan (2026). The EPC system is fully digitalised, including a national EPC database and EMOData API. The measured EPC method has been abolished, and EPCs now rely exclusively on the HB2023 calculation methodology.</p>	<p>- Initiatives are centrally organised and managed by the Danish Energy Agency (Energistyrelsen).</p> <p>- The digital EPC system (national database + EMOData API) is state-maintained and financed through national energy-efficiency programmes.</p> <p>- The EPC methodology (HB2023) is administered by the government via the HBEMO platform.</p> <p>- Development of the BRP and NBRP 2026 is nationally coordinated and financed as part of Denmark's EPBD implementation.</p>
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5	France	<p>In France, the Energy Performance Certificate is known as the Diagnostic de Performance Énergétique (DPE). It is governed by the French Construction and Housing Code and detailed ministerial orders, notably the Arrêté of 31 March 2021, which define calculation methods and certification procedures. France has not yet established a formal national Building Renovation Passport (BRP), but mandatory energy audits introduced in 2023 serve a similar function by providing structured renovation pathways. DPEs are mandatory for property sales and rentals, new constructions, major renovations, and large public buildings over 250 m², with specific exemptions for seasonal use, certain historic buildings, and small dwellings. The Climate and Resilience Law reinforces the DPE's regulatory role by introducing a phased ban on renting low-performing dwellings (class G from 2025, F from 2028, and E from 2034). DPEs are generally valid for ten years if no major renovation occurs. The French EPC uses the standardized 3CL calculation method, based on building characteristics, technical systems, and standardized assumptions on occupancy and climate, with adjustments across eight national climatic zones.</p>	<p>Both residential and tertiary EPCs include two main energy indicators: primary energy consumption (kWhEP/m²/year), covering energy used for heating, cooling, domestic hot water (DHW), ventilation and lighting, and greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂/m²/year), calculated from the same energy uses according to the energy source. Residential EPCs additionally provide more detailed indicators, including final energy consumption, primary energy use by end use (heating, cooling, DHW, lighting and auxiliaries), and complementary information such as estimated annual energy costs. They also assess the energy efficiency of building envelope elements and include recommendations to improve performance, distinguishing between priority actions and optional measures. Regarding the rating system, the French EPC (DPE) applies a seven-level scale from A to G based on absolute thresholds for primary energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Since the 2021 reform, the final rating corresponds to the worse result between the energy and CO₂ indicators, even though no single official table consolidates all class thresholds.</p>	<p>In France, EPC (DPE) diagnosticians must be formally trained (minimum 56 hours), professionally accredited through COFRAC-recognized certification bodies (valid for 7 years), and insured. Candidates must pass an exam composed of theoretical and practical components. Two types of accreditation exist: without mention, allowing diagnostics in individual residential buildings, and with mention, required for collective residential buildings and non-residential (tertiary) buildings, the latter including additional training (minimum +21 hours). They are responsible for on-site inspections, applying the official calculation methodology, and submitting the certificate to ADEME, including a QR code for traceability. Non-compliance (e.g., using non-accredited professionals) may result in fines for both property owners and diagnosticians.</p>	<p>The DPE software assists calculations, but manual data entry by the certifier is required for most building characteristics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blueprints - Visual inspection of the building (on-site visit of the building is compulsory) - Technical sheets of the equipments installed - The meteorological data used in EPC calculations are standardized reference data based on historical measurements from the official national meteorological agency - For occupancy, standardized profiles are used to estimate energy use and schedules. (Energy bills can optionally supplement the assessment, although they are not mandatory and do not replace the calculated results). 	<p>EPC is a regulatory instrument that determines rental eligibility and market access due to progressive rental bans: From 2025, dwellings rated G cannot be rented; extended to F in 2028 and E in 2034.</p>	<p>At least since 2025, all DPE certificates include a unique QR code. This QR code links to a central digital record of the certificate, allowing authorities, buyers, and tenants to quickly verify its authenticity and details. It helps prevent fraud, such as the use of fake or outdated certificates in property transactions. The QR code system for French DPE certificates was introduced through amendments to the Arrêté du 31 mars 2021, notably the Arrêté du 20 juillet 2023, as part of the digital traceability system linked to the ADEME national DPE database.</p>	<p>In France, EPCs (DPE) are managed under a centralized national framework led by the Ministry for Ecological Transition, with ADEME responsible for the national DPE database and observatory. France applies a regulated but open software model: calculation software must comply with the official 3CL methodology but is developed by private providers and validated by authorities. Only COFRAC-accredited diagnosticians can issue DPEs. Certification costs are borne by building owners and set by the market. All DPEs must be registered in ADEME's national database, ensuring traceability, monitoring and quality control.</p>
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6	Germany	<p>"- EPC Procedure defined by DIN 18599, BRP defined by several BAFA EBW guidelines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - dynamic threshold defined by a separate threshold calculation of the so called reference building. This reference building has the same geometry and orientation, but standardized U-values and building services, that differ from the actual building. The final thresholds therefore result of the energy demand of this reference building, that needs to be calculated separately. Depending on renovation/new construction/use of public funding/private or public building/etc. the reference building's non renewable primary energy demands must be undercut by different percentages. - Result pages (Energy Certificate) are nationally standardized and must be displayed in the building. - No regional differences in calculation - Calculation is nationally standardized by DIN18599, but software outputs of the mere calculations and interim results can differ largely in terms of layout and extent and fall under no regulation. - types of energy use: Heating, Hot water usage, Cooling, Mechanical Ventilation, Lighting" - focused on complex non residential buildings, for residential buildings simplified calculations are possible - for substantial renovations or new buildings calculated demand certificates necessary, for other buildings also real consumption certificates exist 	<p>"- Primary Energy non renewable / m²a</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - minimal U-Values per building element category - moisture protection verification - for new buildings: summer thermal protection <p>-EPC Rating classes are derived from the absolute final energy demand per m²and year, not primary energy (A<50kWh, B<75kWh, C<100kWh, D<130kWh, ...)</p>	<p>"- qualifying professional background</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - training course of 280 - 440 hours (depending on university degree) with final exam (written, project work and oral) - yearly: 8 hours of follow up training plus min. 1 energy consultation" 	"- Blueprints	<p>- iSFP as a standardized staged-renovation roadmap. it uses one federal format and directly feeds an implementation bonus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demand- and consumption-based EPCs in parallel 	<p>- with iSFP: strong digital standardisation and quality-control layer for renovation advice</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DIN V 18599 zoned modelling for non-residential buildings allows for standardised and comparable, yet very complex and individual calculations. Especially transferable for countries whose public EPC practice is still more housing-led than complex-building-led. 	<p>One federal expert framework across residential, non-residential, and even process-related programmes</p>
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7	Greece	<p>In Greece, the official EPC is the PEA.</p> <p>The scheme is implemented under KENAK, Law 4122/2013, and related legislation.</p> <p>A valid PEA is required for building sales and leases.</p> <p>Since 1 January 2021, the energy class must appear in advertisements.</p> <p>Random quality control checks to PEAs</p>	<p>The PEA is based on calculated specific primary energy consumption (kWh/m²).</p> <p>It also reports annual total energy consumption and annual CO₂ emissions.</p>	<p>The qualification framework is defined by Presidential Decree 100/2010 and related ministerial decisions.</p> <p>Inspectors are registered in the national BuildingCert registry.</p> <p>The system distinguishes A-class and B-class licences.</p> <p>A-class inspectors are limited to residential buildings and related systems up to 100 kW, while B-class inspectors may inspect all building categories.</p>	Blueprints	<p>Integrating EPCs with digital logbooks and renovation passports creates a transferable model for turning certificates into long-term decision-support tools.</p>	<p>Digital platforms using smart-metering, BIM/digital twins, and dynamic data integration add value by enabling forecasting, benchmarking, alerts, and tailored renovation advice.</p>	<p>A centrally managed digital platform operated by a technical body, with authorised professionals responsible for data entry and mandatory record updates</p>
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8	Italy	<p>- EPC Procedure defined by UNI/TS 11300, for BRP no national model is widespread in use</p> <p>- dynamic threshold defined by a separate threshold calculation of the so called reference building. This reference building has the same geometry and orientation and building service system types, but standardized U-values, that differ from the actual building. The final thresholds therefore result of the energy demand of this reference building, that needs to be calculated separately. The reference building's non renewable primary energy demands must be met.</p> <p>- Result pages (Energy Certificate) are nationally standardized and must be displayed in the building.</p> <p>- Calculation is defined by UNI/TS 11300, outputs of the mere calculations and interim results can differ largely in terms of layout and extent depending by region and software.</p> <p>- types of energy use: Heating, Hot water usage, Cooling, Mechanical Ventilation (calculated inside heating demand), Lighting</p> <p>- focused on residential buildings</p> <p>- only calculated demand certificates exist</p>	<p>- Primary Energy non renewable must meet the ref building's demand (ref with real building service systems)</p> <p>- minimal U-Values per building element category</p> <p>- moisture protection verification</p> <p>- summer thermal protection</p> <p>- minimal ratios of renewable energy</p> <p>-EPC Rating classes are derived from the relative primary energy demand ratio of real to reference building (B=reference demand, C=1.2x reference, D= 1.5x reference). This uses another, separate calculation of the ref building: It is not calculated with the real building services systems, but with standard ones.</p>	<p>- qualifying professional background</p> <p>- must be independent from the planning phase = different person than during designing phase</p> <p>- mechanical/buildingservices/energy engineers are automatically qualified</p> <p>- for others: training course of 80 hours with final exam (written and project exercise)</p> <p>- no yearly renewal requirements</p>		<p>Federated national monitoring over regional registries: a useful model for decentralised countries because SIAPE and PNPE2 add a national layer without abolishing regional implementation.</p>	<p>PNPE2 as a digital one-stop shop: it goes beyond a certificate register by integrating EPC data with other building-efficiency datasets and user-oriented guidance tools. SIAPE public analytics and data filtering: stronger than a simple archive because it supports territorial analysis, anomaly filtering, and national monitoring of regional EPC flows</p>	<p>National APE format, regional execution, ENEA aggregation: a strong hybrid governance model for countries with subnational competences</p>
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9	Malta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EPC required for new buildings, sale, rent, and public buildings >250 m² - Uses design rating EPC (pre-construction) and asset rating EPC (as-built) - BRP mentioned only as optional, not implemented - EPC validity 10 years; new EPC required after major renovation - Exemptions: protected buildings, very small buildings <50 m², temporary structures, low-energy industrial/agricultural buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total primary energy (kWh/m²-year) - Non-renewable and renewable primary energy - CO₂ emissions (kg CO₂eq/m²-year) - Energy for heating, cooling, ventilation, DHW, lighting - On-site renewable energy production - National primary-energy factors - Primary energy rating: internal iSBEM-mt index (not published) - CO₂ rating scale: A+–G displayed on EPC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EPC issued only by registered EPB assessors (architects, mechanical/electrical/civil engineers) - Mandatory BCA-approved EPC training - Registration in the national EPB assessor register - Periodic renewal of registration as required by BCA - Mandatory refresher training possible (Reg. 25(9)(a)) - Strong quality control: random checks, required corrections, penalties, suspension or revocation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-site inspection by a registered EPB assessor (visual assessment, measurements of envelope and systems) - Building documentation: architectural drawings, technical specifications, installation manuals, renovation records - Technical data on HVAC, DHW, ventilation and lighting systems - Standardised national datasets and default values from Technical Document F and iSBEM-mt - Regulatory primary-energy factors and climatic reference data - Information provided by the building owner (photos, plans, equipment data) - In some cases, representative models for dwellings allowed by legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardised national EPC methodology (iSBEM-mt / EPRDM) - Central EPC register with mandatory digital submission - Independent control system using statistical sampling (95% confidence) - Reference-building comparison for EPC rating - Modular EPC workflow: design EPC → asset EPC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Central digital EPC registry managed by BCA - iSBEM-mt software generating a normalised EPC rating index - CO₂ A+–G scale included on EPC - Integration with EU innovation projects (e.g., CrossCert, TIMEPAC) - Technical Document F introduces stricter technical standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Centralised EPC governance under the Building and Construction Authority (BCA) - Mandatory national oversight with independent quality checks - CrossCert: Malta participates in cross-country EPC testing and harmonisation - TIMEPAC: supports digitalisation and BIM integration (indirect linkage to Malta) - QualDeEPC and iBRoad2EPC: relevant for future BRP development - Projects contribute to improving EPC accuracy, digital tools, long-term renovation planning and potential LCA/BRP integration
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10	Poland	<p>Poland is currently updating and aligning its EPC formats with the revised EPBD and is obliged to introduce energy classes and related adjustments by 29 May 2026. However, the preparation of supporting legislation and technical standards is delayed. The Building Renovation Passport (BRP) is not required by law at this stage.</p> <p>Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are mandatory mainly in the case of property sale, rental (upon signing a lease), and completion of construction, when the certificate is attached to the notification of completion or an occupancy permit application. For new single-family houses, an EPC is required for buildings larger than 70 m².</p> <p>All EPC requirements are defined exclusively at national level by relevant ministries, with no role for regional or municipal authorities. EPCs are issued by qualified experts based on technical documentation, without a mandatory on-site inspection. All certificates are stored in the Central Register of Energy Performance of Buildings (CRCEB), ensuring transparency and verification during transactions.</p>	<p>"- Primary Energy non renewable [kWh/m²/year] is used to establish the energy rating class (this is a new law, that should be implemented in Poland from 29th May 2026 - according to EC): (A+: EP≤0; A: EP ≤ 63; B: 63 < EP ≤75 ; C: 75 < EP ≤94; D: 94 < EP ≤113; E: 113 < EP ≤131; F: 131 < EP ≤150; G: > 150)</p> <p>- building also must fulfill some additional requirements e.g. minimal U-Values per building element category (e.g. for external walls U ≤ 0,20 W/(m²·K)"</p>	<p>EPC and energy audits may only be issued by a person/expert listed in the central register of authorized professionals. These are typically civil engineers or specialists with relevant education or examinations, who have full legal capacity and have not been convicted of property-related crimes.</p> <p>Requirements for EPC are provided in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ACT of August 29, 2014 on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Dz. U. 2014 poz. 1200) - ACT of August 29, 2014, on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Dz.U.2024.101) - REGULATION OF THE MINISTER OF INFRASTRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT of February 27, 2015 on the methodology for determining the energy performance of a building or part of a building and on energy performance certificates (Dz.U.2015.376) -Act of July 7, 1994 – Construction Law - Templates for energy performance certificates are provided in Regulation of the Minister of Development and Technology (Dz.U. 2023 poz. 697) 	<p>Expert issuing EPC analyses technical documentation of as built building (all available information incl. photos, blueprints, material characteristics, sources of the energy, building condition), there is no obligation to visit the building in person. The expert takes the responsibility for the EPC.</p>	<p>- Centralized digital EPC registry - but it is not public</p> <p>- EPC is valid for 10 years, unless renovations have been made that affect energy consumption—such as replacing windows, insulating the building, or changing the heat source. In such cases, a new certificate for the apartment or house must be issued</p>		
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11	Portugal	<p>In Portugal, the EPC framework was originally established by Decree-Law No. 78/2006 and has since been updated through successive legislation. Decree-Law No. 101-D/2020 transposed Directive (EU) 2018/844 into national law, while Decree-Law No. 11-D/2025 further amends the system and partially transposes EPBD 2024. Portugal is required to introduce Building Renovation Passports (BRPs) by May 2026. EPCs are mandatory for new buildings and major renovations, at both design stage and prior to obtaining an occupancy permit. They are also required for existing buildings before sale or rental, for large public buildings above 250 m², and in some cases when applying for energy-related funding or tax benefits. Certificates are typically valid for ten years, though validity may be shorter for certain large non-residential buildings. Registration requires a fee, distributed between ADENE, the Environmental Fund and DGEG. Energy performance is assessed using a legally defined methodology set out in the SCE Manual, which is regularly revised and aligned with ISO/EN standards. Calculations consider end uses such as heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting, across nine national climatic zones. Portugal operates a single national EPC system, with mandatory on-site inspection and data collected from both building documentation and physical surveys of the building and its systems.</p>	<p>Portugal's EPC includes several energy indicators, some of which differ depending on building use. Common indicators cover primary energy consumption for heating, cooling and domestic hot water, the share of renewable energy by end use, total self-consumed on-site renewable energy, total CO₂ emissions, and comparison with a reference new-compliant building. Residential EPCs include additional indicators such as useful energy needs for heating and cooling, energy for domestic hot water preparation, electricity for fans, renewable energy for regulated and other uses, and overall primary energy demand for regulated uses. Non-residential EPCs use energy efficiency indicators based on total primary energy consumption, distinguishing between regulated uses (heating, cooling, DHW) and other uses, and include renewable primary energy indicators. Buildings are assigned an EPC rating class from A+ to F. The rating is relative rather than based on fixed absolute thresholds and depends on building type, geometry, orientation and climatic zone.</p>	<p>- Decree-Law No. 102/2021 establishes the requirements for access to and the practice of the profession of technicians within the Building Energy Certification System (SCE). - To practice as a qualified technician (PQ) in Portugal's Building Energy Certification System, candidates must hold a relevant degree, have five years of professional experience, and pass an exam administered by ADENE. There are two categories: PQ-I, for residential buildings and small commercial/service buildings with HVAC systems ≤30 kW, requires a degree in architecture, engineering, or technical engineering and experience in building design or construction; PQ-II, for larger commercial/service buildings, requires a degree in engineering or technical engineering and experience in design, construction, maintenance of HVAC systems, or energy auditing. The content and evaluation criteria of the qualifying examination are defined by ministerial order Portaria No. 28/2022 In Portugal, an EPC issued by a non-certified technician is invalid, subject to fines and may expose the issuer to civil liability.</p>	<p>The DPE software assists calculations, but manual data entry by the certifier is required for most building characteristics. - Blueprints - Visual inspection of the building (on-site visit of the building is compulsory - Technical sheets of the equipments installed - The meteorological data used in EPC calculations are standardized reference data based on historical measurements from the official national meteorological agency - For occupancy, standardized profiles are used to estimate energy use and schedules. (Energy bills can optionally supplement the assessment, although they are not mandatory and do not replace the calculated results).</p>	<p>-Standardized national methodology for EPC calculations -Centralized digital EPC registry -In addition to the EPC, "Large Commercial and Service Buildings" (commercial or service buildings with a usable floor area of 1,000 m² or more—or 500 m² for shopping complexes, supermarkets, and indoor swimming pools) are required to have an up-to-date maintenance plan for the technical systems installed in the building. This plan must be prepared and submitted by a qualified technician, include detailed maintenance tasks and project assumptions, ensure proper operation, and comply with applicable regulations and manufacturer instructions. The plan is reported annually on the SCE portal and is subject to quality verification</p>	<p>-The EPC compares the building's elements, including the envelope and technical systems, with national regulation standards to verify compliance with energy performance requirements. '-It also provides recommendations for improvement measures, highlighting not only potential energy savings but also additional benefits, such as enhanced thermal or acoustic comfort, reduced maintenance, improved building safety, and a better overall building image</p>	<p>- EPC initiatives are managed by ADENE (centralized), which oversees the certification system, sets technical rules, and maintains digital platforms. - Portugal uses a closed, centralized software model for EPCs. The calculation software is open-access and freely available, . - Just certified technicians can officilay issue certificates (following standardised methodologies). -The cost of certification (and the register fee) is generally borne by building owners.</p>
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12	Slovenia	<p>-EPC of a building must be obtained by the property owners (whole building or building unit) in case of selling or renting their property for a period longer than one year.</p> <p>-An EPC must also be obtained for all new buildings.</p> <p>-An energy performance certificate (EPC) is required for buildings over 250 m² owned or used by the public sector and for buildings over 500 m² frequently visited by the public; in both cases, a valid EPC must be displayed in a visible location.</p> <p>-The energy performance certificate is valid for ten years. The client may obtain a new energy performance certificate before the ten-year period expires.</p> <p>- EPCs can be issued either as measured certificates (real consumption data) or as calculated certificates (calculated consumption data).</p> <p>-The preparation of a calculated energy performance certificate requires data on building envelope constructions, installed technical systems, and the building's dimensions.</p> <p>-The preparation of a measured energy performance certificate requires actual energy consumption data for the past three years, as well as information on building constructions, installed systems, and other data related to energy use.</p> <p>-The Building Renovation Passport is not yet a mandatory document in Slovenian legislation.</p>	<p>- Renewable primary energy (kWh/m²·year) – portion of energy demand supplied by renewable sources, such as solar thermal or photovoltaic systems.</p>	<p>Energy performance certificates (EPCs) are issued by licensed experts in accordance with the Energy Efficiency Act. Requirements to become independent energy performance certifier defined in Article 40 of the Energy Efficiency Act (ZURE).</p> <p>Following requirements needed to obtain licence and become independent energy performance certifier:</p> <p>-Appropriate educational level: engineering, architecture, spatial planning, construction or physics</p> <p>-At least 2 years of relevant work experience</p> <p>-Successfully completed a training course for independent experts at least 5 years prior to the application for a licence</p>	<p>- On-site building inspection conducted by a certified Energy Consultant, including measurements, visual assessment, and verification of construction elements and technical systems.</p> <p>- Building documentation such as architectural drawings, technical specifications, renovation records, installation manuals.</p>	<p>-Use of both calculated and measured EPCs. Measured EPC provide a more realistic view of the building's energy performance and operating costs.</p> <p>-Standardized national methodology for EPC calculations</p> <p>-Centralized digital EPC registry</p>	<p>-Slovenia has a central electronic database of all issued EPCs, managed by the Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Energy of Slovenia</p> <p>'-EPC assessors use standardized national calculation tools aligned with national building-energy methodology</p> <p>'-EPCs are generated and issued electronically through an online platform</p> <p>'-Public accessibility of key EPC data (market transparency, real-estate decision making, swareness factor)</p>	<p>-The EPC framework in Slovenia is regulated by national legislation, mainly the Energy Efficiency Act and related implementing regulations</p> <p>-The system is managed at national level, with the responsible ministry overseeing the legal framework, methodology, and registry</p> <p>-EPCs are issued by electronically independent experts, who must meet professional qualification requirements.</p> <p>-A central electronic registry is used for the registration, storage, and verification of issued EPCs.</p> <p>-Financing is mainly market-based, meaning that building owners pay for the preparation of the EPC when it is required.</p> <p>-Public authorities support the framework through supervision, licensing, and digital infrastructure</p>
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13	Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EPC Procedure is regulated by Royal Decree No. 390/2021 - EPC is required when selling or renting a property, when advertising it for sale or rent, for newly constructed buildings and for those undergoing major renovation, as well as for public buildings. It also applies to non-residential buildings exceeding 500 m2 and to properties subject to the Technical Building Inspection (ITE) (residential buildings more than 45 years old). - Valid for a period of ten years (if a property receives a G rating, the certificate's validity is limited to five years) - Conducted by a qualified technician (for existing building, the technician will undertake an on-site inspection to collect real data) - Data of the building (geometry, composition of the envelope, energy systems, renewable energy, solar protection) must be entered into an official energy simulation programme - Result compared to a reference building with the same characteristics - Climatic datasets established in the Technical Building Code - BRP is not yet mandatory in Spain but improvement proposals for existing buildings are. 	<p>Main indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO₂ annual emissions [kg CO₂/m²·year] - Primary non-renewable Energy Use [kWh/m²·year] <p>Complementary indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO₂ annual emissions [kg CO₂/m²·year] disaggregated by services - CO₂ annual emissions [kg CO₂/m²·year] disaggregated by electricity consumption - Primary non-renewable Energy Use [kWh/m²·year] disaggregated by services - Annual energy demand for heating [kWh/m²·year] - Annual energy demand for cooling [kWh/m²·year] <p>Result is a scale from A (most efficient) to G (least efficient).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qualifications that are automatically recognized: competent technician are those that enable the capacity to design building projects and to direct and supervise the execution of construction works - Other university degrees outside the energy field: that must be supplemented with 1 or 2 modules (Environmental Sciences, Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Statistics, Computer Engineering, etc.) - Vocational training and professional certifications: require supplementary training (1 and/or 2 modules), depending on whether they can demonstrate prior competencies in energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-site inspections of the building (to collect real data) - Technical datasheets of the equipments installed - Climate datasets and occupancy are standardized data from CTE (Technical Building Code) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardised national methodology for EPC calculations - Centralized digital EPC registry - In cases where a building receives a G rating, the certificate's validity is limited to five years - Reference-building comparison for EPC rating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EPC compares the building's components, including the envelope and technical systems, with national regulatory standards to verify compliance with energy performance requirements. - Building's energy consumption report carried out in Catalonia to facilitate the interpretation of the EPC. It shows comparisons of energy consumption with other buildings, contribution of CO₂ emissions by each system, comparisons of thermal Transmittance (U-value) with the maximum values permitted and some additional information. - Add-on for generating an energy audit in CE3X enables the generation of an energy audit directly from the certification process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Methodologies for authorising and registering the official label vary by region. Each autonomous community operates its own platform, procedures, and fees for the validation of the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) - EPCs are issued by licensed independent experts, who must meet professional qualification requirements. - The cost of certification (and the register fee) is generally assumed by building owners.
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More information: www.iebra.eu

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